

Testing a model for emergent spinor wave functions explaining elementary particles, gauge interactions and fundamental constants

Christoph Schiller *

Motion Mountain Research, 81827 Munich, Germany

(14 September 2025)

Abstract

A geometric model for wave functions, which also allows deducing the standard model of particle physics, space, and general relativity, is tested against observations. The model is based on Dirac's proposal to describe spin 1/2 particles as tethered objects. Dirac's proposal is condensed into a fundamental principle that defines the quantum of action at the Planck scale. Consequently, quantum particles are modelled as fluctuating rational 3d tangles consisting of strands with Planck radius whose crossing switches are observable. Densities of tangle crossings are shown to have all the properties of wave functions and to follow the Dirac equation, as Battey-Pratt and Racey showed in 1980. Tangles of strands appear to provide the only known model for the ab initio emergence of spinor wave functions, quantum field theory, decoherence, and quantum measurement.

Several consequences of the strand tangle model go beyond quantum field theory. Classifying the possible rational 3d tangle topologies and classifying their deformations with Reidemeister's theorem appear to provide the only known ab initio derivation of the observed elementary particle spectrum, of the gauge interactions, of the principle of least action, and of the fundamental constants. First ab initio estimates for particle masses are provided.

The strand tangle model yields more than 60 tests of quantum theory and particle physics. All tests agree with observations. The fundamental principle of the model also visualizes qubits, deduces general relativity, provides predictions about relativistic quantum gravity, settles several open issues in quantum field theory, and proves that the standard model of particle physics is unique, simple, and elegant.

Keywords

Origin of spinor wave functions; origin of elementary particles; origin of gauge interactions; origin of the standard model of particle physics; origin of the fundamental constants.

* cs@motionmountain.net

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Introduction: describing nature with high precision and a single principle

A description of nature based on the Planck limits \hbar , c , $c^4/4G$ and $k \ln 2$ automatically contains quantum theory, special relativity, general relativity and thermodynamics. This result has been proven in many publications listed and summarized in the following.

However, the Planck limits alone do *not* explain the appearance and the details of spinor wave functions, elementary particles, gauge interactions, the principle of least action, and the Lagrangian of particle physics. Likewise, the Planck limits alone do *not* explain the uniqueness and the values of the elementary particle masses, the coupling constants, the mixing angles, and the number of dimensions. [Deducing these aspects of nature requires tangles of strands with Planck radius](#), and especially their topology and their three-dimensional shapes.

[Part I of the present article begins by showing that observations about particles and black holes require a description of nature and of quantum theory based on fluctuating strands of Planck radius](#). The strand tangle model is based on the counterintuitive notion, due to Dirac [1, 2], that every particle in nature is *tethered*, i.e., connected with unobservable strands to the cosmological horizon. Dirac demonstrated the idea for matter particles with the arrangement illustrated in Figure 1. The scissors represent the spin 1/2 particle and the chair the cosmological horizon – though in nature, also particles and horizons consist of strands. 50 years later, Battey-Pratt and Racey [3] deduced Dirac's equation from Dirac's trick. Shortly afterwards, Kauffman [4, 5] suggested to formalize Dirac's trick with a topological definition of Planck's quantum of action. At the same time, it became clear that black hole entropy is also due to strands, and that they have a Planck-scale cross-section. Together, these results are condensed into a fundamental principle that defines all quantum effects.

Part II derives wave functions, superpositions, Hilbert spaces, entanglement, decoherence and quantum measurements from the fundamental principle. Part III uses the fundamental principle to derive the Schrödinger equation, antiparticles, spinors, the Dirac equation, the principle of least action, and a first set of experimental tests. For the first time, all observations about wave functions are derived from the Planck scale.

Figure 1: In his lectures, Dirac demonstrated the properties of spin $1/2$, a pure quantum effect, using a pair of scissors tied to a chair with strands or with a belt. Any tethered object, such as a pair of scissors, returns to the original state only after a double rotation, but not after a single rotation. Tethered objects and spin $1/2$ particles thus behave in the same way. The figure is inspired by a drawing of Penrose, who attended Dirac's lectures [1]. The details of Dirac's trick are illustrated in Figure 2.

Part IV shows that several differences from quantum theory arise from strands. Only these differences make strands worth exploring. The fundamental principle is shown to restrict the possible elementary particles to the observed ones, to derive the particle quantum numbers, to restrict the possible gauge interactions, to derive their gauge groups, and to determine masses, coupling strengths and mixing angles. In total, strands imply the complete standard model of particle physics, without any deviation, and yield more than 60 numbered experimental predictions, including predictions about neutrino masses, supersymmetry, and dark matter. So far, all tests agree with all observations. In particular, the differences between strands and quantum theory agree with observations and solve the open problems in quantum theory, in quantum field theory, and in the standard model of particle physics. The appendices cover a few intriguing aspects of strands, from general relativity to qubits, preons, strings, the Yang-Mills millennium problem, and the impossibility of an axiomatic approach to fundamental physics.

In short, – all sections end with a summary paragraph that begins with '*In short*' – the article tells how a single fundamental principle **deduced from the observation of spin and the properties of black holes** yields the strand tangle model that leads to the emergence of spinors, Dirac's equation, elementary particles, gauge interactions, the Lagrangian of the standard model with massive neutrinos, and the fundamental constants, including unique coupling constants and elementary particle masses. The lack of alternative Lagrangians is shown. Experimental tests and predictions are deduced. All agree with all observations. All open questions about quantum theory and the standard model are answered. No other model appears to provide these results.

Part I: A geometric model for emergent quantum theory

1 Nature provides a limit for every observable

In 1899, Planck discovered the quantum of action $\hbar = h/2\pi$ while exploring light [6]. Around 1910, Bohr summarized quantum theory [7] as the sum of all consequences of the smallest measurable action value \hbar . The lower limit given by the quantum of action is observed to be invariant across nature. The action limit is confirmed by all real experiments and all thought experiments ever carried out.

In 1905, Einstein derived special relativity from the invariant maximum energy speed c observed in nature [8]. The *principle* of maximum speed, together with all its consequences, was confirmed in all real experiments and thought experiments ever carried out.

In the years around 1926, applying the *principle* of the quantum of action \hbar to electrons led Schrödinger and many others to develop the concept of the wave function, to describe its evolution, and to use it to describe measurements. In 1928, Dirac incorporated spin 1/2 and the energy speed limit c and introduced spinors. Dirac's equation for electrons and Planck's description of light led to quantum electrodynamics, which agrees with all experiments ever carried out.

Around the year 1973, Elizabeth Rauscher discovered that general relativity implies a maximum force [9]. Around the year 2000, the independent work by Gibbons and by the author showed that Einstein's field equations can be deduced from the *principle* of maximum force $c^4/4G$ or the *principle* of maximum power $c^5/4G$ [10–14]. If preferred, one can also start from the equivalent *principle* of maximum mass to length ratio $c^2/4G$ [15] or from the *principle* of maximum mass flow rate $c^3/4G$. All these limits are related to black holes. All these invariant limits agree with all thought experiments and all real experiments ever carried out [10–51]. So does general relativity.

Based on Planck's discovery of the Boltzmann constant k [6], also thermodynamics can be deduced from an invariant limit, namely from the *principle* of smallest observable system entropy $k \ln 2$ [52–57]. The entropy limit and thermodynamics agree with all thought experiments and all real experiments ever carried out. Together with the previous limits, the entropy limit allows deriving Bekenstein's entropy bound and black hole entropy.

Around the year 2000, the mentioned results allowed summarizing quantum theory as the consequence of the smallest action \hbar , special relativity as the consequence of maximum speed c , general relativity as the consequence of maximum force $c^4/4G$, and thermodynamics as the consequence of the smallest system entropy $k \ln 2$. Ideally, these limits are called *corrected* Planck limits because, traditionally, the quantity c^4/G is called the Planck force k the Planck entropy. However, an often overlooked factor 4 is part of nature's force limit $c^4/4G$ [10, 14]; the factor $\ln 2$ disappears in many expressions of thermodynamics [57–59].

As a consequence of observations, *all corrected Planck units are limits of nature*. In particular, the limits include the minimum length $\sqrt{4G\hbar/c^3}$ and the minimum time $\sqrt{4G\hbar/c^5}$. Intervals smaller than these two values cannot be measured, cannot be observed, have no effect, and thus do not exist in nature [60–71]. For this reason, those Planck limits that are *lower* limits are also minimum measurement errors. Nature *prevents* vanishing measurement errors.

Several Planck limits – the Planck mass, the Planck energy and the Planck momentum – are valid only for a single elementary particle because the condition is used to derive them. For example, the Planck mass is derived from the limit size D of a mass m in general relativity

$$D \geq \frac{4Gm}{c^2} \quad (1)$$

and from the limit size D of an elementary particle given by the reduced Compton wavelength

$$D \leq \frac{\hbar}{mc} . \quad (2)$$

This limit is only valid for elementary particles, not for composed or everyday particles or objects. The two size limits lead to a mass limit m of an elementary particle given by

$$m \leq \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{4G}} . \quad (3)$$

thus that elementary particles are less massive than half the Planck mass. This mass inequality is at the basis of the *maximon* concept introduced long ago by Markov [72] and of other proposals. Similarly, also the Planck energy and momentum are upper limits for elementary particles only.

Modern physics predicts that every search for observations or effects *beyond* the corrected Planck limits will fail [73]. Indeed, no known observation contradicts the corrected Planck limits, despite intensive searches in special relativity [74], in quantum field theory and particle physics [75], in general relativity [14], in quantum gravity [76] and in thermodynamics [57].

Not all Planck limits are equal. The speed limit c is observable: some systems realize it, such as light and gravitational waves, and other systems approach it quite closely, such as particles in accelerators or cosmic rays. The quantum of action \hbar is observable: some systems realize it, such as trapped electrons, and other systems approach it quite closely, such as in the photoelectric effect or the Frank-Hertz experiment. The force limit $c^4/4G$ is observable: some systems realize it, such as black holes or gravitational horizons, and other systems approach it quite closely, such as colliding black holes. The *non-relativistic* quantum gravity limit $4G\hbar$ is observable: it is realized in the quantum states of cold neutrons in gravity [77–79]. Also the limit \hbar/c is observable: it is realized in all observations of wave-particle duality.

In contrast, the Planck limits of *relativistic* quantum gravity – those containing c , $4G$ as well as \hbar , such as the corrected Planck length, Planck time or, for single elementary particles, the Planck energy – are neither realized nor approached in nature. Nature *prevents* reaching the limits of relativistic quantum gravity. All experiments and observations about relativistic quantum gravity are several or even many orders of magnitude away from the limit values. For example, measurements of the electron dipole moment are a factor 10^3 away from the corrected Planck length [80, 81]. Measurements of elementary particle energy in cosmic rays are more than a factor 10^7 away from the corrected Planck energy [82]. Measured temperatures, such as in quark-gluon plasmas, are a factor of 10^{20} away from the Planck temperature. Measurements of time intervals, such as the Higgs boson lifetime, are a factor of 10^{20} away from the corrected Planck time [75]. The Planck electric field limit is unattainable because of the Schwinger limit, which is over 10^{40} times lower. The general reason for the unattainability of the relativistic quantum gravity limits is the existence of minimum uncertainties and minimum measurement errors, in particular those for length, time, area, and volume [60–71].

In short, the corrected Planck limits express that *no trans-Planckian effect* of any kind exists or is observable in nature [83]. In addition,

- ▷ In experiments, nature allows reaching and observing the *simple* limits c , \hbar and $4G$ as well as the limits due to combinations of *two* simple ones, such as $c^4/4G$, \hbar/c , $4G\hbar$.
- ▷ The minimum uncertainties and the minimum measurement errors *prevent* from reaching and from observing any combination of all *three* constants, such as the minimum area $4G\hbar/c^3$ or the maximum energy density or maximum pressure $c^7/16G^2\hbar$.

Any *correct* description of nature must reproduce these observations. Few do.

2 Nature's limits forbid points, equations of motion and Lagrangians

Experiments show that nature is made of particles and space. Therefore, the search for a theory of emergent quantum mechanics, which describes the emergence of particles and wave functions, is closely tied to the search for a unified theory that includes relativistic quantum gravity and describes the emergence of space. Both searches are strongly restricted by nature's limits.

In nature, evolving systems are described by physical action. The action W of a system can be *dimensionally* rewritten as

$$W = F l t = \frac{F l^2}{v} \quad \text{or as} \quad W = E t = m c^2 t = \frac{m}{l} c l^2, \quad (4)$$

where F is a force, l is a length, v is a speed, E is an energy and m is a mass. The two expressions can be used to insert the maximum speed $v \leq c$, the minimum action $W \geq \hbar$ and, for general relativity, either the maximum force $F \leq c^4/4G$ or the maximum mass per length ratio $m/l \leq c^2/4G$ of black holes. After insertion and solving for l , both expressions for the action then yield the same statement:

- ▷ Nature limits length intervals, length uncertainties, and length measurement errors:

$$l \geq \sqrt{\frac{4G\hbar}{c^3}} \approx 3 \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m} . \quad (5)$$

So far, no experiment disagrees. In other words, the domain of nature where maximum speed, maximum force, and the quantum of action play a role at the same time – the domain of relativistic quantum gravity – is characterized by a *minimum length*. The minimum length is twice the Planck length [73]. The minimum length is also the *minimum length measurement error* [60–71]. Smaller lengths, distances, or measurement errors *cannot* be achieved or observed. Likewise,

- ▷ Nature's lower limits for area, volume and time cannot be achieved.

Again, each of these Planck limits is also a minimum measurement *error*. Again, all experiments agree. The numerous conceptual problems resulting from the fuzziness of time are not discussed in the following, because they do not lead to additional experimental tests.

Historically, scientists took two millennia to define space as a continuous set of points and to get used to working with real numbers as coordinates. Poking gentle fun at thinkers who challenged continuity and questioned the infinitely small, such as Zeno of Elea, is a part of modern science. [In full contrast, the minimum length implies:](#)

- ▷ Nature has no point-like physical observables.

Point-like quantities cannot be detected or measured. Therefore, point-like quantities – including point particles, Dirac's δ distributions, singularities of any type, or instants of time – *do not exist in nature*. Indeed, no point-like observable has ever been observed. In other words, *every point-like concept is an approximation*. Therefore, no point-like observable or concept can play a role in the description of nature. Points and instants are the oldest errors of fundamental science.

The lack of points and the minimum length measurement error have drastic consequences.

- ▷ Space and time *cannot consist of points, cannot be continuous and cannot be discrete*.

The minimum length implies that continuity, derivatives, differentials, but also discrete points and discrete instants of time do not exist in nature. All these concepts are only *approximate*: they are due to the averaging of some randomly fluctuating substrate. The minimum intrinsic uncertainties and the minimum measurement errors in nature also imply that an *equation* can never be valid precisely, i.e., can never be tested without error or doubt. In relativistic quantum gravity, because of the minimum measurement errors, two measured quantities – the two sides of an equation – cannot be shown to be equal by any experiment.

▷ No unified theory that includes relativistic quantum gravity can make use of equations.

For this reason, no unified equation has ever been deduced or proposed. A second argument confirms the conclusion. Any *unified* equation of motion and any *unified* Lagrangian would have to contain some fundamental fields or observables. The origin of these fields would have to be defined. However, a unified theory that includes relativistic quantum gravity must explain the origin of all fields and observables it uses. This is impossible in a description based on a Lagrangian [84].

▷ No unified theory that includes relativistic quantum gravity can be based on a Lagrangian.

In a unified description of nature, all fields – particles, electric, magnetic, strong, weak, gravitational – must be *emergent*. Therefore, all equations of motion and all Lagrangians are approximate and are due to averaging. Because of the minimum measurement errors, any description of fundamental constituents must be *statistical* and must involve *many* constituents of some randomly fluctuating substrate. The additional consequence that nature cannot have exact parts is explored in Appendices A and G.

The minimum length measurement error implies that the idea that points *exist* in nature needs to be discarded. Instead, a statistical description is necessary. The minimum length measurement error implies that space is not made of points, but of a fluctuating substrate. Nevertheless, using points to describe nature is *useful*, even though points are approximations that have no basis in observations. Using points to describe nature is also *necessary*, as we have no other option at our disposal to describe observations. But we should always remember that points have no basis in reality. The same limitation holds for every “continuous” physical observable. Continuity does not apply to nature, but it is both useful and necessary for its description. But near the Planck scale, measurement results are not points on the line of real numbers, but are fluctuating and fuzzy.

Because of the minimum length and the lack of continuity, any unified description must deduce all known equations of physics *without* the use of more fundamental equations.

▷ Unification means: deducing equations from no equation.

History shows that such a program can be realized. Planck’s discovery of the limit for action W

$$W \geq \hbar \approx 10^{-34} \text{ Js} \quad (6)$$

led to quantum theory and the derivation of Schrödinger’s equation and its Lagrangian. The discovery that the speed v is limited by

$$v \leq c \approx 3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s} \quad (7)$$

led to special relativity and, together with the previous limit, to Dirac’s equation and its Lagrangian. Likewise, the discovery of the smallest system entropy

$$S \geq k \ln 2 \approx 10^{-23} \text{ J/K} \quad (8)$$

can be used to deduce the laws of thermodynamics [57]. Similarly, the discovery by Rauscher, de Sabbata, Sivaram, and many others of maximum force

$$F \leq \frac{c^4}{4G} \approx 3 \cdot 10^{43} \text{ N} \quad (9)$$

led to the subsequent discovery by Gibbons and by the author that the maximum force can be used to derive general relativity with its field equations and Lagrangian [10–14]. It is thus possible to deduce a large part of modern physics from simple inequalities. The remaining task is to deduce the complete standard model of particle physics from such inequalities.

In short, because of the minimum length, fundamental Planck-scale physics cannot have points, instants, equations, or Lagrangians. The only way left to describe nature and observations at the Planck scale is the usual approach of fundamental science. First, a *fundamental principle* is distilled. The fundamental principle contains only simple inequalities involving Planck limits, together with precisely and clearly defined concepts. Then, all possible consequences are *logically deduced* from the fundamental principle. History shows that these consequences can be equations even if the principle does not contain any. Because of the minimum length, equations are intrinsically approximate and can only be valid far away from Planck scales. Every deduced consequence and every deduced equation is tested against all observations. **If a test fails, the proposed fundamental principle is falsified.** If a test is positive, the next test is performed.

3 Black holes require strands

In nature, black holes are limit cases for curved space *and* for densely packed particles. Numerous observations have confirmed both statements and thus confirmed the equivalence of the two descriptions [85, 86]. Therefore, the constituents of black holes are also the constituents of space and of particles. Thus, both the search for relativistic quantum gravity and the search for emergent quantum mechanics require finding the *common constituents* of black holes, space, particles, and wave functions. Thus, they can be called the constituents of nature.

Black holes yield many details about the constituents of nature. The expression for black hole entropy S contains the minimum length in the form of the minimum area $4G\hbar/c^3$ [87, 88]:

$$\frac{S}{k} = \frac{c^3}{4G\hbar} A . \quad (10)$$

Here, k is Boltzmann's constant, A is the surface of the black hole, and the factor 4 is due to the black hole limits. Even though experiments have never confirmed the expression, its order of magnitude is without doubt, as it follows from the limits of nature [57]. Because black holes have entropy, they are composed of constituents that *fluctuate*. Because black holes have *finite* entropy, they are composed of a *finite* number of discrete constituents. Because the black hole entropy contains the *minimum area*, the common constituents of space and particles have an effective cross-section given by the minimum area. Because space and wave functions are *extended* and reach the cosmological horizon, this also holds for the common constituents. **Because black hole entropy is proportional to their surface, black holes are made of filiform constituents [89]. The common constituents of particles and space thus have Planck radius, fluctuate, and reach the cosmological horizon: the common constituents are filiform.**

The minimum length and the expression for black hole entropy eliminate many alternative types of fundamental constituents [73]. In particular, minimum length is *in contrast* with space

lattices, fractals, additional dimensions, non-commutative space, singularities, conformal symmetry, holography, higher dimensions, space-time foam, categories, spatial lattices, supersymmetry, supergravity, conformal gravity, conformal field theory, anti-de Sitter space, de Sitter space, twistors, doubly special relativity, Wick rotation approaches, spin networks, and with any continuous space that contains additional discrete or continuous mathematical structures. Minimum length eliminates many approaches to relativistic quantum gravity [90]. Black hole entropy further eliminates compact constituents, filiform constituents of finite length, and filiform constituents that are branched or knotted. The minimum length and black entropy are also incompatible with knots, bands, branched structures, networks, graphs, or ribbons. [All such structures change the value of black hole entropy.](#) The common constituents *can only be filiform.*

In the 1990s, it was common lore that filiform constituents explain black hole entropy, as told by Weber [89]. For a recent approach, see Verlinde and Visser [91]. In general relativity, filiform constituents have been explored by Botta-Cantcheff [92] and independently and extensively by Carlip [93]. In relativistic quantum gravity, an interesting approach is the use of causal sets, as explored by Sorkin and by Bombelli [94]; filiform constituents can be seen as a specific realization of causal sets. The behaviour of the spatial complement of filiform constituents, thus the motion of the empty space between them, was investigated in detail by Asselmeyer-Maluga [95, 96]; in this approach, a universe is made of space only, albeit an intricately shaped one. The recent bit threads are discussed in Appendix B.

[It can be shown that counting the configurations of filiform constituents allows reproducing black hole entropy, black hole temperature, and black hole mass \[58, 59\]. This allows reproducing Jacobson’s argument \[97\] and deriving Einstein’s field equations of general relativity \[98, 99\]. Therefore, strands yield the Lagrangian of general relativity and describe gravity.](#)

[In short, black hole entropy strongly suggests that black holes are made of filiform constituents.](#)

4 Fermions require strands and a fundamental principle

Not only are black holes and space made of filiform constituents, also matter is. Dirac’s scissor trick of Figure 1 – also called the *string trick* or the *belt trick* – can be extended to a situation where the fermion is *also* made of strands, as shown in Figure 2. Dirac’s trick from 1929, which goes back to Magnus [100], captures the basic properties of spin 1/2: the original situation reappears after a rotation by 4π – keeping the observable particle, scissor or belt buckle *fixed* but *moving* the (assumed unobservable) belt or strand tethers around. In contrast, the original situation does *not* reappear after a rotation by 2π . In experiments, after a rotation by 2π , the sign of the wave function of a spin 1/2 particle is changed. The sign returns to the original value only after a rotation by 4π . The only difference between a tethered system before and after a rotation by 2π is the sign of the tether crossings, as illustrated in Figure 3. If a system is *not* tethered, *no* difference is detectable between the situation before and after a rotation by 2π . Tethers, or strands, are the *only* possible visualization of spin 1/2 in three dimensions. As Dirac explained to Gardner [2], his trick also demonstrates that a positive spin value smaller than $\hbar/2$ is not possible. In simple terms, independently of black holes, *spin 1/2 proves that in nature, all matter is tethered.*

A variant of Dirac’s trick is the *fermion trick*, illustrated in Figure 4. It describes the basic property of fermions: after a double particle exchange, two tethered fermions return to the original situation – but not after a single exchange. Again, crossing changes are observable through their effects on the sign of wave functions, even if the tethers themselves are unobservable. Again, no other visualization of fermion behaviour exists. The effects of tethers have been visualized in

Dirac's belt trick or string trick:**Double tethered particle rotation is like no rotation.**

Figure 2: Top: Dirac's *string trick* or *belt trick* shows that a *double* rotation, by 4π , of a tethered, indivisible particle – here an oriented tangle core – is equivalent to no rotation at all. In contrast, a *single* rotation by just 2π does *not* allow untangling to occur. Dirac's trick reproduces observations as long as the tethers – *any number* of them – are allowed to fluctuate, to untangle and to remain unobservable, whereas their crossing switches are assumed to be observable. Non-trivial cores made of 2 tangled strands therefore exhibit the properties that characterize spin $1/2$ particles. As a result, a tethered particle can *rotate continuously*. Careful observation also shows that Dirac's trick couples rotation and *displacement* of chiral tethered cores. The coupling of rotation frequency and displacement determines the inertial mass, as discussed in Section 37. The twists in the tethers are virtual gravitons and determine gravitational mass. Bottom: the particle *tangle* leads to a probability density and a phase, using the ideas from Figure 12.

numerous internet videos. Examples are found in references [101–105]. The fermion trick even works if the two fermions are connected directly. For example, the two ends of a belt, taken to represent the two particles, reproduce the fermion trick: after one exchange, the belt is twisted, but after two exchanges, it can be untwisted. *The fermion trick confirms that in nature, all matter is tethered.*

Dirac's trick and the fermion trick were the first hints that matter should be described with extended, filiform, *unobservable* constituents, for which *only crossing switches* are observable. Fifty years later, in 1980, Battey-Pratt and Racey showed that unobservable tethers imply the full free Dirac equation [3]. Their argument is presented below. Thus, Battey-Pratt and Racey proved that *Dirac's trick implies Dirac's equation*. In simple words, *Dirac's equation proves that in*

Figure 3: Top: Dirac's trick is based on the idea that a *crossing switch* of tethers leads to an *observable* change in the sign of the wave function. The figure shows that a crossing switch is related to a tangle core rotation by 2π .

Bottom: Simplifying, a crossing switch is the sign change of a crossing. In the strand tangle model, this sign change is *observable* even though the tethers themselves are *unobservable*

nature, all fermions are tethered.

Photons and their wave-particle duality have been visualized as helically deformed filaments [106]. A similar visualization that includes \hbar and that resembles the model for fermions is given later on, in Section 13. In simple words, *photons are tethered.*

In summary, all particles are tethered. However, tethers are not observed in nature. The tethers must be unmeasurably thin. In agreement with the results from black hole entropy and with the measurement limits deduced above, one deduces *tethers must have Planck radius*. This implies that particles, space, and horizons are completely made of filiform constituents of Planck radius. These constituents are called *strands* in the following.

Dirac's trick implies that *crossing switches* are observable – even if the tethers themselves and their crossings are not. In Dirac's trick – and the rest of this article – strands never intersect. For strands with Planck radius, the lack of intersections visualizes the minimum length. All strand crossings seen in diagrams are *apparent* or *skew* and are recognizable as 'crossings' only in a two-dimensional projection. In three dimensions, 'crossings' are defined and recognizable by the shortest distance between two strand segments in a general configuration, i.e., for which the strands are not parallel and not lying in a common plane. A *crossing switch*, or *crossing change*, is the change of *sign of a crossing*, i.e., the change of which strand passes under the other. Figure 3 shows: because of the Dirac trick, *crossing changes of tethers are related to \hbar* . This connection was most clearly stated by Kauffman in the 1980s [4, 5]. In simple words, *Dirac's trick implies that the quantum of action \hbar is due to a crossing switch*. This is illustrated Figure 5. The result

The fermion trick: Double tethered particle exchange is no exchange.

The trick also works if some or all the strands *connect* one tangle core to the other core.

Figure 4: The *fermion trick* shows that a *double* particle exchange of tethered non-trivial cores is equivalent to no exchange at all. In contrast, a *single* particle exchange does *not* allow untangling. The fermion trick works if the tethers – *any number* of them, even if some of them connect the two cores directly – are allowed to fluctuate and untangle. Again, tethers are assumed to be unobservable, whereas crossing switches are assumed to be observable. Indivisible tangle cores made of several tethers thus show all the properties that characterize fermions.

is so important that it is called the *fundamental principle*. It will lead to the definition of wave functions based on crossings, as explored below.

One attempt to relate \hbar to topology, by Ross [107], is found in the literature. So far, no other approach that agrees with all observations and includes general relativity has led to a model for wave functions, for gauge interactions and for fundamental constants.

If everything in nature is composed of strands, what exactly are particles? The straightforward conjecture that particles might be modelled as *open knots*, i.e., as knots in infinitely long tethers, as illustrated in Figure 6, is unsuccessful. Despite intense attempts in this and similar directions [90, 109–124], open knots, prime knots, closed knots, bands, branched structures, loops, networks or graphs do *not* fully explain the particle spectrum or the appearance of wave functions. Above all, none of these topological structures explains gauge interactions or particle reactions.

Between 2008 and 2014, it became clear that modelling elementary particles as *rational 3d tangles* – i.e., as unknotted tangles – *does* explain wave functions, the particle spectrum, particle reactions and particle interactions. The mathematical concept of a rational 3d tangle – a three-dimensional braid – is illustrated in Figure 6. As shown in Part IV, the classification of rational 3d tangles yields the spectrum of elementary particles; the classification of strand deformations using the three Reidemeister moves yields the three known gauge interactions [125, 126]; rational 3d tangles yield the complete Lagrangian of the standard model with massive Dirac neutrinos

The fundamental, Planck-scale principle of the strand tangle model

Figure 5: The *fundamental principle* of the strand tangle model, deduced from Dirac’s trick, describes the simplest observation possible in nature: a *fundamental event*. In the tangle model, a fundamental event occurs at the Planck scale and is *almost* point-like. Every fundamental event results from a *strand crossing switch*. A crossing switch is the *simplest* observable process in nature; it defines \hbar as the unit of the physical action W . The *crossing switch* is a deformation of strands in space, illustrated by the circling arrows. The deformation results, for example, from rotating the two segments on the right-hand side against the two segments on the left-hand side, around the west-east axis in the paper plane. The *location* of the crossing is defined by the centre of the shortest distance between the two strand segments. The strands, best imagined as fully elastic threads, have a Planck-size radius, are not observable, are uncuttable and are impenetrable. The Planck length and Planck time describe the most localized and the most rapid crossing switch possible. As shown in the text, the fundamental principle implies the indeterminacy relation, wave functions, particle tangles, the canonical commutation relation, the Dirac equation, the three gauge interactions, measurements via electromagnetism, the standard model, general relativity, qubits, the lack of parts in nature and the lack of axioms in physics.

[58, 59, 125–130], without any modification, and in agreement with all observations of particle physics. [The fundamental principle describes particle physics.](#)

In short, the results by Planck, Einstein, Dirac, Battey-Pratt and Racey, Rauscher, Kauffman, and Gibbons suggest that three ingredients are *necessary* to describe all observations in nature: corrected Planck limits, unobservable strands connecting everything, and observable crossing switches defining \hbar . These three ingredients are combined in the fundamental principle of the strand tangle model. The rest of this article explains why and how crossing switches of strands are observable, how rational 3d tangles of strands lead to wave functions, particles, quantum fields, interactions, and the fundamental constants, [and how the model can be tested.](#)

5 Rotating and orbiting quantum particles emerge from tethers

Dirac’s trick implies that a tethered particle can *rotate continuously*. This is best experienced in animations. An animation showing the continuous spinning of a particle with six tethers has been produced by Hise [101]; still images are shown in Figure 7. An animation of a spinning particle with two attached belts, corresponding to four tethers, was produced by Martos [102]; still images from the animation are shown in Figure 8. Animations of rotating particles with large numbers of tethers are also available on the internet [104, 105]. In other words, if unobservable tethers can fluctuate, tethered particles can rotate forever, without any obstacles. The relation between spin 1/2 and rotation is not new and was regularly pointed out in the past [131]. In simple words, spin can be visualized as the rotation of tethered cores.

Rational 3d tangles – or 3d braids

Knotted tangles

Links

Knots

Figure 6: The differences and similarities between *rational 3d tangles* – or 3d braids – knotted tangles, links, and knots are illustrated. *Rational 3d tangles* are formed by braiding their tethers, shown with dashed lines. In contrast, *knotted tangles* cannot be formed in this way. Equivalently, rational tangles, unlike knotted tangles, can be disentangled by moving their tethers in space. Rational 3d tangles owe their name, for the case of two strands, to their close relation to rational numbers [108].

A related statement can be made for systems consisting of *two* particles. The fermion trick implies that two tethered particles can *orbit each other continuously*. Martos published a video showing the fermion behaviour of two tethered particles [103]; still images from the video are shown in Figure 9. For example, Figure 9 can be seen as visualizing an electron orbiting a proton in a hydrogen atom. In particular, the video shows that two tethered particles can *orbit each other forever* – if tethers are allowed to fluctuate. Again, the number of tethers can be arbitrary large. In other words, even many electrons orbiting nuclei can be visualized as *tangles orbiting tangles*.

The mentioned properties imply that the tethers of two typical quantum particles do not disturb each other, as long as strands are unobservable and fluctuating, are infinitely flexible, and have no fixed length, no tension, no torsion, and no mass. This is also true for more than two particles. As a consequence, the many tethers filling empty space lead to *no* interaction between distant particles – at usual energies and scales. Exceptions due to entanglement, gauge interactions, and virtual particles are discussed below.

In the strand tangle model, every quantum particle is a *tangle tethered to the cosmological horizon* in which the strands fluctuate continuously. Together with the definition of \hbar as a crossing switch, by modelling quantum particles with unobservable tethers, Dirac deduced several results. Some are related by Gardner in reference [2].

Figure 7: The particle rotation for a (free and moving) lepton made possible by Dirac's trick can be visualized with the animation produced by Jason Hise, available at [101]. The rotating (spinning) central cube symbolizes the tangle core, i.e., the tangled region where the particle is localized with the highest probability. The continuous rotation of a tethered particle is possible, independently of the number of tethers. The cube rotates twice before returning to the starting configuration. This factor of 2 appears in many expressions involving the rotation angle and the quantum phase of fermions. Dirac's trick can be easily reproduced with real ropes, belts, hands, or strips of paper.

- ▷ Because spin is action per rotation and because non-trivial tangles return to themselves after two rotations, non-trivial tangles with their tethers reproduce spin $\hbar/2$, i.e., spin $1/2$, as tangle core rotation.
- ▷ Particles non-vanishing spin below $\hbar/2$ cannot occur.
- ▷ Because Dirac's trick works for rotations around any axis, the rotation axis and the orientation of tethered cores reproduce the spin axis and the phase, and thus reproduce the flag model of spin and spinors.
- ▷ Because all non-trivial tangles return to themselves after two rotations, independently of the tangle topology or complexity, tangles show that spin is angular momentum and that the spin value does *not* depend on the particle mass, its size, or its rotation speed.
- ▷ The exchange of tethered non-trivial tangle cores reproduces fermion behaviour.
- ▷ Fluctuating tethers imply that non-trivial tangle cores orbiting each other reproduce particles orbiting each other.

Figure 8: The return to the original configuration after a double rotation can also be visualized with the animation produced by Antonio Martos, available at [102]. The rotating central belt buckle symbolizes the tangle core. Each belt corresponds to two or more strands. The animation shows that the continuous rotation of a tethered particle is possible.

- ▷ Because orbiting pairs of fermions return to themselves after a rotation by 2π , they visualize that such pairs are bosons, as told in the next section.
- ▷ Tethers reproduce the spin-statistics theorem for fermions. Only spin $1/2$ particles are fermions, and vice versa [132, 133]
- ▷ The necessity of tethers in these arguments shows that no explanation of spin $1/2$ and of fermion properties is possible without tethers.

Strands predict that results are valid generally for all fermions and for all measurable energies. The results thus predict the general validity of *Pauli's exclusion principle*. This validity is observed across nature, for example in the Gibbs paradox, in the Sackur-Tetrode equation for the entropy of monoatomic gases and in the shell structure of atoms [134].

Generally speaking, a tethered structure with spin $1/2$ returns to itself after a rotation by 4π . A tethered structure with spin 1 returns to itself after a rotation by 2π , a spin 2 structure after a rotation by π . A tethered spin 0 structure does not rotate. No elementary rational tangle and thus no elementary particle can have other spin values.

In short, the fundamental principle relating \hbar to crossing switches implies

Test 1: Strands predict the lack of elementary particles with non-standard statistics, including elementary particles with spin between 0 and $1/2$.

Test 2: Strands predict the lack of elementary fermions with spin larger than $1/2$.

[These properties are observed \[75\]](#). Any counterexample would immediately falsify the strand tangle model. Tethered tangles are essential for describing and understanding spin $1/2$, particle rotation, orbiting particles, particle exchange, and fermion behaviour. This understanding is *impossible* without tethers. The result *suggests* that every other motion in the quantum domain – including translation, interference, scattering, and interactions – can also be described with tethered tangle cores. This is indeed the case, as argued in the remainder of this article. As the next

Figure 9: Fermion exchange can be visualized with the animation produced by Antonio Martos, available at [103]. The rotating central belt buckles symbolize the two tangle cores, i.e., the regions where the two particles are localized with the highest probability. (In the strand tangle model, tethers, pairs of tethers, and the belts they form are unobservable.) The first image shows two particles whose positions were exchanged twice. The other images show that the shape changes of the belts, each corresponding to two or more tethers, bring back the original, unexchanged situation. Therefore, the continuous exchange of the two tethered particles is possible. The animation thus illustrates, among others, the motion of an electron (red) continuously orbiting a proton (blue) in a hydrogen atom. The sub-figure 1 on the top left can also be taken as the defining configuration for a composed system. The fermion trick is easily reproduced with long strips of paper, ropes, or belts.

test, it is useful to check the effects of tethers in the case of *composed* particles.

6 Tethers determine the spin of particles composed of fermions

In nature, whenever two spin $1/2$ fermions form a composite, the composite is observed to have either spin 0 or spin 1 and to be a boson. As shown now, tethers reproduce this behaviour.

In the strand tangle model, a system is *composed* when it forms a tangle core connected to the cosmological horizon by more than six tethers, because such tangles can perform Dirac's trick for subsets of strands. Often, the spin value of composed systems differs from the particles they are made of. Examples for composite systems are illustrated in Figure 4 and in Figure 9. The two figures show that a system composed of two fermion tangle cores – two belt buckles – returns to itself exactly after a rotation by 2π – the double exchange. The composite system does *not* return to itself after rotation by π , that is, after a simple exchange. These are the defining properties of *integer* spin. Thus, a composite system of two spin $1/2$ tangles behaves like a particle with integer spin.

The analogy can be made more precise by recalling that in the strand tangle model, each of the two fermions in Figure 9 can spin continuously. The simplest situation is that both particles spin continuously around an axis *along* the straight belts. If the rotation axes and rotation sense of

the two fermions and that of the double exchange *agree*, the situation is described by $S = 1$ and z-component $S_z = +1$, where z is the axis defined by the belts. If the rotation axes of the two fermions are the same, but that of the double exchange is opposite, one has $S = 1$ and $S_z = -1$. If the rotation axes of the two fermions are the same, but that of the double exchange is perpendicular to them (e.g., in the direction of the line connecting the two cores), one has the situation $S = 1$ and $S_z = 0$.

The defining property of spin 0 is that a rotation by any angle keeps the angular momentum unchanged. A composite for which the two cores rotate in *opposite* directions does not rotate when strands are randomly deformed: it has spin $S = 0$.

Apart from the four mentioned cases, a composite of two tethered spin $1/2$ particles cannot have any other behaviour under system rotation. In other words, two particles of spin $1/2$ can only yield a composite with spin 0 or spin 1. For tangles with integer spin, a core rotation by 2π is equivalent to no rotation, in contrast to the case of a half-integer spin core. They are *bosons*. In all these arguments, the two particles do not need to be identical or to be elementary. Also if their tangle cores differ or if they are themselves composed, the results about spin composition still hold. Likewise, particles composed of an odd number of spin $1/2$ particles turn out to be fermions. Instead, particles composed of an even number of spin $1/2$ particles have integer spin and are bosons. Tethers thus reproduce the observed behaviour of fermions under composition.

Tethers also generate boson behaviour. When the positions of two identical tangles with integer spin – elementary or composed – are exchanged, no full orbit of one core *around* the other core is required – in contrast to the case of half-integer spin cores. In the strand tangle model, bosons, whether elementary or composed, can exchange positions and states without hindrance. Identical boson cores can interpenetrate each other. Strand fluctuations can then restore the initial state, but with switched cores. In other words, tethers explain why all particles with integer spin are bosons and why all bosons have integer spin.

In short, using the fundamental principle that defines Planck's quantum of action \hbar with observable crossing switches, the unobservable strands in the tangle model for particles imply the full spin-statistics theorem.

Test 3: Strands deduce that bosons have integer spin and fermions have half-integer spin.

Test 4: Only strands explain the existence, countability, approximate locality, spin, statistics, composition behaviour, *and* behaviour under orbital motion of quantum particles.

[This is observed \[75\]](#). Any counterexample would immediately falsify the model.

7 Unobservable strands, falsifiability, and scientific principles

Even though in quantum theory, the idea of strand-like constituents was proposed in 1929 by Dirac [2], and in the case of black holes, the idea of strand-like constituents is also from the twentieth century, the idea has never been popular. The reason is that one aspect of strands is unusual: strands are unobservable. In particular, strands do not have a single observable property. Can a description of nature based on unobservable strands be scientifically sound?

A first answer is to recall that the conventional description of space and particles is based on points. Points are both unobserved and unobservable. The strand tangle model uses unobservable strands instead of unobservable points as fundamental constituents of space and particles. Both approaches allow deducing testable statements in a reproducible way.

A second answer will be explored shortly: only the unobservability of wave functions ensures that quantum theory describes observations and observables in agreement with experiments. In

turn, the unobservability of strands ensures the unobservability of wave functions, together with all their other properties.

But the third answer is the most important. The only criterion for checking the validity of a proposed theory is the comparison with observations of the statements deduced from the theory. The deductions must be *compelling*: they must be reproducible and without alternatives. The comparison with observations must yield *full agreement*. All observations must follow and no observation must remain unexplained. Otherwise, falsifiability is not given and scientific principles are not realized. It will be shown that all conclusions deduced from strands are compelling, are falsifiable, and agree with observations.

All other claimed criteria about fundamental physics are habits of thought. Among these habits, the yearning to use points also at the Planck scale, the yearning for fundamental equations valid at the Planck scale, and the yearning to use Lagrangians valid at the Planck scale are particularly persistent. Because of the minimum length, nature *cannot fulfil* these yearnings.

In short, nature's fundamental constituents are as unobservable as points and as unobservable as wave functions. Reproducible deductions of experimental predictions ensure falsifiability.

8 Crossings of strands resemble wave functions

Spin 1/2 proves that in nature, matter particles are connected to the rest of nature. Dirac's trick shows that *crossings* of these connections are essential in the study of quantum particles. In this article, the term crossing is used in a sense similar, but not completely identical to the one used in mathematical knot theory [135–137].

▷ A *strand crossing* is the region of the smallest distance between two skew strands.

In three dimensions, the strand segments are *always* at a distance, as illustrated in Figure 10. Equivalently, as usual in knot theory, a crossing always implies a *skew* geometry of two strand segments: the segments should not be parallel nor lie in a common plane. Therefore, a 'crossing' *in the sense of knot topology* appears only when the configuration is *projected* in two dimensions.

The *existence* of a crossing, defined as the region of the smallest distance between two strands, is *independent* of the observer. Crossings can occur between any two strand segments. The segments can be part of the same strand or of different strands. Crossings also arise between extremely distant strands. Such long-distance crossings have no physical importance because crossing *switches* – which define all physical observables – in practice will not arise for them.

Crossings are consistent with the minimum length in nature. The definition of crossing assumes that in the region of the smallest distance, both strands have a radius of curvature that is larger than the Planck length. Because of the Planck-sized radius of strands, the shortest distance at a crossing is always larger than the minimum length.

Figure 10 shows that crossings have mathematical properties that resemble wave functions. The simplest wave function appears in the Schrödinger equation. It is defined by an amplitude R and a phase φ . The *amplitude* R is large when the shortest distance s between the two strands is small. Because of Dirac's trick, the *phase* φ is given by $\alpha/2$, half the orientation of the shortest distance in space, for example, around the direction of motion:

$$\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = R(\mathbf{x}, t) e^{i\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t)} = \frac{1}{s(\mathbf{x}, t)} e^{i\alpha(\mathbf{x}, t)/2} . \quad (11)$$

The more involved Pauli spinors have one density and three phases. Dirac spinors have one density and seven parameters, of which four are phases. Figure 10 shows that strand crossings are

At a given position, a **strand crossing** has the **same properties** as a **wave function**: Both have an **amplitude** and a number of **phases**.

Figure 10: A strand ‘crossing’ consists of two skew strand segments separated by the shortest distance s . A strand crossing allows defining amplitude and phase(s). Therefore, a strand crossing at a point has the *same properties* as a wave function at a point. The drawing on the top right defines the *crossing axis* as the sum of the two tangent vectors at the two endpoints of the shortest distance s . (This requires defining a positive direction on each strand.) The main *phase* α describes the direction in which the shortest distance vector points around the axis, once a sequence is defined among strands. The dotted direction defining *vanishing* phase around the axis is a matter of choice, as usual for the phase. Regardless of the choice of vanishing phase, phase differences are always defined uniquely. Because of the impenetrability of strands, the shortest distance s is never shorter than the minimum length, given by twice the Planck length. The angles or phases β , γ and δ play a role in spinors.

described by an amplitude and four phases. Part II will use the oriented density of tangle crossings to define wave functions. The other angles illustrated in Figure 10 play a role in spinor wave functions, as explained subsequently.

Apart from the ideas by Kauffman [4, 5], there seems to be no research literature on strand crossings in quantum theory. In particular, there appears to be no research on the similarity between crossings and wave functions.

In short, the geometric properties of strand crossings – amplitude and phases – closely resemble the **mathematical** properties of wave functions. So far, no other model provides this resemblance.

9 The search for emergent wave functions leads to the properties of strands

The search for an *emergent* description of quantum theory has been a research topic for almost a century. The efforts of de Broglie, Schrödinger, Bohm, Bell, Kochen, Specker and many other researchers in the twentieth century had a lasting impact that fuelled hope on the one hand and limited possibilities on the other. In this century, books like those by Adler [138] and by Peña, Cetto and Valdés [139] have examined the subject. They concluded that an emergent description of quantum theory using a statistical basis is possible.

Despite the efforts by Adler [140, 141], 't Hooft [142], Elze [143], de la Peña et al. [144], Blasone et al. [145], Grössing [146, 147], Acosta et al. [148], Hollowood [149] Torromé [150], Beyer and Paul [151], and many others [148, 152–165], no *specific* model for emergent wave functions that agrees with observations has been proposed thus far. This has three reasons. First, as the ancient Greeks already stated, nature consists of particles and the void. As a result, any model for emergent wave functions must at the same time be a model for relativistic quantum gravity, which is not straightforward. The second reason is that any model for wave functions, which are unobservable, must itself be unobservable, while allowing the calculation of all observables, as wave functions do. The third reason is that the options left over by the mentioned investigations are hidden and differ from the usual thought patterns. When Battey-Pratt and Racey used tethers to visualize spin 1/2 particles and to derive Dirac's equation in their inspiring paper [3], they did not explicitly explore wave functions. The strand tangle model extends the idea of tethers by modelling elementary particles as *tangles* of unobservable strands and wave functions as *oriented crossing densities*.

The exploration of these topics requires a few definitions.

- ▷ A *strand* is defined as a smooth curved line surrounded by a cylinder with a tiny Planck radius. More precisely, the line is a one-dimensional, open, continuous, everywhere infinitely differentiable subset of \mathbb{R}^3 (or of the spatial part of a curved Riemannian space) without self-intersection, unknotted, and without endpoints. In addition, the line is surrounded by a volume defined by a perpendicular disk of Planck radius $\sqrt{\hbar G/c^3}$ at each point of the line. The entire strand volume is not allowed to self-intersect; thus, the curvature radius of the curved line is never smaller than the Planck length.

From a mathematical viewpoint, the definition of strands is the usual definition used in knot theory, for example, in the ropelength calculations of tight knots [166, 167]. From a physics viewpoint, strands *differ* in several ways from flexible ropes, cables, or cooked spaghetti. First of all,

- ▷ Strands randomly fluctuate in shape and length.

The origin of the shape fluctuations is the continuous pushing of strands against strands – including those that make up the vacuum, as told in Appendix A. This pushing is a consequence of their inability to intersect. Because of the impossibility of measuring or preparing lengths smaller than the minimum length,

- ▷ Strands cannot be cut.

In other words, contrary to habits of thought, strands are *not* made of parts. Strands are indivisible. Strands are *not* made of anything else. In further contrast to everyday life,

- ▷ Strands have no ends.

Strands reach the cosmological horizon, as visualized in Appendix A, continue in and along it and then return to the interior again. But the main difference between strands and any rope of everyday life is their Planck radius. The radius of strands is so small that it is *negligible* in almost

all situations – except in the domain of relativistic quantum gravity. In particular,

- ▷ Strands are unobservable and have *no* observable properties.
- ▷ Only specific changes in the tangling of strands, *crossings switches*, are observable.

In particular, strands do not have mass, colour, energy, tension, torsion, momentum, charge, or any quantum number. Among others, strands have *no* fixed length and *cannot* exert forces: strands cannot pull anything and they do not offer any resistance at all when they are deformed or twisted. The reasons and consequences will be clarified throughout this article.

The concept of a *rational 3d tangle* is derived from topology [108, 168] and is defined intuitively in Figure 6 as a collection of braided strands.

- ▷ *Rational 3d tangles* or *3d braids* are unknotted; their tethers lead to the cosmological horizon along specified average directions in three-dimensional space.

The region of space in which the strands are tied up and tangled is called the *tangle core*. The term *tether* is used for those untangled strand segments that connect the core to the cosmological horizon. Thus, a 3d tangle consists of a core and tethers. *Tethers* are responsible for the quantum of action \hbar , for spin 1/2, for fermion behaviour and for all other quantum effects, including wave functions and their evolution equations. *Cores* determine particle type, quantum numbers, interactions, particle masses, mixings, and coupling constants, including their running.

In physics, filiform particle constituents avoid all arguments against constituents *inside* elementary particles. Experimentally, all the known elementary particles lack particle-like constituents [75]. Also theory argues against particle-like constituents: such constituents would have to be confined inside an extremely small volume, resulting in extremely large kinetic energy and thus in particle mass values that are much higher than those observed. In contrast, *unobservable strands* suggest that the region where they are tangled is the region where the wave function of the quantum particle is localized. The region is extended across space and models the wave aspect of particles.

In short, to agree with observations, strands must have specific mathematical properties: they must be unobservable, tiny, fluctuating, and uncuttable connections spanning across nature. The resulting [conjecture](#) that particles consist *completely* of tangled strands of Planck radius requires several tasks: specifying a strand tangle model for wave functions, deriving conventional quantum theory, explaining the origin of different particles and their masses, explaining gauge interactions, reproducing quantum field theory and the standard model, [exploring the differences between strands and quantum theory](#), and [continuously comparing tangles of strands to experiments](#).

Part II: Wave functions, superpositions, Hilbert spaces and measurements

[This part of the article will show that combining the fundamental principle of Figure 5 and the strand tangle model of particles yields wave functions and all their properties. In particular, strand tangles reproduce and visualize *wave-particle duality*.](#)

The strand tangle model for quantum theory starts from the basic similarity of crossings and wave functions illustrated in Figure 10, in Figure 11 and in Figure 12 and states:

- ▷ Wave functions are *oriented crossing densities* of spinning fermion tangles.
- ▷ Conversely, fermion tangles are fluctuating skeletons of wave functions.

Strands that do not belong to the fermion tangle do *not* contribute to the wave function. The time average over tangle fluctuations is taken over a few Planck times. This averaging time is much shorter than any time interval that plays a role in observations and measurements. The short

Figure 11: Wave functions and probability densities emerge from the crossings of fluctuating tangles.

averaging time is sufficient because neither single strands nor strand shapes are observable, and because there is no ‘speed’ limit for strand shape fluctuations.

Two roads lead from tangles of strands to wave functions: Schrödinger’s approach and Feynman’s approach. They are illustrated in Figure 12 and Figure 14. The two approaches differ in how they perform the time average, i.e., in how they explain the blurring that leads from a given tangle to its wave function. Both approaches are worth exploring.

Schrödinger’s approach starts with a *loose* tangle core and averages its crossings over all possible strand shape fluctuations realized during the averaging time.

- ▷ Tangle fluctuations are due to the pushing and jiggling of vacuum strands.

As a result, *each segment of a particle tangle* continuously changes shape and the crossings in a particle tangle continuously move around in space. Strands thus differ from approaches making the same point, such as that of Beyer and Paul [151], only through the specific way that the fluctuations are modelled. Crossings also continuously appear or disappear. Averaging all crossings occurring at a point in space, with their smallest distances and orientations, yields a local value for the wave function, with amplitude and phase. This average thus yields the common *Schrödinger picture* of quantum mechanics.

For example, the spinning tangle for a free particle illustrated in Figure 7 leads – after discarding the unobservable strands, keeping the observable crossings switches and averaging the shape fluctuations (not shown in the figure) – to a rotating cloud with a rotating phase. A first impression of the rotating cloud resulting from a spinning tangle was already given in Figure 2.

In the Schrödinger approach, the three steps of the averaging procedure leading from crossings to wave functions and probability densities are visualized in Figure 12. The first step consists of reducing the tangle to its crossing midpoints, crossing distances/amplitudes, and respective crossing phases, leaving out the unobservable strands. The second step consists of averaging all crossing midpoints, distances/amplitudes and phases over the strand shape fluctuations occurring during a few Planck times. It yields the wave function. Strands and their crossings imply that the quantum phase *varies* from point to point, a feature not shown in Figure 12, but shown in Figure 13. The third step consists of using the crossing density to deduce the crossing *switch* density. The crossing switch density is the usual probability density.

As the inset at the top right of Figure 12 clarifies, at a given point in space, a crossing can be described by *one positive real number* that specifies the smallest strand distance and by *up to four*

Figure 12: In the strand tangle model, the *wave function* in the Schrödinger picture is the time-averaged *oriented crossing density* and the *probability density* is the time-averaged *crossing switch density* of a particle tangle. The figure illustrates how a tangle – an electron in this case – defines crossings and local phases, how these fluctuating crossings lead to a wave function and a central phase, and how the observable *crossing switches* lead to a probability density. The figure contains a simplification: in nature, the phase of the wave function *depends* on the position, as illustrated in the following Figure 13.

angles or phases. Also a wave function at a point is described by one positive real number and several angles or phases. In the following, the three types of wave functions will be deduced from crossings. Three types of wave functions are important in this context: wave functions for the case that spin is neglected, Pauli spinors and relativistic Dirac spinors. Each type takes a different number of crossing phases into account.

The simplest wave function, neglecting spin, is used in the Schrödinger equation or in the Klein-Gordon equation. It is described by a single complex field ψ that can be written as

$$\psi = R e^{i\varphi} = \sqrt{\rho} e^{i\alpha/2} . \quad (12)$$

Here, R is the (positive) modulus or *amplitude*, $\rho = R^2$ is the *probability density*, φ is the *phase* and $\alpha = 2\varphi$ is the tangle core rotation angle due to Dirac's trick. The similarities between crossings and wave functions lead to the following definition:

- ▷ The *amplitude* due to a crossing varies inversely with the shortest strand distance s illustrated in Figure 12. The *probability density* increases when the strand density increases. More precisely, the *amplitude* or *modulus* $R(\mathbf{x}, t)$ of the wave function at a point \mathbf{x} is defined as

$$R(\mathbf{x}, t) = \left\langle \frac{1}{s^{3/2}} \right\rangle \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} . \quad (13)$$

The average – denoted as $\langle \rangle$ – is taken over all possible strand shape fluctuations during a few Planck times. The crossing distance s is defined as the shortest distance between two strand segments. The average of the crossing distance is normalized with the help of the number n , the so-called (*minimal*) *crossing number* of the tangle. The crossing number n is the smallest number of crossings that arise if a tangle is laid down on paper. The crossing number n is a topological invariant; for example, $n = 3$ for the electron tangle presented in Figure 25. In particular, the crossing number n is observer-invariant; it is a constant factor introduced in the modulus to normalize the wave function.

As a result of the definition, strand fluctuations imply that the amplitude $R(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is a continuous and differentiable positive real function of space and time, as expected. In the same way, the inset at the top right of Figure 12 leads to the definition of the quantum phase.

- ▷ The (*quantum*) *phase* is due to the average orientation of the shortest distance s around the crossing axis. More precisely, the quantum phase $\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ of a simple wave function at point \mathbf{x} is *half* the time-averaged local strand *crossing phase* α of the particle tangle – the rotation around the crossing axis – at that point:

$$\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \langle \alpha(\mathbf{x}, t)/2 \rangle . \quad (14)$$

The factor of 1/2 is due to Dirac's trick. Again, the average is denoted by $\langle \rangle$ and is taken over a few Planck times and thus over the underlying strand shape fluctuations.

- ▷ The *crossing axis* is defined with the two unit tangent vectors of the strands at the endpoints of the shortest distance s , as illustrated in the inset of Figure 12. In particular, the crossing axis is given by the *sum* of the two tangent vectors. The crossing axis is always perpendicular to the shortest distance vector.
- ▷ The *sign* of a crossing is the direction in which the right hand turns when the thumb and index finger follow the two strands along their orientations: a clockwise right-hand rotation corresponds to a positive sign.

In simple words, the *phase* of the crossing specifies the orientation of the shortest distance around the crossing axis – or some other preferred direction. The phase angle α is measured against a preferred direction, indicated by the vertical black dotted line in Figure 12. The other angles describing the crossing are ignored in the case of the Schrödinger equation and the Klein-Gordon equation. As usual, there is freedom in the definition of the preferred direction that defines a vanishing phase of a particle tangle. In Figure 12, the freedom is the ability to choose the direction of the black dotted line. In the case of tangles yielding gauge fields instead of wave functions, the freedom to choose the orientation of the zero phase is related to the freedom of gauge choice, as will become clear below.

Figure 13: In a moving wave packet, the phase depends on the position, as illustrated in this image by Bernd Thaller, which visualizes the phase with colour and the amplitude with colour saturation. The image is from his beautiful website [169] and is used with his permission.

An instructive visualization of wave functions when spin is neglected uses *colour* for the phase and uses colour *saturation* for the amplitude, as shown in Figure 13. This visualization method is used in the fascinating quantum theory books by Thaller [170, 171] and in the animations found on his website [169].

The second type of wave function, the non-relativistic *Pauli spinor*, also takes into account the angles β and γ of a crossing defined in Figure 12. These angles describe the orientation of the crossing in space and are thus related to the spin orientation. A *non-relativistic spinor* used in the Pauli equation has two complex components and can be written [172, 173] as

$$\Psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{i\alpha/2} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\beta/2) e^{i\gamma/2} \\ i \sin(\beta/2) e^{-i\gamma/2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

Again, ρ denotes the probability density. In all situations *without* interactions, the tangle core can be approximated and imagined to be a rigid spinning body. The three angles α , β and γ are the Euler angles that describe the orientation of the rigid body in three dimensions. The factors $1/2$ are due to Dirac's trick. In other words, a Pauli spinor can be described by one positive real number and three phases. Alternatively, a Pauli spinor is a flagpole with a rotating flag. The additional sign required in the flag model specifies the tangling state of the tethers. In simple words, Pauli spinors are oriented crossing densities of strands.

The third and last type of wave function, the relativistic *Dirac spinor* with four complex components, can be described by one positive density, three real parameters, and four real phases. Dirac spinors take Lorentz boosts and the angle δ of Figure 12 into account, which describes the relative weight of particles and antiparticles. Dirac spinors are explored later on.

The definition of wave function as an oriented crossing density of strands also shows that each wave function is an aspect of reality describing a single quantum system. Strands thus confirm the Pusey–Barrett–Rudolph theorem that makes the same statement [174].

In short, nature is neither perfectly continuous nor perfectly discrete.

- ▷ *Quantum effects* and *measurements* are due to crossing switches.
- ▷ *Continuous quantities* arise through *time averages*, over a few Planck times, of strand shape fluctuations.
- ▷ *Wave functions* are oriented crossing densities resulting from the averaging of strand

shape fluctuations in spinning fermion tangles. Wave functions are blurred strand crossings of a particle tangle. They are *rotating and diffusing clouds* of tangle crossings.

▷ Tangles are the fluctuating *skeletons* of wave functions.

Strands imply that wave functions describe systems completely. The *local amplitude* is the time-averaged local density of tangle crossings. The *local phase* is the time-averaged local orientation of tangle crossings. As a result, a particle whose spin is neglected is described by one complex-valued field. We stress that Schrödinger wave functions, even though they neglect spin, are due to fluctuating tangles. The next sections will *prove* that oriented crossing densities have all the known properties of wave functions and that tangles are skeletons of wave functions.

10 Path integrals and rotating arrows emerge from tangles

Feynman's path integral approach is presented in his beautiful book *QED* [175]. He described the motion of a quantum particle as an *advancing and rotating arrow* taking all possible paths. The tip of the arrow – describing the phase – traces a helix around the path; the wavelength and angular frequency are determined by the momentum and the energy of the particle. Wave functions arise when the effects of all possible paths are superposed. In particular, the phases and amplitudes for all paths arriving at the final point must be added.

The strand tangle model directly leads to Feynman's path integral approach. The approach is based on *tight* rotating tangles, while keeping in mind that strands are unobservable. The three steps of the approach are illustrated in Figure 14. The first step is to *neglect* the radius of the unobservable strands and to imagine that the tangle core is *tightened* to a point-like region by “pulling” the tethers. This yields a point particle with a phase arrow attached to it. For the rotating tangle of a free particle illustrated in Figure 7, this step implies neglecting the unobservable tethers and zooming out until the central cube, the tangle core, has a negligible size. In the strand tangle model, the continuous rotation of the tangle core is the rotating phase; it thus visualizes Feynman's rotating arrow. The second step is to imagine that the *tight tangle core*, which is continuously spinning, randomly changes its motion, taking all possible paths. As before, the fluctuations are due to fluctuating strands making up empty space. Averaging over all possible paths of the tight tangle core yields the wave function. The third step is, as before, the definition of the probability density as the crossing switch density.

In the strand tangle model, the fluctuations of the tangle motion represent the effects of all the possible paths. With the definition of tangle addition given below, the path combination at the final point occurs exactly as in Feynman's path integral formulation of quantum theory. Contracting electron tangles – and the photon tangles introduced below – to a point and ignoring their unobservable tethers fully reproduces all the details of Feynman's approach. The two possible rotation directions of advancing cores distinguish right-handed from left-handed particles. The two mirror versions of a chiral core distinguish particles and antiparticles.

Feynman's path integral approach for deriving wave functions from strands was used by Battey-Pratt and Racey in their discussion of the Dirac equation [3]. Mathematically, the path integral approach yields the same result for amplitude and phase that arises in Schrödinger's approach. However, defining the phase using the orientation of a tight tangle core corresponds more directly to Feynman's idea of a rotating arrow. In addition, the appearance of half angles in the definition of spinor wave functions becomes more intuitive. This also explains the *g*-factor of 2. In any case, the description of the quantum state using a fluctuating *tight* tangle is equivalent to the description with a fluctuating *loose* tangle. Both ways lead to a wave function described by an

Figure 14: In Feynman's *path integral formulation*, the wave function and the probability density are due to time-averaged fluctuating (almost) point-like particle tangles. The figure illustrates how a tangle that is "pulled tight" defines a position and a local phase. The fluctuations of the (almost) point-like tangle core then lead to a wave function. In particular, *an advancing particle is an advancing rotating arrow*. For particles with spin, the tangle can be represented by a flagpole with a rotating flag. The arrow or the flag represents the phase. As usual, the modulus of the wave function leads to a probability density. Also this figure is simplified: in reality, the phase of the wave function of a particle *depends* on the position, as shown in Figure 13.

amplitude and one or several phases, that is, to one or several continuous complex functions.

How can one be sure that the tight tangle path averaging process results in the correct wave function $\psi(\mathbf{x}, t)$? The answer is the same as that of the original path integral formulation. Because an advancing rotating tight tangle reproduces the fermion propagator, its path integral reproduces the free particle wave function and, as will appear below, its full evolution equation [175].

In short, the strand tangle model of quantum particles reproduces the *path integral formulation* of quantum mechanics once particle tangle cores are approximated as *tight* chiral tangles of strands with vanishing radius and the unobservable tethers are ignored. Averaging tight tangles that fluctuate over space yields the usual wave function. In other words, the wave function of a particle is either a *rotating and diffusing cloud* of oriented crossings or a cloud due to a continuously fluctuating tight tangle core. In both cases, wave functions are oriented crossing densities.

Linear combinations

Figure 15: The linear combination of two states representing a particle localized at two different positions visualizes the superposition of wave functions in the strand tangle model.

11 Tangles describe superpositions of wave functions

Oriented crossing densities of tangles can only model wave functions if they form a *Hilbert space*. A Hilbert space is a vector space with an inner product and several technicalities.

Interestingly, it is possible to define operations for fluctuating tangles – the skeletons of wave functions – and show that these operations led to a Hilbert spaces for their oriented crossing densities. One starts with

- ▷ The *scalar multiplication* $a\psi$ of a state ψ by a complex number $a = re^{i\delta}$, with $0 \leq r \leq 1$ is formed by taking the underlying tangle, rotating its tangle core by the angle 2δ and then ‘pushing’ a *fraction* $1 - r$ of the tangle to the cosmological horizon, thus keeping the fraction r of the original tangle at finite distances. Thus, scalar multiplication with $r \leq 1$ is a process of *tangle core rotation and thinning*. Time averaging of the remaining tangle fluctuations leads to the wave function $a\psi = re^{i\delta}\psi$.

A simple case of a double scalar multiplication of a tangle, with real numbers, is illustrated in Figure 15. The figure visualizes how *partial tangles* arise via *thinning* an original tangle core without generating additional crossings. Even though there is a choice about which specific fraction r of tangle crossings is kept and which specific fraction $1 - r$ of crossings is sent away, this choice is only apparent. The resulting crossing density, defined as the average over fluctuations, is independent of this choice because the tangle topology, which specifies the particle, remains intact. In

simple words, the tangle version of scalar tangle multiplication is *unique*.

The tangle version of scalar multiplication is also *associative*: the relation $a(b\psi) = (ab)\psi$ holds by construction. The scalar multiplication of strands also behaves as expected for the factors 1 and 0. Finally, strand multiplication by -1 is defined as the rotation of the full tangle core by 2π , as required by Dirac's trick. In other words, the scalar multiplication of wave functions by complex numbers can be modelled as tangle core rotation and thinning.

Also addition can be defined for tangles – more precisely, for partial tangles.

- ▷ The *sum* or *superposition* of two partial tangles $a_1\psi_1$ and $a_2\psi_2$, for which $|a_1|^2 + |a_2|^2 = 1$ and for which ψ_1 and ψ_2 describe the same particle, is defined by stretching or thinning the original particle core into two partial tangles connected by an *addition region* that does *not* contain any crossings. Time averaging then leads to the usual linear combination $a_1\psi_1 + a_2\psi_2$.

An example of superposition for the case of two quantum states at different positions in space is shown in Figure 15. Visualizations for other types of superpositions are given later on.

The definition of a linear combination of tangles *requires* that the two partial tangles $a_1\psi_1$ and $a_2\psi_2$ belong to the same particle. Tangles thus automatically implement the corresponding *superselection rules* of quantum theory.

The sum of two partial tangles is *unique*, for the same reasons given for the case of scalar multiplication. Tangle addition is also commutative and associative, and there is a zero state, or identity element, given by an untangled set of strands without crossings. Tangle addition also implies distributivity with respect to the addition and scalar multiplication of states.

In short, using core rotation, core thinning, and untangled addition regions, linear superpositions of partial tangles can be defined, leading to linear superpositions of wave functions. This proves that oriented crossing densities form a *vector space*. The next task is to test whether tangle superpositions describe the observed interference of quantum particles.

12 Strands lead to the interference of fermions

The observation of *interference* of quantum particles – such as electrons, neutrons, atoms, molecules and photons – is due to the superposition of coherent quantum states with different phases at one position in space. Interference results from the linear combinations of wave functions, i.e., from quantum state superpositions, and is a typical effect of wave-particle duality and of quantum physics.

As expected, the strand tangle model reproduces interference. For example, using the definition of superpositions given above, an equally weighted sum of a partial tangle and the same partial tangle with a phase rotated by $\pi/2$ (thus with a core rotated by π) results in a tangle whose phase is rotated by the intermediate angle, thus with a phase rotated by $\pi/4$. An example of constructive interference is illustrated in the upper half of Figure 16.

In experiments, the most interesting observation is *destructive* interference, i.e., the *extinction* of particles. In experiments, the multiplication of a wave function ψ by -1 yields the negative of the wave function, i.e., its additive inverse $-\psi$. The local sum of a wave function and its exact negative vanishes. This is the description of extinction in conventional quantum theory.

In the strand tangle model, the negative of a fermion tangle is a tangle with a core rotated by 2π . Using the strand definition of linear combinations, the sum of a fermion quantum state with its *exact* negative requires rotating half of the core by 2π and then connecting it to the other, unrotated half, without crossings. This is impossible without untangling the core. Equivalently,

Figure 16: The strand explanation at the basis of interference: the phases of two crossings connected by strands either superpose constructively (top) or destructively (bottom).

this situation yields untangled vacuum strands at that position. This is shown schematically in the lower half of Figure 16. Therefore, the result of the situation is a *vanishing* crossing density in the spatial region where a state is added to its exact negative. Vanishing crossing density is the defining characteristic of the vacuum. Strand tangles thus explain extinction as a consequence of particle tangle superpositions.

The interference in the case of the double slit experiment is visualized for electrons in Figure 17. Depending on the two paths taken to the final region of superposition, the phases add up or cancel out. To describe the double-slit experiment also during the passage through the slits, one needs to keep in mind that an advancing tangle can shed one strand and incorporate a neighbouring one. This process of *hopping* is part of the propagation of tangles. After the two slits, the two

Figure 17: The tangle explanation of interference is illustrated for an electron tangle passing a double slit. Depending on the phase difference arising in the two paths, the electron tangle interferes constructively or destructively with itself. The explanation requires taking the *hopping* of tangles from strand to strand into account.

partial tangles must hop on the same strands to continue and interfere. (If they do not, they are absorbed.) With the hopping process, strand tangles visualize that the quantum particles pass both slits and then yield an interference pattern on the detection screen.

Test 5: Strands predict the lack of observable deviations from superpositions and interference. So far, this prediction agrees with experiments [176]. In other words, tangle superpositions describe and visualize the double-slit experiment.

In short, fluctuating strand tangles describe and explain both the constructive and destructive interference of matter particles, in full agreement with observations. This result for fermions suggests exploring the case of photons.

13 An intermezzo: strands lead to the interference of photons

In the strand tangle model, a photon is a single strand with a rotating loop or *twist*. The graphic summary of the relation of photon tangles to electrodynamics is given in Figure 18. The relation of photons to the other gauge bosons in nature is deduced below, in Section 29. Topologically, a moving photon is a propagating first Reidemeister move, i.e., a propagating twist, a moving and rotating strand loop.

The twist is the tangle core of a photon. The size of the twist is the photon wavelength. In other words, strands imply that radio-frequency photons can have twists of a size of kilometres and more. The energy of a photon is localized in the curved sections of its strand. For a photon, like for every particle, only crossing switches are observable; the tethers are not. When a photon advances, its core advances and rotates. The phase of a photon is determined by the pointing direction of its core. As illustrated in Figure 18, the photon, like the electron, can therefore be seen as an advancing rotating arrow. Thus, the strand tangle model simply adds a twist and two unobservable tethers to the conventional description of the photon as a rotating arrow.

The tangle model shows that a photon whose core has rotated by 2π is equivalent to a photon with an unrotated core, because the tethers can fluctuate from one configuration to the other. This – much simpler – *spin 1* version of Dirac’s trick is illustrated in the top left of Figure 18. An almost trivial ‘boson trick’ corresponding to the ‘fermion trick’ mentioned above also exists: after a single core exchange, two nearby photons can yield the same observables as before if each core hops to the other strand. Thus, photons have spin 1 and show boson behaviour. The photon tangle is topologically trivial; as explained below, this implies a vanishing mass. Electric and magnetic fields are densities and flow densities of twists.

Electric charge, its slower-than-light motion, and its conservation arise naturally from strands. Figure 18 shows how strands imply Coulomb’s law. *Mathematical theorems* based on these two properties by Heras [177–181] and by Burns [182] then *prove* that Maxwell’s equations hold, including the Lagrangian of classical electrodynamics. In particular, strands imply minimal coupling. The way of visualizing Maxwell’s equations and quantum electrodynamics with the help of twisted strands has been extensively explored elsewhere [129].

Figure 19 visualizes the interference of a photon – always only with itself, as told by Dirac [183] – occurring in the double-slit experiment. The ‘negative’ of a photon state is a strand whose looped twist points in the opposite direction. The addition of half a twist with its other negative half yields a strand without crossing. This situation visualizes extinction and is shown on the right-hand side of the figure. In the case of extinction, partial photon tethers with opposite phase add up to a vacuum strand.

Photons have wave properties: they have frequency and wavelength; therefore, they can interfere. Photons also have particle properties: they can be counted and have angular momentum,

Figure 18: The summary of the strand tangle model for electromagnetism is illustrated. The motion of a photon with its rotating phase, the absorption of a photon, the origin of electric charge from topological tangle chirality, and the origin of Coulomb's law are visualized. More details are given in Part IV and in reference [129].

linear momentum and energy. *The tangle model of photons and of electrons thus visualize wave-particle duality.* A literature search shows that a similar description of photons, also based on a curved strand, the so-called 'corkscrew model' of the photon [106], is part of physics lore. However, that description has never been expanded to include the quantum of action.

In short, the tangle model of the photon is a strand with a rotating twist. The model reproduces electromagnetism. The model also describes interference. In particular crossing switches explain why a photon only interferes *with itself*. The rotating twist model of the photon also yields a U(1) gauge symmetry, as confirmed in more detail below.

14 Tangles imply Hilbert spaces and operators

To form a Hilbert space, crossing densities deduced from tangles must allow defining an inner (or scalar) product. This implies reproducing the following properties of wave functions:

Figure 19: The strand tangle explanation of photon interference is illustrated. Depending on the relative phase between the two paths, a photon passing through a double slit interferes constructively or destructively with itself. The explanation requires taking into account the strand hopping of partial photons.

- ▷ The *inner (or scalar) product* between two states $\psi_1(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\psi_2(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is defined as $\langle \psi_1 | \psi_2 \rangle = \int \bar{\psi}_1(\mathbf{x}, t) \psi_2(\mathbf{x}, t) d\mathbf{x}$.
- ▷ The *norm (or modulus)* of a state is $\|\psi\| = \sqrt{\langle \psi | \psi \rangle}$.
- ▷ The *probability density* ρ of a state is $\rho(x, t) = \langle \psi | \psi \rangle = \|\psi\|^2$.

In the strand tangle model, the *conjugate tangle* $\bar{\psi}$ is formed from the tangle ψ by exchanging the sign of each crossing, i.e., by exchanging underpasses and overpasses. Conjugation thus arises by switching crossings. As a consequence,

- ▷ The *inner product* $\langle \psi_1 | \psi_2 \rangle$ is a complex number whose phase is given by the average crossing rotation between the two states and whose magnitude is the complex ratio of switched crossings in the tangle $\bar{\psi}_1$ that also appear in the tangle ψ_2 .

This inner product has all the required properties: it is Hermitian, sesquilinear and positive definite. Being related to crossing switches, the inner product is a physical observable, in contrast to the states themselves. This property is as expected.

The inner product of wave functions allows defining the *norm* of a wave function. In conventional quantum mechanics and in the strand tangle model, the norm is the square root of $\langle \psi | \psi \rangle$. The norm has the value 1 for every single-particle quantum state defined with tangles. The required technicalities about the completeness of the norm are automatically realized by tangles of strands. Thus, wave functions defined with strand tangles are normalized in the tangle model and form a *Hilbert space*.

Anticipating the results presented below, the investigation of electrodynamics [129] shows that the (appropriately signed) minimum crossing number of a tangle is the *electric charge* of a particle in units of $e/3$. In the tangle model, the probability density thus reproduces the charge density. All strand processes, all shape fluctuations and all strand exchanges of strand tangles *conserve* charge.

As already mentioned, the probability density is the crossing *switch* density. Because the definitions of the probability density and the inner product involve crossing switches, both quantities are physical *observables*. This is as expected.

Once states and their Hilbert space are defined, *operators* on that Hilbert space can be defined using strands: *operators deform tangles*. Several classes of operators occur. In quantum theory, *unitary operators* preserve inner products. In the strand tangle model, *unitary operators*, such as the time evolution operator, deform tangles by retaining the norm of the wave function, that is, by retaining both the topology and the shape of the tangle core. *Unitary operators deform tethers but keep the tangle core rigid*. In quantum theory, also self-adjoint or *Hermitian operators* are important: they conserve probabilities, have a real spectrum and describe physical observables. In the strand tangle model, *Hermitian operators* leave the tangle topology invariant but *deform the tangle core*. In quantum theory, *field operators* also play a role. Some aspects of field operators are explored in Appendix C.

The position operator X localizes a particle tangle core at a ‘point’, i.e., it tightens the core into a given region of Planck size. The momentum operator P ‘localizes’ a particle tangle core at a momentum value, i.e., it deforms the core into an infinitely long helix with given wavelength. Conventional quantum theory leads to the operator equation

$$PX - XP = i\hbar . \quad (16)$$

This well-known *canonical commutation relation* was first deduced by Born and Jordan in 1925 [184]. In 1987, Kauffman suggested that the commutation relation is due to a crossing switch [4, 5]. However, at that time, no one took up this suggestion. The strand tangle model does. Strands deduce the relation from the fundamental principle, as will be shown in a separate paper.

Tangles of strands reproduce wave functions and their Hilbert space. Tangles also reproduce the countability of particles. Therefore, strands also reproduce the Fock space, using only three-dimensional space. [In the research literature](#), strands appear to be the first model achieving this.

In short, once strand tangles are used to define wave functions as oriented crossing densities, they reproduce superpositions, form Hilbert spaces, allow deducing unitary and Hermitian operators, and produce Fock spaces. Probability densities, defined as crossing switch densities, behave as expected from conventional quantum theory and as observed. The next tests will check whether tangles of strands reproduce indeterminacy, measurements, decoherence, and entanglement.

15 Indeterminacy is a consequence of the fundamental principle

Heisenberg's *indeterminacy relation*, which is also called the *uncertainty relation*, is a well-known result of quantum theory. It is related to wave-particle duality and has been confirmed in all experiments. Crossing switches of strands explain the relation.

In nature, measurements lead to eigenstates. In the strand model, measurements lead to specific crossing configurations. For a general strand configuration corresponding to the middle case of the fundamental principle of Figure 5, it is unclear, and thus uncertain or indetermined, to which of the two outer configurations it belongs. Strand fluctuations will lead to random measurement results. The randomness leads to an uncertainty or indeterminacy in the measurement of any observable, denoted by Δ . The two outer configurations in Figure 5 are separated by \hbar . On average, the measurement of action W is thus uncertain by half a crossing switch and thus by half a quantum of action \hbar . Therefore, for a general tangle configuration,

$$\Delta W \leq \hbar/2 . \quad (17)$$

For position and momentum, whose operators do not commute, this yields

$$\Delta x \Delta p \leq \hbar/2 . \quad (18)$$

Because of strands, the indeterminacy product for any two observables whose product is an action and whose operators do not commute is given by half a crossing switch, and thus half a quantum of action. In simple words, the indeterminacy relation is a *direct consequence* of the fundamental principle defining the smallest measurable action \hbar . A separate publication will show in detail that Heisenberg's canonical commutation relation is due to the non-commutativity of tangle deformations.

In short, in the strand tangle model, the fundamental principle relating crossing switches to Planck's quantum of action \hbar implies that quantum states obey Heisenberg's indeterminacy relation. This agrees with all observations. Any counter-example would immediately falsify the strand tangle model.

16 Measurements, Born's rule, wave function collapse and decoherence

Experiments show that every measurement of an observable A on a quantum state ψ has two effects. First, every measurement yields a real *eigenvalue* a of the operator A describing the variable being measured. Secondly, every measurement changes, projects, or collapses the quantum state into the corresponding *eigenstate* ψ_a for which $A\psi_a = a\psi_a$ – in the situation without degeneracy. The collapse occurs with a probability given by $|\langle \psi_a | \psi \rangle|^2$, the squared inner product between the

Spin measurement

Figure 20: A measurement of a superposition, here for spin up and down, dissolves the addition region, here outwards or inwards. For an animated version of such a spin superposition, produced by Jason Hise, see [youtube.com/shorts-KGW3QvwFuE](https://www.youtube.com/shorts/KGW3QvwFuE).

quantum state and the eigenstate. This is known as *Born's rule*.

In nature, every measurement apparatus is a device that produces, stores, and displays measurement results. This is possible because every measurement apparatus contains a memory, and thus is a *classical* device. All devices with a memory contain at least one *bath*, i.e., a subsystem described by a temperature [185]. Thus, every measurement apparatus *couples* a bath to the system that is measured. The detailed coupling depends on and defines the observable being measured by the apparatus. Every coupling of a quantum system to a bath results in *decoherence*. Decoherence leads to wave function collapse and probabilities. Therefore, collapse and probabilities are necessary and automatic consequences of decoherence in conventional quantum theory [186, 187].

The strand tangle model describes the measurement process in precisely the same way as conventional quantum theory. In addition, strands *visualize* the measurement process.

- ▷ A *measurement* is a specific deformation of the system tangle, induced by the bath in measurement apparatus, that *deforms* the strands of the quantum system into the resulting eigenstate.
- ▷ The deformation of the tangle of the quantum system by the bath strands is the *collapse* of the wave function.
- ▷ The storage of the result in the memory of the measurement apparatus involves the tangle of the quantum system and the tethers in the bath of the apparatus.

An example of a measurement of a spin superposition is illustrated with strands in Figure 20.

- ▷ When a measurement is performed on a superposition of two spin states, *the untangled ‘addition region’ is dissolved by the bath.*

When this dissolution occurs, one of the underlying eigenstates ‘gobbles up’ the other eigenstate: the wave function *collapses*. This process is triggered by the strands in the bath inside the measurement apparatus (not shown in the figure). In the case of a spin superposition, the strands of the apparatus dissolve the addition region either towards the outside or the inside. The choice is determined by the fluctuation details of the state of the bath coupled to the state of the system being measured. Thus, the specific strand fluctuations determine the outcome of the measurement.

In the strand tangle model, when the bath in the measurement apparatus and the state of the quantum system select a measurement outcome, the bath strands change the original quantum state being measured into an eigenstate. This change occurs by deforming all the strands of the quantum state being measured into the strand configuration of the eigenstate. In other words, a large number of bath tangles causes the quantum state to collapse by pushing the strands of the quantum system. Therefore, in any measurement, the initial quantum state and the final quantum eigenstate differ only in their strand shapes and not in their topologies. This is observed.

The probability of measuring a particular eigenstate will depend on the (weighted) volume that the eigenstate takes up in the superposition. The bath will choose the eigenstate with the higher weight more often. This is Born’s rule.

For example, whenever the position of a particle is measured, an initially delocalized, spread-out quantum state is localized at the measured position. For photons, the process is illustrated in Figure 21. The many unobservable strands of the bath in the detector *localize* the quantum state of the photon, and thus the tangle core, at the spot where the detector is triggered. The many detector strands *dissolve* the addition regions and push the tangle core towards a “single” position. This is the collapse of the quantum state. The final position itself is random, as it depends on the fluctuations of the photon strand and of the detector strands. The large number of detector strands leads to a single final position. The final position will be one of the positions of constructive interference. When the particle core triggers the particle detector, the tangle crossings of the particle interact with the crossings of the charges inside the detector at the position where the photon is localized. Strands thus explain why extended superpositions still lead to localized detection.

Thus, the strand description of measurement is a specific realization of wave function collapse induced by baths in the environment. This approach has been championed by Zeh [186] and many after him. The details of contextual collapse are still being refined [188]. In simple words, strands imply that there is a stochastic aspect in every quantum system and its measurement. The strand description appears to resolve the issues raised by Adler [189]. In addition,

Test 6: Strands predict the lack of measurable deviations from decoherence.

Figure 21: The detection of a photon arriving at a screen in a superposition produced by the double slit experiment of Figure 19 is illustrated. The photon state is a superposition of photons located at the dotted circles. The unobservable tethers of the bath in the detector *decohere* or *collapse* the superposition. The observable crossing switch of the photon is then detected at the screen at a single position.

This prediction agrees with observations [190].

In short, like conventional quantum theory, the strand tangle model describes measurements as bath-induced decoherence and collapse. Any measurement apparatus – which includes a bath by definition – interacting with a quantum system automatically enforces Born's rule through the many strands of the bath. In particular, strands visualize the collapse of the wave function as a shape deformation from a superposition tangle to an eigenstate tangle, dissolving any addition regions describing the superposition. This description agrees with the usual description of collapse as a consequence of environmentally induced decoherence. In the strand tangle model, quantum probabilities are thus due to strand fluctuation probabilities. Above all, strands visualize the measurement process and reproduce all its observed properties.

17 Strands imply a finite decoherence time

In nature, the decoherence process that is part of the quantum measurement process takes time. Numerous experiments have confirmed this. [191–196]. The value of the decoherence time is due to the interaction with the bath in the apparatus or the environment. Generally speaking, the denser and the more energetic the microscopic degrees of freedom of the involved bath, the faster the decoherence.

The observed decoherence time can be estimated using various methods. A simple estimate arises for baths composed of many scattering particles. In this case, the decoherence time is typically of the order of the time interval between two scattering events due to the bath. The resulting spatial localisation is of the order of the (thermal) de Broglie wavelength of a typical bath particle. More precisely, the decoherence time is given by the particle flux and the interaction

cross-section, as explained by Joos and Zeh [186] and by Tegmark [197]. In most – but not all – practical situations, the resulting decoherence time is extremely short and leads to localization within a tiny spatial domain.

A second estimate of the decoherence time uses the relaxation time and the temperature of the bath [187, 198]. In all everyday situations, unmeasurably small values for the decoherence time result. Long decoherence times are possible if interactions with baths are minimized [199]. This requires careful experimental setups in specialized laboratories. Such setups are commonly realized in research experiments, such as those that involve qubits.

Also in the strand tangle model, scattering processes occur. Also in the strand tangle model, the relaxation time at the origin of decoherence arises because of microscopic processes in the bath. Also in the strand tangle model, the decoherence time is an effective interaction time. The decoherence time is the time that the bath strands take to *project* a particle tangle onto the eigenfunction of the measured value of the observable by dissolving the addition region. The projection process, i.e., the decoherence process, dissolves the addition region of superpositions. Because decoherence changes the shape of a tangle, its result is one specific quantum state.

Strands also clarify that the collapse of the wave function is *not limited by any speed limit*, as no energy and no information are transported, and thus no signal is transmitted. Indeed, the collapse occurs because the strands of the system are deformed by the strands from the bath. Strand motion can be superluminal. Therefore, the collapse *seems* superluminal, in particular, if one disregards the bath. A companion paper will explore the strand model of decoherence in detail.

The strands describing the bath also explain all other quantum effects. For example, bath strands describe the quantum Zeno effect [200]. As another example, bath strands describe the decoherence of qubits [199]. Qubits are briefly explored in Appendix B.

The combination of decoherence and minimum length that characterizes the strand model of quantum mechanics is also found in the Montevideo interpretation of quantum mechanics proposed by Gambini and Pullin [201, 202]. Investigating the aspects in common with the strand model is worthwhile.

In short, strands reproduce decoherence in all its aspects: decoherence leads to a single outcome, takes time, destroys macroscopic superpositions, appears superluminal and is a result of fluctuations in the baths contained in the measurement apparatus or in the environment.

18 Quantum entanglement is topological entanglement

In nature, two or more particles can be *entangled*. Entangled states are coherent multi-particle states that are not separable and thus cannot be written as the product of single-particle states. Entangled states are a fascinating and characteristic aspect of quantum physics. They do not exist in classical physics but are regularly observed and explored in many quantum experiments.

In conventional quantum theory, an N -particle wave function is usually described by a single-valued function in $3N$ dimensions. However, the strand tangle model naturally defines N wave function values at each point in three-dimensional space: each particle is described by its tangle and each tangle yields, via short-term averaging, its own complex wave function value(s) at each point in space. Because separate particles have separate tangles, the state of N particles can be described in 3 spatial dimensions – despite the recurring prejudice that this is impossible. The possibility arises because the Planck radius renders strands unobservable. At the same time, the minimum length implies that the three dimensions of everyday space are only approximate and so are the $3N$ dimensions of configuration space. Configuration space is an approximate concept. Not only is the common statement that wave functions live in $3N$ dimensions approximate. Because

Figure 22: Two examples of two distant particles with spin in *separable, unentangled* and thus *incoherent* states are illustrated, both in the strand tangle model and in their corresponding observed probability densities.

the statement contradicts observations, it is wrong. If the statement were true, we would not need traffic lights to avoid accidents in 3d or 2d space. And because all observations confirm that 3 dimensions are sufficient to describe many particles, 3 dimensions are also sufficient to describe entanglement.

In nature, an *entangled state* is a non-separable superposition of several particle states. A state is entangled or non-separable if it is *not* a product of separate particle states. A well-known example of entanglement is the spin entanglement of two identical, but distant fermions in a spin 0 state. The example was introduced and discussed in detail by Bohm [203]. It was experimentally realized many times, for example by Fry [204].

In the strand tangle model, two distant fermions in a *separable* state are modelled as two distant, separate tangles of identical topology. Figure 22 illustrates two such separable basis states in the strand tangle model. In this case, the two states have total spin 0 and are described by $|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle$ and by $|\downarrow\uparrow\rangle$. Such states, with their unlinked or barely linked tethers, are also typical outcomes of spin measurement experiments on spin 0 states of particle pairs. However, other states are also of interest. Using the definition of tangle addition, a superposition such as $\sqrt{90\%} |\uparrow\downarrow\rangle + \sqrt{10\%} |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle$

Entangled state $\sqrt{90\%} |\uparrow\downarrow\rangle + \sqrt{10\%} |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle$

Strand model:

Observation yields:

either this eigenstate (90%)

or this eigenstate (10%)

Figure 23: An *entangled, inseparable* and *coherent* spin-0 state of two distant particles is illustrated. The *addition region* around both particles prevents either particle from being seen as a separate system that is independent of the rest of its environment.

of the two spin-0 basis states looks as illustrated in Figure 23. Such a state is not a product state and therefore it is not separable, but *entangled*.

The strand tangle model enables a straightforward definition and visualisation of entanglement.

- ▷ In the strand tangle model, a state is *non-separable* whenever the tethers of the particles remain topologically entangled even if the tangle cores are pulled apart. More precisely, as illustrated in Figure 23, two states are entangled if their untangled addition region surrounds *both* tangle cores.

In the strand tangle model, the entanglement of two particles is visualized with the addition region. When the spin orientation of one of the particles is measured, the untangled addition region dissolves. The result of the measurement will either be the state favoured by the inside of the addition region or the state favoured by the outside. Because the tethers of the two particles are linked, after the measurement, independently of the outcome, the spins of the two particles will always point in opposite directions. This happens independently of particle distance. After the measurement, the state is separable. Despite this extremely rapid and seemingly superluminal collapse, no energy travels faster than light. Thus, the strand tangle model fully reproduces the behaviour of entangled spin 1/2 states as it is observed in experiments.

The similarity of quantum entanglement and topological entanglement has been noted for a long time [205–213]. Tethers provide a basis for this analogy. For example, suitably connecting the tethers at spatial infinity should recover the results of the classification of multi-particle entanglement by Quinta and André [209]. Likewise, the description of entanglement with tethers in Figure 23 reproduces the demonstration of this aspect of quantum mechanics that was provided

by Mermin [214]. Also the descriptions of two-particle entanglement, or two-qubit entanglement, with two Bloch spheres, as given by Filatov and Auzinsh [215], are simplified when using tethers. The additional mathematical conditions they require to describe entanglement can be seen as effects of unobservable tethers. Above all, in contrast to the description of entanglements with Borromean links [205], tethers explain that certain measurements on entangled three-particle states can lead to a separate particle and an entangled two-particle state.

In short, using the definition of wave functions as oriented crossing densities, tangles of strands reproduce quantum entanglement as topological entanglement of tethers. All observed aspects of entanglement follow from the fundamental principle. This result leads to a further test.

19 Strands are hidden, but not hidden variables

At first sight, the strand tangle model seems to introduce hidden variables into quantum theory. One is tempted to argue that the fluctuating shapes of strands play the role of hidden variables. However, the Kochen-Specker theorem, which is valid for sufficiently high Hilbert space dimensions [216], states that non-contextual hidden variables are impossible. In real-life systems, the conditions of the theorem are always satisfied [and thus eliminate such variables](#).

The strand tangle model does *not* contain hidden variables. First, strands and their shapes are unobservable. Therefore, strands and shapes are not variables. Not only are strands and their shapes hidden, they also have *no* measurable properties: strands have no momentum, no energy, no spin, no charge, and no quantum numbers. Therefore, it is impossible to define a measurable *position* or *shape* for strands. In nature, only crossing switches are observable, as shown in Section 31. All illustrations in the present article are *unphysical*, because they depict strands in specific positions and shapes, suggest that strands can be counted without uncertainty, and suggest that a common time coordinate for each figure can be defined. The figures become physically correct only once they are modified to include an indeterminacy of time and an indeterminacy of position for every strand segment. In nature, only crossing switches are observable, as shown in Section 31. In other words, all the figures in this article should be *blurred*.

Secondly, strand shapes evolve in a manner dictated by the influence of the environment, which consists of all other strands in nature, including those of empty space itself. Therefore, the evolution of strand shapes and crossing switches is *contextual*.

For the two given reasons, the strand tangle model does not contradict the Kochen-Specker theorem. The strand tangle model provides *no* observables beyond those of quantum theory. As expected from any model that reproduces decoherence, the strand tangle model leads to a *contextual* and *probabilistic* description of nature. In particular,

Test 7: Strands predict the lack of measurable deviations from the linear behaviour of wave functions.

No deviation has ever been found or even proposed without internal contradictions [217–219].

The results of the strand tangle model also agree with the research results on probabilities in quantum mechanics. The tangle model reproduces the approach to quantum theory as a theory of extrinsic properties, as stated by Kochen [220]. Strands confirm the investigations of Colbeck and Renner [221–223], who showed the lack of alternatives to quantum theory and in particular, the lack of ‘more complete’ theories that are in agreement with observations and the freedom of choice. The results of the strand tangle model also agree with the Pusey–Barrett–Rudolph theorem, which states that wave functions are more than only information about a quantum state [174] and that wave functions describe single quantum systems.

In short, it was shown that the strand tangle model does *not* make use of non-contextual hidden variables, **but includes hidden stochastic influences from empty space itself**. *The fluctuations of the strand vacuum are the origin of probabilities of quantum physics*. Strands imply that wave functions *emerge* from fluctuating tangle shapes and describe each system *completely*, **without possibility of adding more details**. Quantum theory remains as fascinating as ever.

20 The probability density is limited

In the strand tangle model, quantum probabilities are due to strand fluctuations. Strand fluctuations are due to the fluctuating environment of every quantum system. The environment fluctuates due to the fundamental, Planck-scale fluctuations in nature. This connection between probabilities, strands and the Planck scale implies a limit.

Test 8: Strands limit the value of the probability density to

$$\|\psi(\mathbf{x}, t)\|^2 \leq \left(\frac{c^3}{4G\hbar} \right)^{3/2} \approx 3 \cdot 10^{103} \text{ m}^{-3} . \quad (19)$$

This upper limit for the probability density is the inverse of the minimum volume. **A higher value has never been observed, because the minimum volume, and equivalently, the minimum length, is unattainable in experiments, as shown in Section 2**. In particular, the limit contradicts the existence of Dirac's δ distribution. The limit also prevents the existence of *singularities* in nature, of any type. The limit on the probability density confirms the lack of perfect locality in nature. Finding an exception to the limit would immediately falsify the strand tangle model. So far, no observation contradicts this limit for probability density, the corresponding limit on charge density, and the equivalent limit for the amplitude of wave functions.

The Planck limits for probability density and for wave function amplitude have not been discussed in the research literature, mainly because there is no hope to test them. As a note, there is no Planck limit for the phase or the phase difference. A phase angle is a length ratio, and length ratios are not limited by Planck limits or strand fluctuations.

In short, strands imply that the probability density is limited by the inverse of the minimum volume in nature. Strands thus prevent the appearance of singularities. This result concludes Part II of this article, which has shown that oriented crossing densities of particle tangles are wave functions and visualize interference, Hilbert spaces, entanglement, Fock spaces, decoherence and quantum measurements. Equivalently, Part II has shown that *wave functions are blurred tangles and tangles are fluctuating skeletons of wave functions*. This result leads to exploring the evolution of tangles over time.

Part III: Dynamics of states

21 The Schrödinger equation emerges from tangles

This third part of the article explores the *time dependence* of oriented crossing densities, i.e., the evolution of wave functions. As shown now, the time evolution follows directly from the fundamental principle of Figure 5 defining the quantum of action \hbar with a crossing switch.

Experiments show that free fermions propagate, spin, precess, and diffuse. In the tangle model, a localized fermion with constant speed is described by a localized chiral tangle core that *advances, fluctuates and diffuses, rotates*, i.e., spins and *precesses*. A visualization of the motion of a free

Motion of particles in the strand model and in observations

Figure 24: Tangles of free fermions at rest (top), in slow motion (middle), and in fast motion (bottom) are illustrated. Vacuum strands are not shown, even though they induce the spinning and precessing. The relativistic flattening of the fermion core is illustrated, together with the increasing alignment of the rotation axis with the direction of motion for high momentum values.

fermion tangle is given in Figure 24. Already Figure 2 suggested that Dirac's trick couples the rotation of a chiral core to its displacement.

Why do advancing particle tangles rotate? This is the first situation in this article in which it is necessary to recall that the vacuum is made of strands as well. Any moving particle advances through the vacuum strands. The motion can be compared to a maple seed falling through the air. The maple seed rotates around its path because its shape is *chiral*. The rotation speed depends on the geometrical shape of its wings. Likewise, when a quantum particle moves through the vacuum, the vacuum strands lead to a rotation of the chiral core around the particle path. The rotation speed of a chiral particle core depends on its average shape. The spinning and precession of the advancing particle are due to the behavior of the particle tethers and the vacuum strands during Dirac's trick. On average, after every second core rotation, the fluctuations rearrange the tethers.

While advancing, the tangle fluctuations of a free particle will also *spread out* its moving core. Like the spinning, also this effect is a consequence of the impenetrability of the strands: the various fluctuating strand segments of the tangle continuously push against each other, thus spreading out the core over time. The spreading yields the *diffusion* of the probability density.

Every tangle core rotation leads to crossing switches. The fundamental principle states that each crossing switch yields a quantum of action \hbar . Thus, a rapid core rotation results in many crossing switches per time, whereas a slow rotation results in a few crossing switches per time. The quantity defined by action per time of a free particle is commonly called *kinetic energy*. Thus,

- ▷ Particles with *high* kinetic energy have *rapidly* rotating tangle cores; particles with *low* energy have *slowly* rotating cores.

Because the fundamental principle relates crossing switches to \hbar , the kinetic energy E of a tangle is automatically related to the angular frequency ω of its core rotation by the relation

$$E = \hbar\omega . \quad (20)$$

This relation, discovered by Planck and Einstein and agreeing with all data, thus follows from the fundamental principle. In simple words, the local phase of a wave function ψ for a moving core *rotates*. In the literature, it appears that only crossing switches of strands yield the relation between energy and rotation. This result implies

$$\omega = i\partial_t , \quad (21)$$

a relation that will be used shortly. As usual, the imaginary unit i describes the rotation of the core phase during propagation.

All experiments, including diffraction, confirm that the quantum phase changes over distance.

- ▷ Rapidly moving tangles show many crossing switches per distance; slowly moving tangles show few crossing switches per distance.

The fundamental principle implies that the natural observable in this case is action per distance:

- ▷ The *momentum* of a moving tangle is the number of crossing switches per distance.

Because of the fundamental principle, the momentum p of a tangle is related to the wave number $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ of the core rotation by

$$p = \hbar k . \quad (22)$$

This relation was first given, for matter particles, by de Broglie in 1913. The fundamental prin-

principle thus yields wave-particle duality. In the literature, it appears that only crossing switches of strands yield de Broglie's relation. This second relation completes the description of the phase of propagating wave functions. The relation implies

$$k = -i\partial_x . \quad (23)$$

Again, the imaginary unit i describes the rotation of the core phase during propagation. The wave function is complex-valued because it describes the rotation of the phase in a plane orthogonal to the direction of motion.

An advancing particle tangle continuously performs one Dirac trick after another. In the case of non-relativistic motion, the core shape is *rigid* when the core advances and rotates. The greater the particle momentum, the more vacuum strands align the core rotation axis with its direction of motion. This effect is illustrated in Figure 24. The helix traced out by the endpoint of the tangle phase depends on the momentum and energy of the particle. Given the speed v of the particle, both momentum and energy can be used to define the inertial mass of the particle. The *inertial mass* m determines the tightness and the frequency of the phase helix. The value m depends only on the details of the tangle core structure, i.e., on the topology and the average chiral shape of the core. In contrast, at relativistic speeds, the rotating core is flattened. Figure 24 illustrates both cases.

In the non-relativistic case, energy and momentum are related as

$$E = \frac{p^2}{2m} \quad \text{i.e.,} \quad \omega = \frac{\hbar}{2m} k^2 . \quad (24)$$

This *dispersion relation* reflects how the frequency and wave number increase with increasing energy and momentum of the particle tangle. The fundamental principle allows repeating Schrödinger's argument from 1926 [224]. Substituting the above differential relations into the dispersion relation yields the evolution equation for the oriented crossing density of the tangle, i.e., for the wave function ψ :

$$i\hbar\partial_t\psi = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\partial_{xx}\psi . \quad (25)$$

This is Schrödinger's equation for a free particle wave function in one spatial dimension and describes how the oriented crossing density of free fermion tangle advances, how its phase rotates, and how it diffuses.

The Schrödinger equation, being a wave equation, implies Heisenberg's *indeterminacy relation*. This confirms the deduction given above and agrees with observations.

The derivations retrace the history of quantum theory. Schrödinger derived his evolution equation from de Broglie's relation for matter waves. Because the equation is linear, its solutions also yield and describe superpositions, interference and entanglement. All these quantum effects, but also Hilbert spaces and all other mathematical quantum aspects, disappear if \hbar is set to zero.

The strand tangle model combines the descriptions of a particle as a diffusing rotating phase, as a rotating arrow taking all possible paths, and as rotating flagpole. All these descriptions are found in the literature. They were developed by Schrödinger [224], Dirac [183], Feynman [175], Hestenes [225–228], Penrose [1], among many others. More authors are cited later on.

In short, in the strand tangle model, the chiral shape of the particle core implies that core displacement and core rotation are related. As a consequence, the wave function, or crossing density, of a free non-relativistic particle whose spin is neglected obeys the free Schrödinger equation. Even though the Schrödinger equation neglects spin, it results from tangles with rotating cores

and can only be explained and visualized with a helical motion of a rigid tangle core. Dirac's trick slows down the motion of fermions; therefore, they move more slowly than photons and have mass. In contrast to usual quantum mechanics, the mass value of particles is *not a free parameter* but uniquely determined by the structure and shape of the tangle core. Several tasks [and tests](#) remain: including the speed limit c , including fermion spin, including gauge interactions, and calculating tangle mass values.

22 The Klein-Gordon equation emerges from tangles

In 1980, Battey-Pratt and Racey [3] showed that tethered *relativistic* particles whose spin is neglected are described by the Klein-Gordon equation. Their approach can also be used in the strand tangle model. Neglecting spin effectively assumes a spin orientation constant in time and space. The only difference to the derivation of the Schrödinger equation is the relativistic motion. Taking into account the speed limit c yields time dilation. Time dilation, combined with Dirac's trick, changes (half) the core spinning frequency ω as a function of the core speed v :

$$\nabla^2\psi = \frac{\omega^2 v^2}{c^4(1 - v^2/c^2)}\psi . \quad (26)$$

Inserting the relativistic expression for the observed angular rotation frequency of the tangle phase $\omega/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ (the core rotates with twice that frequency) yields

$$\nabla^2\psi - \frac{1}{c^2}\partial_{tt}\psi = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2}\psi = \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2}\psi , \quad (27)$$

where mass m is again introduced as a constant that relates the translation speed and the angular frequency of Dirac's trick. This is the well-known *Klein-Gordon equation*. In other words, Battey-Pratt and Racey showed that the Klein-Gordon equation follows from Figure 24. The result confirms that the core spinning frequency $\omega = 2mc^2/\hbar$ due to Dirac's trick reproduces what Schrödinger called *Zitterbewegung*.

The definition of the quantum phase with crossings explains that the phase varies all over three-dimensional space and is not defined only at the centre of the rotating core. The crossing density also yields an amplitude value that is a function of position. In this way, the strand tangle model solves the issues mentioned by Battey-Pratt and Racey in their paper [3]. No other emergent derivations of the Klein-Gordon equation appear to be available in the literature.

In short, the strand tangle model reproduces the result by Battey-Pratt and Racey: for relativistic matter particles whose spin is neglected, tangles whose wave functions are defined as oriented crossing densities, follow the Klein-Gordon equation. The next task is to add spin.

23 Pauli spinors and the Pauli equation are due to tangles

Any realistic model of wave functions must include *spin* and must describe the change of its orientation over space and time. The results about tangles derived so far can be extended to realize this requirement. This section treats the non-relativistic case.

To extend the wave function by including the orientation of the spin rotation axis, it is most practical to use the *Euler angles* α , β and γ [172, 173]. They allow describing the crossing density

as

$$\Psi(x, t) = \sqrt{\rho} e^{i\alpha/2} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\beta/2)e^{i\gamma/2} \\ i \sin(\beta/2)e^{-i\gamma/2} \end{pmatrix} . \quad (28)$$

Again, the crossing density is the square root of the probability density $\rho(x, t)$. Again, the angle $\alpha(x, t)/2$ describes the phase, i.e., half the rotation *around* the axis. The newly added orientation of the spin axis is described by a two-component matrix that uses the two angles $\beta(x, t)$ and $\gamma(x, t)$ shown in Figure 10 and Figure 12. Because of the half angles, the two-component matrix is a *spinor*, as Ehrenfest named it, in analogy to the terms ‘vector’ and ‘tensor’. The half-angles lead to a minus sign after a rotation by 2π and to a return to the original situation after a rotation by 4π , as is observed. For the case that $\beta = \gamma = 0$ at all times and all positions, the wave function ψ used in the Schrödinger equation is recovered.

As described by Payne [229], by Penrose and Rindler [1], and by Steane [230], a Pauli spinor can be visualized as a flag on a pole and a sign. The length of the flagpole is described by a positive real number $\sqrt{\rho}$. It is the *amplitude* of the wave function. The direction of the flag around the pole is described by the first angle α . The flag angle α is the *phase* of the wave function; it corresponds to the rotating arrow used by Feynman in his book *QED* [175]. These two parameters are the same as those used when spin is neglected. The spin orientation, i.e., the orientation of the flagpole, is described by the two additional angles β and γ . The sign of the spinor indicates whether the flag has been rotated by an even or odd multiple of 2π .

The strand tangle model for a fermion naturally reproduces spinors and their flag visualization. As before, it starts with a tangle core rotating rigidly. As illustrated in Figures 10 and 12, every fluctuating tangle core has a local crossing density, a local average phase, and a local average orientation of the crossing axis. The crossing density of the tangle core – the ‘size’ or ‘density’ of the core – reproduces the positive real number $\sqrt{\rho}$. The orientation of the tangle core – the flag – is described by three angles, as if the flagpole were glued into the tangle core. Because of Dirac’s trick, the expression for the axis orientation naturally contains *half* angles. The twistedness of the tethers reproduces the sign of the spinor.

The last ingredient is the description of the orientation of particle spin during particle motion [231]. For a propagating wave function, the spin orientation is described by the wave vector $\mathbf{k} = -i\nabla$ multiplied by the spin operator $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$. Here, the *spin operator* $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, for a spin 1/2 matter particle, is defined as the vector built from the three specific matrices

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \right) . \quad (29)$$

These three matrices are called the *Pauli matrices*. They are deduced from strands below, in Figure 34. They only arise if the tangle is non-trivial and has at least two strands. The description of the spinning motion and the spin axis can be inserted into the non-relativistic dispersion relation $\hbar\omega = E = p^2/2m = \hbar^2 k^2/2m$. This yields the free wave equation

$$i\hbar\partial_t\Psi = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}\nabla)^2\Psi . \quad (30)$$

This is *Pauli’s equation* for the evolution of a free, non-relativistic quantum particle with spin 1/2.

Anticipating the inclusion of electrodynamics deduced below, the electric and magnetic potentials can be included in the Pauli equation in the usual way [231]. This step uses minimal coupling to the electromagnetic field. Minimal coupling, deduced below, implies substituting $i\hbar\partial_t$ with **the**

expression $i\hbar\partial_t - qV$ and substituting $-i\hbar\nabla$ with $-i\hbar\nabla - q\mathbf{A}$. This substitution introduces the electric charge q and electromagnetic potentials V and \mathbf{A} . A bit of algebra involving the spin operator then leads to the Pauli equation for a charged particle

$$(i\hbar\partial_t - qV)\Psi = \frac{1}{2m}(-i\hbar\nabla - q\mathbf{A})^2\Psi - \frac{q\hbar}{2m}\boldsymbol{\sigma}\mathbf{B}\Psi, \quad (31)$$

where the magnetic field $\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}$ appears explicitly. The equation is famous for describing the motion of non-relativistic silver atoms, which have spin $1/2$, in the Stern-Gerlach experiment. In that experiment, an inhomogeneous magnetic field splits a beam of silver atoms into two beams. This effect is due to the new, last term on the right-hand side, which does not appear in the Schrödinger equation. Depending on the spin orientation, the sign of the last term is either positive or negative. Thus, it acts as a spin-dependent potential. The two options produce the upper and lower beams of silver atoms observed in the Stern-Gerlach experiment. *The spin term implies a g -factor of 2 that is due to the half angle in Dirac's trick.*

In short, an oriented non-relativistic tangle core that rotates **continuously and rigidly** visualizes a spinor and its flag model. The motion of such a tangle follows the Pauli equation for non-relativistic particles with spin $1/2$ and a g -factor of 2. The next step is the exploration of the relativistic case.

24 Rational 3d tangles describe antiparticles

The explanatory power of the strand tangle model is confirmed for the case of antiparticles. In the tangle model, *antiparticles* are mirror tangles that rotate in the opposite direction. Because **all fermion tangles are topologically chiral**, the strand tangle model correctly models the opposite handedness of particles and antiparticles, their opposite charge, and their identical mass values.

Figure 25 illustrates antiparticles using the rational 3d tangles for the electron and the positron. Their tangles will be introduced later on, in Section 28. The tangles reproduce all their quantum numbers. The figure shows that the two tangles can be continuously transformed into each other by moving and rearranging their tethers in space. This possibility explains why *rational* tangles – unknotted tangles formed by braiding tethers and illustrated in Figure 6 – *reproduce* Dirac spinors, for which the particle-antiparticle content can vary *continuously* from one position to the next. Such a continuously varying anti-particle content is observed in experiments and is an essential aspect of the Dirac equation. For example, the transformation of particles into antiparticles is at the basis of Klein's paradox [232]. The ability to reproduce this continuous transformation is a further argument showing that the strand tangle model for particles agrees with observations.

Open knots, prime tangles, and all other knotted tangles do not allow a smooth transition between particles and antiparticles. Only rational 3d tangles – 3d braids – the simplest of all tangles, allow describing transitions from particles to antiparticles. **In particular, rational tangles model virtual particle-antiparticle pairs by temporary local braiding of vacuum strands, as illustrated later on, in Figure 32. Again, only rational tangles allow modeling this process.**

In short, only rational 3d tangles allow visualizing the continuous transition between **real and virtual particles and antiparticles** that is observed in experiments. The transition is reproduced by tether deformations that change tangles into mirror tangles.

Figure 25: The tangle for an electron (left) can be *continuously deformed* into the tangle for a positron (right). One way to proceed is to untwist two neighbouring tethers, shift the third strand, and properly twist the two tethers of the first two strands. Another way to proceed is to flatten all tethers into one plane, to rotate three tethers together against the other three and to bend all six tethers out of the paper plane again.

25 Tangles lead to Dirac spinors and the free Dirac equation

The first *quantitative* derivation of the Dirac equation from tethered rotation was discovered by Battey-Pratt and Racey and published in 1980 [3]. This section introduces the background, gives a short summary of their work, and then shows that the fundamental principle allows using the same derivation for the case of tangles of strands.

Numerous derivations and visualizations of the Dirac equation have been published over the last decades [233]. Among them, in 1965, Loinger and Sparzani [234] showed that the Dirac equation can be visualized with *relativistic spinning tops*. They rewrote a general Dirac spinor, with its four complex and eight real components, as

$$\psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{i\delta} L(\mathbf{v}) R(\alpha/2, \beta/2, \gamma/2) . \quad (32)$$

Here, $\sqrt{\rho}$ is the amplitude of the Dirac spinor, i.e., the square root of the probability density, R

is a matrix with three real parameters describing the orientation and phase of the spin (or flag), L is a matrix with three real parameters describing the relativistic boost transformation, and δ is the fraction of particle and antiparticle. All quantities depend on space and time.

Spinning bodies agree with numerous visualizations of Dirac spinors found in the literature. A spinning top that precesses visualizes the description given by Hestenes [225–228]. A spinning top also visualizes the flag description of spinors [1, 230, 235] if one idealizes the top as a flag. More precisely, a free fermion and antifermion can be visualized [as a spinning flag pair](#) [236]. Spinning tops also agree with hydrodynamic visualization used by Fabbri [237], expanding the papers by Takabayasi and by Jakobi and Lochak cited in it. Feynman’s description of a quantum particle as an *advancing* and *rotating* arrow [175] can be seen as a point-like spinning top.

To derive the full Dirac equation, Battey-Pratt and Racey [3] *added tethers* to the visualization of particles as rotating bodies. Battey-Pratt and Racey explained that tethered rotation – called Dirac’s trick in the present article – can go on forever. They also explained that tethered rotation is described by quaternions and by $SU(2)$. They further showed that relativistic covariance can be included in the description: during the relativistic motion of a *tethered* spinning particle, the average size of Dirac’s trick contracts by the Lorentz factor. For the case that spin orientation is ignored, they deduce the Klein-Gordon equation from the relativistic contraction. They then included antiparticles, though without providing an explicit model for them, and explored the evolution of spin and tethered relativistic rotation over time. Doing so, they showed

- ▷ Dirac’s trick implies the γ^μ matrices and their Clifford algebra.
- ▷ The first two components of the γ^μ matrices describe a particle, whereas the last two components of the γ^μ matrices describe its antiparticle.

In other words, they showed that *Dirac’s gamma matrices arise from tethers*. This result can be confirmed by comparing the Dirac representation of the gamma matrices with the Pauli representation of $SU(2)$, and by deducing the Pauli matrices from tethers. Both the Pauli matrices and the gamma matrices are due to tethers. The result also confirms the connection between the γ^μ matrices and the geometry of spin worked out about a century ago by Fock and Iwanenko [238]. Finally, Battey-Pratt and Racey showed that combining the Lorentz contraction with tethered rotation leads to the Dirac equation for free particles. In simple words, they showed

- ▷ The free Dirac equation is the *differential version* of Dirac’s trick for a tethered, spinning, and relativistic particle.

They wrote to Dirac about their discovery, but he never answered.

The fundamental principle of the strand tangle model rephrases, simplifies, and extends the result of Battey-Pratt and Racey. First of all, quantum particles are not imagined as tethered bodies, but as being themselves made of strands. More precisely, quantum particles are described as rotating and fluctuating rational 3d tangles. Secondly, the fundamental principle automatically introduces Planck’s quantum of action \hbar . Thirdly, particle tangles automatically include antiparticles as mirror tangles. Fourthly, strands are automatically unobservable because of their Planck radius. Fifthly, strands describe empty space as an aggregate of untangled strands. Sixthly, fluctuating tangles automatically introduce wave functions as oriented crossing densities of particle tangles and thus visualize spinors.

In the strand tangle model, a Dirac spinor is described by the geometry of its rotating tangle core. Because the tethers are unobservable, the core can be visualized as a spinning top. The geometry of a spinning top leads to describing a Dirac spinor using the eight real parameters derived from a spinning tangle core: *one* strand crossing density, *three* angles specifying the rotation axis or spin axis and specifying the phase of the core (its flag direction), *three* parameters that describe

the contracted shape of the tangle core and thus specify the boost direction and magnitude, and *one* angle that specifies the relative weight of particle and antiparticle. These eight real parameters defines a complex 4-component *Dirac spinor* $\psi(x)$ as follows:

- ▷ Averaged over a few Planck times, the oriented crossing density of the fluctuating strands in the tangle defines the *amplitude* of the wave function and its square norm defines the probability density.
- ▷ Averaged over a few Planck times, the position of the *centre* of the core yields the *maximum* of the probability density.
- ▷ Averaged over a few Planck times, the orientation of the core crossings yields the *spin orientation*.
- ▷ At each position x , the two *upper* complex components of the Dirac spinor $\psi(x)$ are defined by the local average of finding, at that position, the (tight) tangle, with a given orientation and phase. These components determine the orientation of the flag of the particle spinor. They are described by the two complex components of the Pauli spinor. Density, rotation, and (flag) orientation of the tangle core were defined and visualized in Part II with oriented crossing densities. Figure 12 illustrated the details.
- ▷ At each position x , the two *lower* complex components of the Dirac spinor $\psi(x)$ are defined by the local average of finding, at that position, the (tight) *mirror* tangle, i.e., the antiparticle, with a given orientation and phase. These components determine the flag orientation of the antiparticle spinor. They correspond to two further complex components for the Pauli spinor of the antiparticle.
- ▷ The boost matrix L describes how relativistic boosts flatten the average core. If it is spherical at rest, boosts change it into an ellipsoid, as illustrated in Figure 24.
- ▷ In addition to the visualizations by Battey-Pratt, Racey, Loinger, and Sparzani using spinning bodies, a spinning *rational* 3d tangle also explains the phase δ . This phase describes the relative fraction of particle and anti-particle, i.e., of core and mirror core. The two extreme cases for the phase δ are visualized in Figure 25. *So far, only rational 3d tangles appear to reproduce this angle.*

Therefore, the strand tangle model, with its use of tethered rotation and with its continuous transformation between rational particle and antiparticle (mirror) tangles, reproduces all eight real parameters describing spinors. The eight real parameters describing cores correspond to the four complex numbers used by Dirac in his equation [234, 239, 240]. In other words,

- ▷ Free relativistic fermions are rotating rational 3d tangles.

Because tangles are tethered, the argument chain of Battey-Pratt and Racey can also be applied to tangles of strands.

- ▷ Rational 3d tangles of strands follow the Dirac equation.

It is worth noting that, together with Part IV of this article, strands imply that generalizing Clifford algebras or adding more dimensions does not help in understanding particle physics, because such generalizations are not related to tethers.

A second, *qualitative* argument helps to understand the appearance of the free Dirac equation from strands. The free Dirac equation

$$i\hbar\gamma^\mu\partial_\mu\psi = mc\psi \quad , \quad (33)$$

where ψ is now a complex quantity with four components, is due to five basic properties of nature:

1. The action limit is given by \hbar , which yields wave functions ψ .

2. The speed limit for massive particles is given by c , which yields Lorentz transformations and Lorentz invariance.
3. Spin $1/2$ is described by rotation in Minkowski space-time.
4. Antiparticles exist; their spin requires Dirac's γ^μ matrices.
5. The particle mass value m connects phase rotation frequency and wavelength using the imaginary unit i .

For conventional quantum theory based on continuous wave functions, these five properties are necessary and sufficient to yield the free Dirac equation, as shown by Simulik [241–243]. All five properties also follow from the strand tangle model:

1. All physical observables are due to crossing switches, which imply a minimum observable action \hbar ; oriented crossing densities imply the existence of wave functions.
2. Tethers constrain the tangle cores to advance less than one Planck length per Planck time, which is slower than c (see Figure 2).
3. Tethers reproduce the spin $1/2$ properties for rotation, exchange, and boosts, including fermion behaviour in Minkowski space-time.
4. Tethers yield the γ^μ matrices [3], with tangles and mirror tangles corresponding to particles and antiparticles.
5. Through Dirac's trick, tethers connect tangle core rotation and tangle core displacement and lead to a finite mass value m .

In particular, both in nature and in the strand tangle model, the inability to observe action values below \hbar leads to wave functions and probability densities. Both in nature and in the strand tangle model, the inability to observe speed values larger than c leads to Lorentz invariance and the relativistic energy-momentum relation. Both in nature and in the strand tangle model, a finite mass value, the spin $1/2$ properties, and the γ^μ matrices arise. This implies the Dirac equation for free particles and thus also for tangles of strands. In simple words, both in nature and in the strand tangle model, the fundamental principle associating the quantum of action \hbar to crossing switches leads to the Dirac equation.

In short, the ideas of Battey-Pratt and Racey about tethered rotation imply: fluctuating rotating rational 3d tangles represent spinning relativistic fermions; the oriented crossing densities of such tangles follow the free Dirac equation. This result can be verified.

26 A second derivation of the free Dirac equation

Once Dirac spinors are defined, the simplest derivation of the free Dirac equation might well be the one given in 1996 by Lerner [244]. His derivation is based on only two conditions: conservation of spin current and Lorentz covariance. Lerner showed that together, these two conditions completely and uniquely imply the free Dirac equation.

In the strand tangle model, an advancing particle in a vacuum can be visualized as a tethered maple seed, a tethered propeller, or a tethered spinning top. The definition of spin with tethered rotation implies that particles move in a vacuum at a constant speed; that is, chiral tangle cores move at a constant speed and keep rotating, using Dirac's trick, with a constant rotation frequency. In other words, strand tangles imply that *spin current is conserved* over space and time. No friction

or any other mechanism in the tangle model can destroy spin current conservation. The strands that make up the vacuum produce a constant effect on free particle tangles: their action per time and thus their tangle rotation frequency remains constant. The diffusion of the tangle does not change the conservation of the spin current. Thus, the first condition used by Lerner is fulfilled by tangles.

In addition, the definition of spin using tethers implies the *Lorentz covariance* of spin, i.e., the proper behaviour under rotations and boosts. As mentioned, this property was already explored and confirmed by Battey-Pratt and Racey [3] in 1980. In particular, Lorentz covariance arises because under boosts, the average tangle cores change shape. Cores change of shape under boosts in the same way that a sphere changes to an ellipsoid. Dirac's trick behaves in the same way: the average size and time of the tethers performing the trick change according to special relativity. The strand model thus realizes Lorentz covariance.

In total, both conditions required by Lerner are reproduced by the strand tangle model. Therefore, *strand tangles follow the free Dirac equation*.

Both derivations of the Dirac equation imply the existence of Zitterbewegung. Strands thus confirm that Zitterbewegung is due to tangle core rotation. Both Battey-Pratt and Racey [3] and Hestenes [228] have discussed the issue in detail. Strands confirm their descriptions.

In addition, the derivation by Lerner shows

Test 9: Strands predict the lack of measurable deviations from the free Dirac equation.

Deviations from the free Dirac equation – excluding virtual particle effects due to quantum electrodynamics at this point – have been searched for in detail. So far, for all measurable energies and length scales, no deviation has been found [75], not even in thought experiments [138, 217–219].

In short, Dirac's trick implies the conservation of spin current and follows usual relativistic behaviour. These two properties imply the free Dirac equation. *Dirac's equation is due to Dirac's trick*. In simple words, the strand tangle model agrees with all measurements about phase, spin, and motion of matter and antimatter. This result leads to a further topic.

27 The principle of least action follows from strands

The Dirac equation follows from the principle of least action. In any system in nature, a higher value of the action corresponds to a higher amount of change. In microscopic systems, action is observed to be minimized for sufficiently short times [245]. According to the fundamental principle of the strand tangle model, the action of a physical process is the number of occurring crossing switches. In the strand tangle model, each crossing switch yields an action \hbar . Therefore,

- ▷ Least action is the smallest number of crossing switches.
- ▷ Every motion and every process in nature minimizes the number of crossing switches.

This connection was made beautifully clear by Quincey with his image of a surveyor's wheel [246, 247]. But strands imply more.

Every crossing switch produces a quantum of action. In contrast, a strand shape deformation without a crossing switch does not produce an action. As shown in Figure 26 and as detailed in Section 31, a crossing switch couples to the electromagnetic field. Therefore, every crossing switch requires an 'effort' or 'cost'. Strands confirm that physical *action, the measure of change, has a 'cost'*.

In other words, the coupling to the electromagnetic field implies that crossing switches are less probable than other strand deformations. Therefore, because every amount of observability

Crossing switches *couple* to photons

Figure 26: The geometry of crossing switches leads to coupling to photons. This coupling is the reason that crossing switches are observable and allow measurements. The observability underlines that crossing switches have an objective reality, even though strands are unobservable. The coupling to photons also implies the least action principle. This coupling is also the simplified Planck scale description of the electromagnetic Feynman vertex [129]; the geometry of the coupling between crossing switches and photons determines the fine-structure constant.

implies an effort and comes at a cost, the fundamental principle implies that nature *minimizes* crossing switches. Strands thus imply the *principle of fewest crossing switches*. Thus,

Test 10: Strands predict the lack of the slightest measurable deviation from the least action principle and from the description of motion with Lagrangians. Discovering such a deviation would falsify the strand tangle model.

In particular, the result applies to all motion in the quantum domain.

Because of the fundamental principle and because of the principle of fewest crossing switches, the action for a relativistic particle with spin moving from one space-time point to another will depend on *how often* the tangle core has performed the Dirac trick *in time* on one hand, and on *how many* Dirac tricks have occurred over *distance*, as described by the mass value of the particle, on the other hand. The two aspects yield the two terms of the Lagrangian density for the free Dirac equation that appear in the principle of least action:

$$\mathcal{L} = i\hbar c \bar{\psi} \gamma^\mu \partial_\mu \psi - mc^2 \bar{\psi} \psi . \quad (34)$$

The Dirac Lagrangian yields the action for a free particle that is minimized by minimizing the number of crossing switches occurring for its tangle. The results of Part IV will extend the principle of least action to interacting particles and to gauge fields.

So far, the research literature does not contain any other explanation for the principle of least action. The strand model appears to be the first such explanation.

As a note, strands predict both the lack of measurable deviations from the free Dirac Lagrangian and the lack of trans-Planckian effects. Despite their apparent contradiction, these predictions agree with all observations because the Planck limits of relativistic quantum gravity – those containing c , $4G$, and \hbar – cannot be reached.

In short, even though strands imply the lack of unified equations and of a unified Lagrangian, the fundamental principle of the strand tangle model implies the principle of least action for all measurable microscopic processes in nature. This might well be the first explanation of the principle. This result confirms the validity of the Dirac equation in a third way, complementing the two ways given above.

Part IV: Differences to conventional quantum theory

Thus far, the strand tangle model deduced from the fundamental principle has *reproduced* conventional quantum theory and *allowed to visualize* wave functions. If these were the only results, the strand tangle model would be unnecessary: Occam’s razor would speak against it. However, the strand tangle model and quantum theory *differ*. The differences are due to the possibility of classifying particle tangles, classifying core deformations, and calculating average core shapes. Tangle classification is possible because *elementary* particles are the *simplest possible* tangles:

- ▷ Elementary particles are *rational 3d* tangles of one, two or three strands.

The concept of rational 3d tangle was introduced in Figure 6. Rational 3d tangles arise by braiding tethers, i.e., by moving tethers around in space. Therefore, such tangles contain cores but do not contain knotted regions. Rational 3d tangles are three-dimensional generalizations of braids, in which all tethers are distributed over all directions as much as possible. It will appear that modelling elementary particles as rational 3d tangles *explains, derives and fixes* their spectrum, spins, charges, quantum numbers, masses, and all other particle properties.

Also the *interactions* of particle tangles can be classified. The observed gauge interactions arise, and no other ones. It will appear that rational 3d tangles *explain, derive and fix* the gauge interactions, their Lie groups and their coupling constants.

In short, in contrast to continuous wave functions, the strand tangle model promises to restrict quantum field theory to a specific set of allowed elementary particles and to a specific set of allowed interactions. [The strand tangle model can be tested by comparing the allowed particle properties, including the mass values, and the allowed interaction properties, including the gauge groups and coupling constants, with experiments. This comparison is performed in the following.](#)

28 Classifying tangles leads to the spectrum of elementary fermions

This and the following sections deduce how classifying rational strand tangles leads to the observed spectrum of elementary fermions and bosons, with their observed quantum numbers, repeating the arguments of references [127–130].

Dirac’s trick implies that fermions are *non-trivial* rational tangles. Only non-trivial rational tangles, illustrated in Figure 6, can be localized at a point in space by ‘pulling’ their tethers; only non-trivial rational tangles differ from their mirror tangles, i.e., from their antiparticles. Non-trivial rational tangles made of one strand do not exist. One-stranded rational particle tangles can neither have spin $1/2$ nor have mass, because Dirac’s trick does not apply to them, as argued in Part I of this article. To allow Dirac’s trick, fermions must be made of two or more strands.

In nature, a fermion is *elementary* if it is smaller than its Compton wavelength. In the strand model, a fermion is *elementary* if its core is smaller than its Compton wavelength, in other words, if Dirac’s trick occurs *around* its core.

Elementary particle tangles can only be made of one, two, or three strands. Rational 3d tangles of more than three strands are always larger than their Compton wavelength: the Dirac trick can occur separately for at least two parts of such a tangle. *More than three strands* form *composite* particles, such as hadrons [130], or even more complex systems, such as atoms or people. In other words, rational 3d tangles of more than three strands can always be decomposed – by pulling them apart – into simpler tangles. For fermions, this decomposition stops once the elementary tangles of Figure 27 are reached. Therefore, *elementary fermions* can only consist of two or three strands. No *simpler* rational 3d fermion tangle is missing.

Quarks: 'tetrahedral' tangles made of two strands with four tethers (only simplest family members)

Parity $P = +1$, Baryon number $B = +1/3$, Spin $S = 1/2$

Charge $Q = -1/3$

Charge $Q = +2/3$

Leptons: 'cubic' tangles made of three strands along coordinate axes (only simplest family members)

Figure 27: The figure shows the simplest conjectured tangle for each elementary fermion. Elementary fermions are rational 3d tangles that are formed by braiding tethers. All elementary fermion tangles are non-trivial and consist of two or three strands. The tangles yield spin $1/2$ and fermion behaviour. The cores are localized, realize Dirac's trick, and thus yield positive mass values. The localized cores lead to additional, more complex tangles in addition to those shown here. They are illustrated in Figure 28 and Figure 29 and explain the three generations. At large distances from the tangle core, the four tethers of quarks approach the axes of a tetrahedron, and the six tethers of leptons approach the coordinate axes. The tangles of the quarks, the electron, muon, and tau are topologically chiral and thus electrically charged. Neutrino cores are twisted strand triplets: they are geometrically chiral, but not topologically chiral; thus, they are electrically neutral. No additional elementary fermions appear.

The origin of the 3 quark generations

Figure 28: Each *quark* is described by a tangle family with an infinite number of tangles of two strands. The six families define the six quark types and the three generations. The same classification arises for anti-quarks, which are represented by the respective mirror tangles; they are not shown here. In the strand tangle model, the number of generations is thus related to the structure of the Higgs braid, which is itself a result of the three dimensions of space.

The origin of the 3 lepton generations

Figure 29: Each *lepton* is described by a tangle family with an infinite number of tangles of three strands. The simplest tangles for each lepton are shown at the top of the figure. The tangles due to one added Higgs boson are shown further down. The six families define the six lepton types and the three generations. Anti-leptons are represented by the corresponding mirror tangles; they are not shown.

There is another way to see that in the strand tangle model, *elementary* rational 3d tangles can consist at most of three strands. When a strand is added to form a *more complex* rational 3d tangle than those of Figure 27 or Figure 36, one gets one of the following two cases:

- The more complex tangle can be a tangle already found in the two figures. For example, a photon tangle that is extended by tangling an additional strand can yield, depending on the details, a graviton tangle, a quark tangle, or an (unbroken) weak W_i tangle. Similarly, a strand added to a quark tangle can lead to a lepton tangle. These cases lead to cores that are smaller than their Compton wavelength and thus lead from one elementary particle to another.
- The more complex tangle can be taken apart into simpler tangles connected by strands that blend into vacuum strands. For example, this occurs if a strand is added to a gluon tangle or to a W tangle. The resulting four-stranded core can be decomposed – pulled apart – into *several* elementary tangle cores. The same occurs if a strand is added to a lepton; such a four-strand tangle can also be separated into two simpler cores.

In simple words, all elementary tangles have at most three strands. Comparing the topological details listed below shows that

- ▷ Two-stranded fermions are *quarks*. Three-stranded fermions are *leptons*.

One notes that the cores of the heavier charged leptons can be seen as combinations of electron cores and W cores, which reproduces their observed weak decay behaviour. Alternatively, the cores of the heavier quarks can be seen as combinations of lighter quark cores and W cores, or equivalently, as combinations of lighter quarks and partial Higgs tangles. This reproduces their observed mixing and the expected mass generation mechanism.

The six tethers of the leptons blend into the surrounding vacuum strands: far from the core, the tethers behave like geodesics and allow leptons to appear as free particles. The four tethers of the quarks do not blend into the surrounding vacuum strands: even far from the core, the tethers do not behave like geodesics and prevent quarks from arising as free particles. Quarks need to form composites to allow their tethers to behave like geodesics that blend into the vacuum and thus to behave as free particles. Using the tangle model of the strong interaction, the quark-tangle assignments in Figure 27 fully reproduce the quark model of hadrons, as shown in references [128] and [130]. The allowed and forbidden meson quantum numbers are explained. The meson tangle structures also provide natural and correct deductions of which mesons violate CP symmetry. The hadron tangles also reproduce all meson and baryon mass sequences.

All fermions also have *additional* tangles, as illustrated in Figure 28 for quarks and in Figure 29 for leptons. Every massive elementary particle is described by an infinite *family* of tangles that contains the simplest possible core, the simplest core plus one complete Higgs braid, the simplest core plus two Higgs braids, etc. Thus, the strand tangle model reproduces *Yukawa coupling* as an important aspect of particle mass.

Figure 28 shows how the infinite class of quark-like tangles consists of six infinite families, corresponding to three generations with two quarks each. In other words, the infinitely many possible quark and antiquark tangles consist of $6 + 6$ separate infinite tangle families. Each quark family is an infinite series of tangles. In a family, each tangle differs from the next by one Higgs braid. The structure of the Higgs braid thus limits quarks to three generations. A similar structure of six tangle families arises for the leptons. They are illustrated in Figure 29.

An important check for the tangle–particle assignments are the resulting quantum numbers. In nature, quantum numbers lead to conservation laws that restrict particle reactions.

Baryon and lepton number count tangle cores with two and three strands. In addition, the

braiding of an additional strand can describe non-perturbative effects, such as baryon number non-conservation and sphalerons, that arise in the early universe.

Spin was already discussed in Part I. Because elementary fermions are composed of only two or three strands, one obtains:

Test 11: The strand tangle model implies that all elementary fermions are massive.

Test 12: Strands implies that all elementary fermions have spin $1/2$.

The first statement confirms that neutrinos are massive Dirac fermions. It agrees with all experiments so far [75]. Also the second statement, a consequence of tethers, agrees with all experiments so far. The second statement eliminates elementary fermions of spin $3/2$ and thus eliminates supersymmetry. Indeed, all fermions with higher spin values observed so far, such as various nuclei, are *composed*.

Flavour quantum numbers count the tangles of a specific flavour, i.e., tangles of a specific topology (or from the corresponding family). Quark tangles automatically provide the correct values by counting the respective cores.

Charge parity C is the topological chirality of a tangle core. This assignment reproduces all the observed C parities of the elementary particles.

Electric charge is the signed number of crossings involved in the topological chirality of a tangle. Each crossing yields a charge $e/3$ or $-e/3$, depending on the sign of the crossing [129]. This assignment reproduces the observed electric charge values of all elementary particles. Because of its topological definition based on chirality, electric charge does not depend on tangle shape, i.e., does not depend on the state of a particle; electric charge can only have two signs; it is additive; antiparticles have opposite charge; electric charge interacts in a preferred way with photons of one (geometric) chirality or helicity; finally, electric charge is automatically conserved in interactions. There does not seem to be any other way to define electric charge. Strands also imply that magnetic charge cannot arise.

Parity P describes the behaviour of a tangle under spatial reflections. This assignment reproduces all the observed P parities of the elementary particles. Parity violation by the weak interaction is discussed below.

Time reversal T changes the tangle spin and direction of motion. This assignment reproduces the observed behaviour under time reversal of all elementary particles. The CPT theorem is automatically satisfied, as is observed.

Weak and strong charge are also explained for each fermion and boson. They are explored in references [128] and [130]. The charges explain the interactions to which the corresponding particles are subjected and reproduce all observations.

In the strand model, all quantum numbers are *topological invariants*. Because of this topological basis, quantum numbers are integers and not influenced by strand fluctuations and changes of particle state. The strand definitions explain why quantum numbers are either additive or multiplicative and why they are conserved.

In the strand model, no other elementary fermions appear to be topologically possible.

Test 13: Strands predict the lack of contradictions between tangle properties and observed particle properties, such as forbidden values of quantum numbers, new quantum numbers, or unexpected non-conservation. For example, millicharged particles, leptoquarks, Majorana particles, or weakly charged particles without mass are predicted not to exist.

Test 14: Strands predict the lack of any unknown energy scale in high-energy physics.

Test 15: Strands predict the lack of any substructure in elementary particles that *differs* from tangles of strands. This includes the preons and ribbons discussed in Appendix D, the

superstrings discussed in Appendix E, Möbius bands, prequarks, knots, tori, loops, and any other localised or extended substructure [113–116, 122, 123].

Test 16: Strands predict the lack of any new elementary fermion of any kind. This includes the lack of sterile neutrinos, magnetic monopoles [248], and supersymmetric partners.

So far, all observations confirm the predictions [75]. The last prediction will be extended to a full prediction about dark matter below. Any experimental counterexample would immediately falsify the strand tangle model.

It should be noted that the tangle model of fermions is compatible with several particle models in the research literature that are deduced from general relativity with and without torsion. In models such as those of Popławski [249] or of Burinskii [250, 251], an elementary fermion is assumed to be a Planck-scale *torus*. In the tangle model, Figure 25 shows that an electron can be seen as three spinning crossings – once the unobservable tethers are ignored and only crossings are kept. In practice, this yields a structure similar to a fuzzy torus that is always larger than a few Planck lengths and which can be as large as a Compton wavelength. The same properties are deduced in the cited papers on torus models. However, it must be stressed that strands *eliminate* the concept of electron radius, or of any other elementary particle radius. Elementary particles are not spherical objects.

In short, in the strand tangle model, the classification of elementary fermion tangles leads to the three generations of leptons and quarks. No additional elementary fermion appears possible. All observed quantum numbers are due to *topological* properties of the particle tangles. As a consequence, the fermions due to tangles cancel the anomalies of the standard model, as required [252, 253]. As shown later on, in contrast to the quantum numbers, the fundamental constants – mass values, mixing angles, and coupling constants – are due to *geometric* properties, namely to the (average) *shape* of tangles. **Without exception, the statements deduced from the strand tangle model agree with observations. Any counterexample would immediately falsify the model.**

29 Classifying tangle deformations leads to interactions and gauge groups

So far, only *free* particles have been described with tangles. The next task is to explore the *interactions* of particles and to determine their properties. The present section summarizes previous papers on the strand tangle explanation of the origin of the gauge groups, the origin of quantum electrodynamics, the origin of quantum chromodynamics with the quark model, and the origin of the full standard model [125–130].

In free particle motion, tangle cores remain *rigid*. In line with the geometric effects of Hermitian operators, interactions arise when tangle cores do *not* behave like rigid structures:

- ▷ Gauge interactions are observable deformations of tangle cores.

In other words, gauge interactions are *deformations* of tangles that lead to crossing switches. This statement is promising for two reasons. First, on scales larger than the Planck scale, all observable tangle core deformations and thus all interactions appear to be *local*.. Secondly, all deformations that change crossings can be *classified*.

The classification of deformations that change crossings is possible with the help of the mathematical theorem published by Reidemeister in 1927 [137]. The theorem states that there are only three possible *Reidemeister moves*: *twists*, *pokes* and *slides*. These three basic deformations are illustrated on the left side of Figure 30. *Every* observable tangle core deformation is *composed* of the three Reidemeister moves. As shown now, exploring the three Reidemeister moves yields

Figure 30: In an interaction, a gauge boson rotates the bent strand segment enclosed by a dotted circle. The *observable* deformations of tangle cores can be classified with *Reidemeister's theorem*. The three possible *Reidemeister moves* specify the generators of the three observed gauge interactions and determine the generator algebras, as shown in the subsequent figures. The full gauge group arises when the rotations by the angle π induced by the generators are generalized to arbitrary angles. As a result, the three Reidemeister moves determine the three gauge groups [125, 127].

a surprising result: the three moves generate the local gauge groups $U(1)$, (unbroken) $SU(2)$ and $SU(3)$ [125, 126]. In addition, each Reidemeister move yields the tangle for its gauge bosons.

Figure 30 shows how an approaching gauge boson core deforms a fermion core. The gauge boson is absorbed and becomes a vacuum strand; the induced local fermion core deformation leads to a local phase change in the fermion core. Exploring the details yields complete agreement with experiments. In particular, modelling interactions as core deformations implies minimal coupling, as the deformation depends on the density of arriving gauge bosons. Minimal coupling and local

Figure 31: The *twist*, the first Reidemeister move, leads to a local Lie group U(1). When twists – rotations of the region inside the dotted circle by π – are generalized to arbitrary angles, they yield all the group elements of U(1). The twist also yields the strand tangle model for the photon.

gauge symmetry lead to the usual Lagrangians of QED, of QCD, of the weak interaction with its symmetry breaking, and thus to the full Lagrangian of the standard model [127–130].

Test 17: Strands predict the lack of the tiniest deviation from minimal coupling, for every gauge interaction, at *any* measurable energy or scale.

This prediction agrees with all observations [75]. Strands visualize the result.

Figure 31 shows that a twist, or *first* Reidemeister move, can be visualized as the local rotation by π of *one* strand segment. In the figure, the segment is enclosed by a dotted circle that can be imagined as a transparent plastic disc glued to it. *Generalized* twists can be seen as local rotations by an *arbitrary* angle of the segment or disc. One notes directly that performing a *double* twist is equivalent to *no* rotation. It is straightforward to check that the set of generalized twists also fulfils all other axioms of the U(1) Lie group [125]. As a result, *photons are permanently rotating twists*. The freedom in defining the twist phase yields local U(1) gauge symmetry. The twist model for photons implies the photon propagator and thus the Lagrangian of the electromagnetic field.

Core twists reproduce quantum electrodynamics in all its details, as shown in reference [129]. Figure 32 and Figure 33 use strands to illustrate a selection of processes involving virtual particles. Perturbative QED, including the running of the fine-structure constant, appears automatically [129]. In the limit of many photons, classical electrodynamics arises from strands. *Electric fields* are volume densities of virtual photons, i.e., of bound twists. *Magnetic fields* are flow densities of (bound) twists. In other words, photon exchange or twist exchange implies that the *electromagnetic field* is defined by the space-time rotation rate it induces on an electric charge. *Electric charge* results from topological tangle chirality. This leads to minimal coupling and visualizes the descriptions by Feynman [175], Hestenes [225–227], and Baylis [239, 240].

Test 18: No massless, electrically charged elementary particle will be found.

Test 19: Not the slightest deviation from the local U(1) gauge group or from quantum electrodynamics, at *any* measurable energy, will be observed.

Thus far, all observations have confirmed the strand tangle model of electromagnetism [129], which fully reproduces quantum electrodynamics. For example, Furry’s theorem is automatically realized by strands [254].

In the strand tangle model, the gauge group SU(2) arises from *pokes*, that is, from the *second* Reidemeister move. Pokes can be seen as local rotations by the angle π of *two* strand segments, as illustrated in Figure 34. Again, the three possible pokes are best visualized by imagining that

Figure 32: Two processes from quantum electrodynamics are shown in their strand representation. Top: strands describe the appearance and disappearance of a virtual electron-positron pair. Bottom: strands describe the annihilation of an electron and a positron. This description yields no deviation from quantum electrodynamics, at any measurable energy.

the dotted circle encloses a transparent plastic disc that contains, in this case, *two* parallel strand segments. The plastic disc behaves like a belt buckle. Its three possible rotations by π form the *algebra* of $SU(2)$ [125–127]. Indeed, Figure 34 directly shows that the three pokes behave under concatenation in the same way as i times the Pauli spin matrices

$$\tau_x = i\sigma_x = i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \tau_y = i\sigma_y = i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \tau_z = i\sigma_z = i \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (35)$$

behave under multiplication [125]. Indeed, the matrices can be directly read off from the figure.

Figure 33: Two further processes studied in quantum electrodynamics are shown in their strand representation. Top: a free electron emitting and absorbing a virtual photon. Bottom: an electron and a positron interacting via a virtual photon. Again, this description yields no deviation from quantum electrodynamics, at any measurable energy.

(Their relation to the unit quaternions is well known.) *Generalized* pokes are defined as local rotations by an *arbitrary* angle of plastic disc enclosing the two strand segments. It is straightforward to verify that generalized pokes realize the $SU(2)$ Lie group axioms [125]. The freedom in defining phases yields the corresponding local gauge symmetry. Together with the minimal coupling illustrated in Figure 30, this result yields the full (unbroken) weak interaction Lagrangian.

Strands imply that only massive fermions can exchange weak bosons: only massive particles interact weakly. Strands also imply and predict that neutrinos have mass. Strands explain why Pauli matrices appear in the context of spin, in equation (29) and in the context of the weak interaction, in equation (35). As a consequence, due to the tangle structure of particles, *maximal parity violation* arises: parity violation occurs because core rotations due to spin $1/2$ resemble the core deformations due to the group $SU(2)$ of the weak interactions [127, 128]. In addition,

The poke, or second Reidemeister move, on pairs of strands generates an $SU(2)$ Lie group, because the three rotations by π generate the algebra of $SU(2)$:

Figure 34: The three types of *pokes*, the second Reidemeister moves, are visualized. Pokes can be modelled by rotating by the angle π a region – inside the dotted circle – containing both strands. (A visualization deforming only one strand is also possible.) The three pokes generate the Lie algebra of $SU(2)$ and imply a model for (unbroken) weak bosons. The Pauli matrices can be read off directly [125].

also $SU(2)$ *breaking* arises: a vacuum strand is included in the unbroken, massless weak bosons and leads to the W and Z boson tangles [127, 128]. Also the Higgs mechanism is reproduced. In other words, W and Z bosons are derived from permanently rotating pokes. The freedom in defining the poke phase yields local $SU(2)$ gauge symmetry. The models for W and Z imply their propagators and the Lagrangian of the weak field. Also particle *mixing* is a consequence of the strand tangle model of the weak interaction: it arises from tether braiding, itself a specific type of poke deformation.

Test 20: Strands predict the lack of deviations from the weak interaction properties of the standard model with massive mixing Dirac neutrinos, at *any* measurable energy.

So far, all observations confirm the strand tangle model of the weak interaction, which completely reproduces the conventional description of the standard model of particle physics [75].

In the tangle model, the local gauge group $SU(3)$ arises from *slides*, the *third* Reidemeister moves. The set of the fundamental slides is illustrated in Figure 35. Slides are best visualized by imagining that the dotted circle encloses a transparent plastic disc that contains, in this case, two crossing strand segments. Exploring the algebra of the local disc rotations by π in the figure, one

Slides, or **third Reidemeister moves**, acting on strand pairs in three-strand structures, can be generalized to the generators of the Lie group $SU(3)$.

Figure 35: The ten important deformations deduced from the *slide*, the third Reidemeister move, are visualized. Slides can be modelled by rotating the region inside the dotted circle by the angle π . Each triplet row defines an $SU(2)$ subgroup. (Other visualizations are also possible, e.g., by deforming only one strand.) With the definition of λ_8 , the eight slides $i\lambda_1, \dots, i\lambda_8$ (thus without $i\lambda_9$ and $i\lambda_{10}$) generate the Lie group $SU(3)$ and imply a model for gluons. Each of these eight deformations corresponds to i times a Gell-Mann matrix [125].

observes that they behave like i times the matrices [125]:

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda_1 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_2 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_3 &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \\
\lambda_4 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_5 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_9 &= \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \\
\lambda_6 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_7 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_{10} &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \\
&&&& \text{and } \lambda_8 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{36}
\end{aligned}$$

In particular, the matrices can be directly read off from the figure. One notes that slides 3, 9 and 10 are linearly dependent; to get an orthonormal basis, it is conventional to use only slide 3 and the additionally defined slide $\lambda_8 = (\lambda_{10} - \lambda_9)/\sqrt{3}$. The threefold axis at the centre of the three-strand configuration yields the factor $1/\sqrt{3}$, which is due to the sine of the angle $2\pi/3$. This yields the orthonormal basis of the eight *Gell-Mann matrices* $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_8$ that realize the trace relations $\text{tr } \lambda_n = 0$ and $\text{tr}(\lambda_n \lambda_m) = 2\delta_{nm}$. As Figure 35 shows, only λ_8 is an actual slide, or third Reidemeister move, in the original sense of the term. This might explain why the relation between the third Reidemeister move and the algebra of $SU(3)$ was discovered so late [126]. The matrices λ_9 and λ_{10} are not Gell-Mann matrices. However, together with their corresponding slides, the two matrices are useful for visualizing the three $SU(2)$ subgroups of $SU(3)$.

In other words, the slides 1 to 8 generate the Lie algebra of $SU(3)$. *Generalized* slides, or *generalized* third Reidemeister moves, are rotations by an *arbitrary* angle of the two crossing strand segments enclosed by the circular plastic discs illustrated in Figure 35. These generalized slides realize all the required axioms and yield the full, local $SU(3)$ Lie group. This is the main result of previous publications [125–128]. The implied freedom of phase definition yields local $SU(3)$ gauge symmetry. As a result, gluons are permanently ongoing slides with a rotating phase. This model for gluons yields the gluon propagator. The strand model of the gluon also yields the three-gluon and four-gluon vertices. As a consequence, strands yield the Lagrangian of the strong fields.

As shown in reference [130], the strand tangle model for the strong interaction implies the quark model of hadrons, yielding their correct quantum numbers. Colour fields are densities of virtual gluons. The gluon tangles yield glueballs, with their observed quantum numbers. Modelling the strong interaction as gluon exchange implies minimal coupling and asymptotic freedom. The strand tangle model also implies that the strong interaction *cannot* produce CP violation. The tangle model of hadrons yields the correct sequence of tangle complexity and thus yields the correct mass sequences among hadrons. The colour charge of a quark tangle is given by the orientation of its three-ended side in space. Because of their strand structure, gluons carry a double colour charge. As a consequence, colour charge is conserved.

Test 21: No deviation from quantum chromodynamics, at *any* energy, will ever be observed.

The strand tangle model of the strong interaction [130], including the first estimate of the strong coupling constant summarized below, agrees with quantum chromodynamics and [with all observations](#) [75].

In total, strands yield an emergent model for electromagnetic fields, for weak interaction fields, and for strong interaction fields. The field intensities are densities of the corresponding gauge bosons, which are strand configurations specified by the Reidemeister moves. Because only three Reidemeister moves exist, the strand tangle model implies:

Test 22: No other gauge group – such as $SU(5)$, $SO(10)$, E_8 , or any gauge supergroup – will be observed, at *any* energy. Grand unification is impossible.

This prediction agrees with all data [75]. The strand tangle model thus eliminates many unification attempts. The strand description of gauge theories also solves the Yang-Mills millennium problem, as told in Appendix F. Because strands eliminate other symmetries, strands also respect the Coleman-Mandula theorem [255].

The research literature on the strand-gauge connection is limited. The visualization of the three gauge interactions with strands agrees with and extends the ideas of Boudet [256]. He described gauge theory using geometric concepts, in parallel to the approach by Hestenes [225–227]. Strands can be seen as a way to simplify both descriptions.

The appearance of virtual particles from the strand tangle model has been treated extensively in other publications [129, 130]. *Virtual particles* are particles whose tethers do not all reach the cosmological horizon. In other words, virtual particles arise as short-lived deformations of vacuum strands or particle strands. This model of virtual particles reproduces all their effects in quantum field theory, without measurable deviations. So far, no other model in the literature provides this explanation and this agreement with observations.

In short, when gauge interactions are modelled as *deformations* of elementary particle tangle cores, gauge interactions are automatically local (at scales larger than the Planck scale). Classifying observable deformations yields only three possible types: each Reidemeister move leads to a gauge interaction. The three possible Reidemeister moves – twists, pokes and slides – determine the gauge groups $U(1)$, $SU(2)$ and $SU(3)$, as implied by Figure 30 and as explored in references [125–130]. The resulting charges, conserved quantities, symmetry breaking and other aspects agree with observations. In the strand tangle model, gauge fields are densities of the corresponding gauge bosons and lead to minimal coupling. No other gauge groups are predicted to exist in nature. Virtual particles appear automatically in the strand tangle model. All these consequences follow from the fundamental principle.

30 Classifying tangles leads to the spectrum of elementary bosons

In the strand tangle model, *elementary bosons* consist of one, two, or three strands [125, 127–130]. More strands imply composite particles or groups of *several* bosons. The Reidemeister moves, illustrated in Figure 30, directly suggest that one-stranded bosons correspond to photons, two-stranded bosons to the weak unbroken W_1 , W_2 and W_3 bosons, and three-stranded bosons to gluons. This assignment is valid before the breaking of $SU(2)$ gauge symmetry.

A complete overview of all the possible elementary boson tangles is given in Figure 36. All unbroken elementary gauge boson tangles are *trivial*, that is, topologically untangled, as Figure 36 shows. The tangles of the unbroken gauge bosons can be described as one bent strand among straight strands. The bent strand implies spin 1: gauge bosons are vector bosons. The bends in the tangles can *transfer* or *hop* from one strand to the next, yielding boson behaviour. The size of the bent strands defines the wavelength and corresponds to the region carrying energy. The region of the bent strands is thus the region that allows observation and detection of the boson.

The W and Z bosons, also shown in Figure 36, form a special case. They are composed of three strands that (asymptotically) lie along a line. They arise from the unbroken bosons by the

Elementary bosons are simple configurations of 1, 2 or 3 strands that propagate:

Figure 36: The proposed rational 3d tangles for each elementary boson are illustrated. Their tangles are composed of one, two, or three strands. For each gauge boson, the tangle structure determines the spin value 1 because any curved strand can rotate by 2π and return to its original shape. The graviton has spin 2 because each of its curved strands can rotate by π and return to the original shape. Except for the Higgs, all boson tangle cores rotate during propagation. Both photons and gluons are massless and thus are described by a single tangle. The W and Z tangles are asymptotically linear. The W, Z and Higgs are localizable and thus have mass; therefore, they also have more complex tangle family members, in addition to the simplest ones shown here. The W tangle core is topologically chiral thus is electrically charged. No additional elementary bosons are predicted to exist.

addition of a vacuum strand. The process is usually called the Higgs mechanism, yields the three-stranded, massive W and Z bosons, and breaks the $SU(2)$ symmetry. Their linear overall structure – which distinguishes the W from the electron and from the electron neutrino – implies spin 1, boson behaviour, and a non-vanishing mass. No other elementary boson with spin 1 appears topologically possible. The W boson is the only elementary boson with a topologically chiral core and thus is the only boson with an electric charge. The tangle has a unit electrical charge because it contains three crossings of the same chirality.

In the strand tangle model, the *Higgs boson* is a complete braid of three strands with six crossings. Random fluctuations in its tangle do not lead to its rotation. For this reason, the Higgs tangle has spin 0. The tangle is not chiral, thus electrically neutral, has positive P parity, and has no strong charge. Among rational 3d tangles, only a full braid has spin 0 and reproduces the observed positive parity values.

Test 23: Strands predict the lack of any *additional Higgs boson*.

This agrees with data [75]. No other elementary boson with spin 0 appears topologically possible. Observing an additional Higgs boson would immediately falsify the strand tangle model.

For every massive particle, the core can be extended by adding one or several Higgs braids. This does not change any quantum number because the Higgs has the same quantum numbers as the vacuum. Therefore, every massive particle – fermion or boson – is described by an *infinite set* of tangles. Some of these options are illustrated in Figure 28 and Figure 29. The value of particle mass is influenced by the addition of one or several Higgs braids. Only the Higgs braid produces this mass-influencing property.

The processes illustrated in Figure 28 and Figure 29 imply that the Higgs boson couples to itself. The self-coupling, illustrated in Figure 39, implies that the Higgs boson is massive. Both properties are observed [75]. In contrast, no Higgs braid can be added to cores of massless elementary particles.

The *graviton*, the last elementary boson, has an unlocalized core that returns to itself after a rotation by π ; thus it has spin 2 and is a boson. Because of its non-localized structure, shown in Figure 36, the graviton has a vanishing mass. Every massive spinning particle continuously emits and absorbs virtual gravitons. This mechanism for gravitational mass is as expected. With the help of the graviton, strands describe general relativity with its field equations and its Lagrangian [58, 59, 127]. Cosmology is also reproduced. Also black hole thermodynamics, the Unruh effect, and relativistic quantum gravity arise. No other elementary boson with spin 2 appears topologically possible.

As mentioned, topologically trivial tangles imply that all elementary particles with integer spin are bosons and vice versa. Particle composition was explored in Section 6. Therefore,

Test 24: Strands predict that no elementary boson has spin 3 or larger.

This deduction agrees with observations: all known high-spin bosons are composed, *none is elementary* [75].

No additional elementary vector gauge boson appears possible: neither is a higher number of strands possible in an elementary particle, nor is a more complex tangling of strands compatible with boson properties. The boson tangles for photons, gluons, and gravitons imply that these particles are massless; their tangle cores can rotate unhindered by tethers, in contrast to the W, Z, and Higgs bosons, which cannot. These latter tangles have to perform low-probability tether motions to advance and therefore have mass.

Test 25: Strands predict the lack of any *additional elementary vector gauge boson*.

Once tangles are assigned to the gauge bosons, the corresponding charges can be defined from the topological properties of their tangles. *Electric charge* is related to the topological chirality of a tangle [129]. *Colour charge* is related to the threefold symmetry of quark and gluon tethers [130]. *Weak charge* is due to a combination of chiral tangle topology and geometry. Thus,

Test 26: Strands predict conservation of electric and colour charge, but the lack of weak charge conservation.

Test 27: Strands predict the lack of additional charge types.

Strands naturally imply the lack of localized composites of photon tangles. The possibility of extremely short-lived ZZ-composites or W^+W^- composites appears unrealistic. In contrast, glueballs, composites of gluons, are allowed by the strand tangle model [130]; so are many other boson composites, from meson molecules to organic molecules. In total, strands forbid some boson composites:

Test 28: Strands predict the lack of ‘photonballs’.

Test 29: Strands predict the lack of glueballs with incorrect quantum numbers [130].

In contrast, strands reproduce the existence of entangled bosons, such as biphotons. These are regularly observed [257].

The classification of elementary bosons implies

Test 30: Strands predict the lack of *further elementary bosons*, of any spin.

In particular, the strand tangle model predicts the absence of additional gauge bosons, supersymmetric bosons, or additional Higgs bosons. In combination with the previous section on fermions, the prediction becomes even more general:

Test 31: Strands predict the lack of *any new elementary* particle – including dilatons, inflatons, geons, leptoquarks, anyons, axions [258], metaparticles [259], photinos, gluinos, gravitinos, sterile neutrinos and any elementary dark matter particle.

Test 32: Dark matter, both galactic and cosmological, if it exists at all, is predicted to consist of known matter, i.e., of black holes and particles from the standard model.

The predictions follow from the strand tangle model of elementary particles and from its classification of the possible rational 3d tangles – assuming no mistakes or oversights. So far, they agree with all observations.

In short, classifying elementary boson tangles reproduces the unbroken gauge bosons with trivial tangles of one, two, or three strands, reproduces the observed mass-producing Higgs boson with a braid, yields W and Z mass, implies the twisted two-stranded spin-2 graviton, and **leaves no room for additional elementary bosons**. Any contrasting experiment would immediately falsify the strand tangle model.

31 All measurements are electromagnetic

In nature, every observation, every measurement process, and every measurement device makes use of electromagnetism. For example, all human senses, including hearing and touch, use electromagnetic effects. Also all seven base units of the International System of Units (SI) are defined and applied using electromagnetic means of observation. Likewise, every comparison with a standard or a unit uses electromagnetism. Examples are the reading of a balance, of a length value on a ruler, of the hands of a watch, or of a thermometer.

In the strand tangle model, the fundamental principle illustrated in Figure 5 defines all observations, all measurements, and all physical observables as consequences of crossing switches. The details of the electromagnetic interaction – summarized in Figure 18 – imply that *crossing switches are observable because they couple to electromagnetic fields*. The coupling is illustrated by Figure 26. Strands thus confirm at the most fundamental level that without electromagnetism, there are *no* observations and *no* measurements.

Test 33: Performing any non-electromagnetic observation or measurement is impossible. Performing one would falsify the strand tangle model.

The fundamental, Planck-scale principle of the strand tangle model for a photon

A **photon** is described by a moving and rotating **arrow** ↑

Figure 37: A photon can be used to visualize the fundamental principle of the strand tangle model when the strand radius r is the Planck length. The average size of the photon loop corresponds to its wavelength.

The report by Chew [260] makes the same statement.

Strands thus explain why crossing switches are observable: crossing switches couple to electromagnetism. In contrast, single moving strand segments or simple strand deformations do not couple to electromagnetism and thus are not observable. Therefore, strands *explain* the fundamental principle. Equivalently, the fundamental principle can be illustrated with Figure 37.

The relation between crossing switches and electromagnetism also explains how the minimum time $\sqrt{4\hbar G/c^5}$ arises in the fundamental principle. A crossing switch could, in principle, take an arbitrarily short time. However, such a trans-Planckian crossing switch cannot couple to the electromagnetic field: a photon wavelength shorter than a (corrected) Planck length is impossible. A trans-Planckian crossing switch would have no physical effect and would be unobservable.

Test 34: Strands predict the lack of any measurable effect due to time or length intervals shorter than the corrected Planck limits.

The conclusion confirms the results of Section 1.

In short, the fundamental principle implies that all measurements are electromagnetic. Strands also imply that only crossing switches that take longer than the minimum time are observable. No trans-Planckian effect is predicted to be measurable or to play a role in nature. These deductions agree with all observations. Any contrasting experiment would immediately falsify the strand tangle model.

32 Strands limit the possible interaction vertices of the standard model

The strand description of interactions also proves that, as a consequence, particle reactions and decays are described by Feynman diagrams. At the same time, tangles *restrict* the possible interactions and vertices. This section summarizes the results published in references [127–130].

The tangles of the elementary fermions and bosons given in Sections 28 and 30 allow only a *limited number* of interaction vertices. The lack of additional interaction vertices is due to the structure of the rational 3d tangles for the elementary particles. Given that elementary tangles consist of at most 3 strands, and that at most one vacuum strand can be involved, only *triple* and *quadruple* interaction vertices can arise. For the same reason, vertices cannot involve more than two fermions. In other words, strands *restrict* the possible particle reactions and particle decays.

The allowed interaction vertices allowed by strands are illustrated in Figure 38 and Figure 39. The vertices reproduce the conservation of charge, parity, energy, momentum, and spin. These vertices cover all observed Feynman diagrams of the standard model with massive Dirac neutrinos [261, 262]. No additional vertex arises, and no observed vertex is missing [75]. As an example, strands fully reproduce perturbative QED, including the calculation of the anomalous g -factor of the leptons [129], at all measurable scales. The same occurs for QCD: the quark model and confinement are reproduced [130].

The vertex list in the two figures – including the lack of quintuple vertices – implies that QED, QCD and the theory of the weak interaction are *renormalizable* if they are extrapolated to point-like particles [263]. Because of the minimum length, strands also eliminate the Landau pole. These results are as expected, given that tangles yield a *finite* description of quantum field theory.

In short, because the fundamental principle restricts the rational 3d tangles to those of the observed elementary particles, the topology of these tangles, in turn, restricts the possible interaction vertices to the observed ones. The restrictions reproduce the standard model with massive neutrinos and imply its renormalizability and finiteness.

Test 35: The fundamental principle implies the lack of deviations from quantum field theory and particle physics.

This is observed [75]. Any contrasting observation, in particular any new physics beyond the standard model, would immediately falsify the strand tangle model. **In other words, the standard model of particle physics is elegant and simple: it follows from the fundamental principle.**

33 Strands reproduce the standard model Lagrangian

Even though the Lagrangian of the standard model with massive neutrinos contains numerous terms, tangles allow a rapid first check. Because of the Dirac equation and the allowed elementary rational 3d tangle structures, strand tangles imply *mass terms* for the charged leptons, the neutrinos, and the quarks. Because of the Reidemeister moves, strand tangles imply the *boson terms* of the three gauge interactions. Because of the interaction vertices and the resulting minimal coupling, tangles imply both the *dynamic terms* and the *interaction terms* for all fermions: leptons and quarks. Strand tangles imply, due to the chiral fermion structures, maximal parity violation. Strand tangles imply, due to tether braiding and unbraiding, the Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa mixing matrix for quarks and the Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata mixing matrix for neutrinos. Strands imply, due to the tangle shapes, the Higgs tangle, the Higgs interaction vertices, the Higgs mass, the W mass, the Z mass and all their dynamic terms. As a result, all terms in the Lagrangian of the standard model, including massive mixing Dirac neutrinos [264], arise from rational 3d tangles of strands and thus from Figure 38 and Figure 39. In particular, strands imply

Figure 39: The remaining interaction vertices allowed by fermion and boson tangle topologies imply the full Lagrangian of the standard model and its renormalizability.

that no alternative or modification to the standard model Lagrangian with massive neutrinos is possible. This conclusion agrees with all experimental data [75].

A second, more detailed check that strands reproduce the standard model with massive neutrinos can be performed with the expression for the Lagrangian density that has been collected by Shiflett [265]. The Lagrangian density consists of terms for the gauge fields, of terms for the Higgs boson, and of Dirac terms – dynamic terms and mass terms – for all fermions. The terms are due to the propagators and to the interaction vertices presented so far.

Generally speaking, the Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} of the standard model is a sum of terms for the elementary bosons and for the elementary fermions. Tangles of strands predict this structure because strands imply the principle of least action, thus predicting the existence of a Lagrangian for all elementary particles, and because strands predict the lack of any type of elementary particle that differs from bosons and fermions. The classification of simple rational 3d tangles restricts the spectrum of elementary particles to the observed one. The resulting spectrum is given in Figure 36 and Figure 27. As seen above in the derivation of the Dirac equation and of the Klein-Gordon equation, strands also imply the appearance of dynamic terms and of mass terms for all elementary fermions – also for neutrinos – and for the Higgs boson. The W and Z mass terms arise similarly, because symmetry breaking changes the tangle structure of the weak bosons. The general structure of the Lagrangian density of the standard model is thus predicted and explained by strands. The next task is to check the details.

Shiflett writes the Lagrangian \mathcal{L} of the standard model with massive neutrinos in the following structured manner:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L} = & -\frac{1}{4}B_{\mu\nu}B^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{8}\text{tr}(\mathbf{W}_{\mu\nu}\mathbf{W}^{\mu\nu}) - \frac{1}{2}\text{tr}(\mathbf{G}_{\mu\nu}\mathbf{G}^{\mu\nu}) && \text{(the gauge terms)} \\
& + (\bar{\nu}_L, \bar{e}_L) \tilde{\sigma}^\mu i D_\mu \begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix} + \bar{e}_R \sigma^\mu i D_\mu e_R + \bar{\nu}_R \sigma^\mu i D_\mu \nu_R + \text{h.c.} && \text{(lepton dynamic terms)} \\
& - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{v} \left[(\bar{\nu}_L, \bar{e}_L) \phi M^e e_R + \bar{e}_R \bar{M}^e \bar{\phi} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix} \right] && \text{(electron, muon, tauon mass terms)} \\
& - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{v} \left[(-\bar{e}_L, \bar{\nu}_L) \phi^* M^\nu \nu_R + \bar{\nu}_R \bar{M}^\nu \phi^T \begin{pmatrix} -e_L \\ \nu_L \end{pmatrix} \right] && \text{(neutrino mass terms)} \\
& + (\bar{u}_L, \bar{d}_L) \tilde{\sigma}^\mu i D_\mu \begin{pmatrix} u_L \\ d_L \end{pmatrix} + \bar{u}_R \sigma^\mu i D_\mu u_R + \bar{d}_R \sigma^\mu i D_\mu d_R + \text{h.c.} && \text{(quark dynamic terms)} \\
& - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{v} \left[(\bar{u}_L, \bar{d}_L) \phi M^d d_R + \bar{d}_R \bar{M}^d \bar{\phi} \begin{pmatrix} u_L \\ d_L \end{pmatrix} \right] && \text{(down, strange, bottom mass terms)} \\
& - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{v} \left[(-\bar{d}_L, \bar{u}_L) \phi^* M^u u_R + \bar{u}_R \bar{M}^u \phi^T \begin{pmatrix} -d_L \\ u_L \end{pmatrix} \right] && \text{(up, charmed, top mass terms)} \\
& + \overline{(D_\mu \phi)} D^\mu \phi - m_h^2 [\bar{\phi} \phi - v^2/2]^2 / 2v^2. && \text{(Higgs dynamic and mass terms)}
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

where ‘h.c.’ denotes the Hermitian conjugate of the preceding terms. In particular, ψ h.c. is $\bar{\psi} = \psi^\dagger = \psi^{*T}$. Strands explain the lack of additional lines in the Lagrangian as a consequence of the possible interaction vertices given in Figure 38 and Figure 39. Strands also explain the different treatment of the right- and left-handed fermions as a consequence of their chiral tangle cores together with the strand description of the weak interaction.

In the Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} , the derivative operators D for the left- and right-handed leptons

and quarks, as well as that for the Higgs, are defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
D_\mu \begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix} &= \left[\partial_\mu - \frac{ig_1}{2} B_\mu + \frac{ig_2}{2} \mathbf{W}_\mu \right] \begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix}, \quad D_\mu \nu_R = \partial_\mu \nu_R, \quad D_\mu e_R = [\partial_\mu - ig_1 B_\mu] e_R, \\
D_\mu \begin{pmatrix} u_L \\ d_L \end{pmatrix} &= \left[\partial_\mu + \frac{ig_1}{6} B_\mu + \frac{ig_2}{2} \mathbf{W}_\mu + ig \mathbf{G}_\mu \right] \begin{pmatrix} u_L \\ d_L \end{pmatrix}, \\
D_\mu u_R &= \left[\partial_\mu + \frac{i2g_1}{3} B_\mu + ig \mathbf{G}_\mu \right] u_R, \quad D_\mu d_R = \left[\partial_\mu - \frac{ig_1}{3} B_\mu + ig \mathbf{G}_\mu \right] d_R, \\
D_\mu \phi &= \left[\partial_\mu + \frac{ig_1}{2} B_\mu + \frac{ig_2}{2} \mathbf{W}_\mu \right] \phi.
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

In the last expression, ϕ is a 2-component complex Higgs field. Because the Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} is SU(2) gauge invariant, a gauge can be chosen such that ϕ has the form

$$\phi^T = (0, v + h)/\sqrt{2}, \quad \langle \phi \rangle_0^T = (\text{expectation value of } \phi) = (0, v)/\sqrt{2}, \tag{39}$$

where v is a real fundamental constant such that $\mathcal{L}_\phi = (\overline{\partial_\mu \phi}) \partial^\mu \phi - m_h^2 [\bar{\phi} \phi - v^2/2]^2 / 2v^2$ is minimized, and where h is the residual Higgs field that is observed. The mentioned expectation value is a fundamental constant of nature that must be explained with strands.

The (residual) Higgs boson tangle of Figure 36, with its braid structure, visualizes that particle masses arise from strand braiding and implies the interaction of the Higgs with itself shown in Figure 39. The Higgs boson tangle also visualizes that the number of generations is limited to three [129, 130]. The strand origin of the fundamental constants of nature will be explained in the next section.

In the Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} , the fields B_μ , \mathbf{W}_μ and \mathbf{G}_μ are the gauge boson vector potentials for electromagnetic, weak and strong interactions. As shown in references [125, 127, 128], Reidemeister's theorem implies that strands do not allow additional gauge interactions or additional gauge bosons. As shown in Section 29, the Reidemeister moves for strands imply that the weak fields \mathbf{W}_μ and the strong fields \mathbf{G}_μ are composed of 2×2 and 3×3 traceless Hermitian matrices, whereas the electromagnetic field B_μ is not a matrix. The associated field tensors are

$$\begin{aligned}
B_{\mu\nu} &= \partial_\mu B_\nu - \partial_\nu B_\mu, \\
\mathbf{W}_{\mu\nu} &= \partial_\mu \mathbf{W}_\nu - \partial_\nu \mathbf{W}_\mu + ig_2 (\mathbf{W}_\mu \mathbf{W}_\nu - \mathbf{W}_\nu \mathbf{W}_\mu) / 2, \\
\mathbf{G}_{\mu\nu} &= \partial_\mu \mathbf{G}_\nu - \partial_\nu \mathbf{G}_\mu + ig (\mathbf{G}_\mu \mathbf{G}_\nu - \mathbf{G}_\nu \mathbf{G}_\mu).
\end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

The self-interaction of the weak and strong bosons – and the lack of such effects for photons – is explained by strands.

Because of SU(2) breaking – which is also explained and described by strands – the real boson fields A_μ , Z_μ and W_μ^\pm are mixtures of \mathbf{W}_μ and B_μ components described by the weak mixing angle θ_w , a further fundamental constant of nature. The boson fields are related by

$$\begin{aligned}
A_\mu &= W_{11\mu} \sin \theta_w + B_\mu \cos \theta_w, \quad Z_\mu = W_{11\mu} \cos \theta_w - B_\mu \sin \theta_w, \quad W_\mu^+ = W_\mu^{-*} = W_{12\mu} / \sqrt{2}, \\
B_\mu &= A_\mu \cos \theta_w - Z_\mu \sin \theta_w, \quad W_{11\mu} = -W_{22\mu} = A_\mu \sin \theta_w + Z_\mu \cos \theta_w, \\
W_{12\mu} &= W_{21\mu}^* = \sqrt{2} W_\mu^+, \quad \sin^2 \theta_w = 0.2315(4).
\end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

The value of the weak mixing angle is a fundamental constant that strands need to explain.

Strand tangle chirality implies that fermions of different handedness behave differently and must be distinguished. In the Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} , the fermion fields consist of right- and

left-handed leptons e_R, e_L, ν_R, ν_L and quarks u_R, u_L, d_R, d_L . All fermion fields have implicit 3-component generation indices, $e_i = (e, \mu, \tau)$, $\nu_i = (\nu_e, \nu_\mu, \nu_\tau)$, $u_i = (u, c, t)$, $d_i = (d, s, b)$ that ‘contract’ into the fermion mass matrices $M_{ij}^e, M_{ij}^\nu, M_{ij}^u$ and M_{ij}^d . As told above, the three generations of leptons are explained with the classification of the elementary tangles [127–130]. As also told above, fermion behaviour is explained by Dirac’s trick. Therefore, all fermion fields in the Lagrangian density also have implicit 2-component indices which ‘contract’ into the Pauli matrices

$$\sigma^\mu = \left[\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \right], \quad \text{with}$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}^\mu = [\sigma^0, -\sigma^1, -\sigma^2, -\sigma^3], \quad \text{tr}(\sigma^i) = 0, \quad \sigma^{\mu\dagger} = \sigma^\mu, \quad \text{tr}(\sigma^\mu \sigma^\nu) = 2\delta^{\mu\nu}. \quad (42)$$

Strands also explain colour charge with the geometry of the quark tangles, as told in reference [130]. Therefore, the quark fields also have implicit 3-component colour charge indices that contract into \mathbf{G}_μ .

As a result, the Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} contains implicit sums over 3-component generation indices, 2-component Pauli indices, 3-component colour charge indices in the quark terms and 2-component SU(2) indices in $(\bar{\nu}_L, \bar{e}_L)$, (\bar{u}_L, \bar{d}_L) , $(-\bar{e}_L, \bar{\nu}_L)$, $(-\bar{d}_L, \bar{u}_L)$, $\bar{\phi}$, \mathbf{W}_μ , $\begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix}$, $\begin{pmatrix} u_L \\ d_L \end{pmatrix}$, $\begin{pmatrix} -e_L \\ \nu_L \end{pmatrix}$, $\begin{pmatrix} -d_L \\ u_L \end{pmatrix}$ and ϕ . The electroweak and strong coupling constants, the Higgs vacuum expectation value, and the Higgs mass are related and measured to be

$$g_1 = e/\cos\theta_w, \quad g_2 = e/\sin\theta_w, \quad g > 6.5e = g(m_\tau^2),$$

$$v = 246 \text{ GeV} \approx \sqrt{2} 180 \text{ GeV}, \quad m_h = 125.02(30) \text{ GeV}, \quad (43)$$

where the electromagnetic coupling constant (at low energy) has the value $e = \sqrt{4\pi\alpha\hbar c} = \sqrt{4\pi/137.036(1)}$ in natural units. All the observed values of the fundamental constants need to be explained with strands.

For the observed bosons A_μ, Z_μ and W_μ^\pm that arise after symmetry breaking, using equations (38) and (39) and rewriting the terms, one gets the following expressions and relations:

$$-\frac{1}{4}B_{\mu\nu}B^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{8}\text{tr}(\mathbf{W}_{\mu\nu}\mathbf{W}^{\mu\nu}) = -\frac{1}{4}A_{\mu\nu}A^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{4}Z_{\mu\nu}Z^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^-\mathcal{W}^{+\mu\nu} + \dots,$$

$$A_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu, \quad Z_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu Z_\nu - \partial_\nu Z_\mu,$$

$$\mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^\pm = D_\mu W_\nu^\pm - D_\nu W_\mu^\pm, \quad D_\mu W_\nu^\pm = [\partial_\mu \pm ieA_\mu] W_\nu^\pm$$

$$D_\mu \langle \phi \rangle_0 = \frac{iv}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} g_2 W_{12\mu}/2 \\ g_1 B_\mu/2 + g_2 W_{22\mu}/2 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{ig_2 v}{2} \begin{pmatrix} W_{12\mu}/\sqrt{2} \\ (B_\mu \sin\theta_w/\cos\theta_w + W_{22\mu})/\sqrt{2} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \frac{ig_2 v}{2} \begin{pmatrix} W_\mu^+ \\ -Z_\mu/\sqrt{2} \cos\theta_w \end{pmatrix}. \quad (44)$$

The observed mass values are

$$m_A = 0, \quad m_{W^\pm} = g_2 \frac{v}{2} = 80.425(38) \text{ GeV}, \quad m_Z = g_2 \frac{v}{2} \cos\theta_w = 91.1876(21) \text{ GeV} \quad (45)$$

and also these fundamental constants require an explanation with strands.

For the observed fermions, the ordinary 4-component Dirac fields are composed of the left-

and right-handed 2-component fields of each fermion generation,

$$\begin{aligned}
e &= \begin{pmatrix} e_{L1} \\ e_{R1} \end{pmatrix}, \nu_e = \begin{pmatrix} \nu_{L1} \\ \nu_{R1} \end{pmatrix}, u = \begin{pmatrix} u_{L1} \\ u_{R1} \end{pmatrix}, d = \begin{pmatrix} d_{L1} \\ d_{R1} \end{pmatrix}, & \text{(first generation)} \\
\mu &= \begin{pmatrix} e_{L2} \\ e_{R2} \end{pmatrix}, \nu_\mu = \begin{pmatrix} \nu_{L2} \\ \nu_{R2} \end{pmatrix}, c = \begin{pmatrix} u_{L2} \\ u_{R2} \end{pmatrix}, s = \begin{pmatrix} d_{L2} \\ d_{R2} \end{pmatrix}, & \text{(second generation)} \\
\tau &= \begin{pmatrix} e_{L3} \\ e_{R3} \end{pmatrix}, \nu_\tau = \begin{pmatrix} \nu_{L3} \\ \nu_{R3} \end{pmatrix}, t = \begin{pmatrix} u_{L3} \\ u_{R3} \end{pmatrix}, b = \begin{pmatrix} d_{L3} \\ d_{R3} \end{pmatrix}, & \text{(third generation)} \\
\gamma^\mu &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma^\mu \\ \tilde{\sigma}^\mu & 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ where } \gamma^\mu \gamma^\nu + \gamma^\nu \gamma^\mu = 2I g^{\mu\nu}. & \text{(Dirac gamma matrices)} \quad (46)
\end{aligned}$$

The corresponding antiparticles are related to the particles according to $\psi^c = -i\gamma^2\psi^*$ or $\psi_L^c = -i\sigma^2\psi_R^*$, $\psi_R^c = i\sigma^2\psi_L^*$. Strands explain the relation by defining antiparticles as mirror particles rotating in the opposite direction. The fermion charges are the coefficients of A_μ when (41) and (43) are substituted into either the left- or right-handed derivative operators (38). The fermion masses are the singular values of the 3×3 fermion mass matrices M^ν, M^e, M^u, M^d

$$\begin{aligned}
M^e &= \mathbf{U}_L^{e\dagger} \begin{pmatrix} m_e & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_\mu & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m_\tau \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}_R^e, & M^\nu &= \mathbf{U}_L^{\nu\dagger} \begin{pmatrix} m_{\nu_e} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_{\nu_\mu} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m_{\nu_\tau} \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}_R^\nu, \\
M^u &= \mathbf{U}_L^{u\dagger} \begin{pmatrix} m_u & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_c & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m_t \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}_R^u, & M^d &= \mathbf{U}_L^{d\dagger} \begin{pmatrix} m_d & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m_b \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}_R^d, \quad \text{where}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
m_e &= 0.510998910(13) \text{ MeV}, 1 \text{ meV} < m_{\nu_e} < 2 \text{ eV}, m_u = 2.4(7) \text{ MeV}, m_d = 4.9(8) \text{ MeV}, \\
m_\mu &= 105.658367(4) \text{ MeV}, 1 \text{ meV} < m_{\nu_\mu} < 2 \text{ eV}, m_c = 1.26(8) \text{ GeV}, m_s = 105(25) \text{ MeV}, \\
m_\tau &= 1776.84(17) \text{ MeV}, 1 \text{ meV} < m_{\nu_\tau} < 2 \text{ eV}, m_t = 172.9(1.5) \text{ GeV}, m_b = 4.25(12) \text{ GeV}.
\end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

where the \mathbf{U} s are 3×3 unitary matrices, thus obeying $\mathbf{U}^{-1} = \mathbf{U}^\dagger$. Consequently the “true fermions” with the observed masses are actually linear combinations of the fermions appearing in \mathcal{L} , or conversely the fermions in \mathcal{L} are linear combinations of the true fermions:

$$\begin{aligned}
e'_L &= \mathbf{U}_L^e e_L, e'_R = \mathbf{U}_R^e e_R, \nu'_L = \mathbf{U}_L^\nu \nu_L, \nu'_R = \mathbf{U}_R^\nu \nu_R, \\
u'_L &= \mathbf{U}_L^u u_L, u'_R = \mathbf{U}_R^u u_R, d'_L = \mathbf{U}_L^d d_L, d'_R = \mathbf{U}_R^d d_R \quad \text{or equivalently,} \\
e_L &= \mathbf{U}_L^{e\dagger} e'_L, e_R = \mathbf{U}_R^{e\dagger} e'_R, \nu_L = \mathbf{U}_L^{\nu\dagger} \nu'_L, \nu_R = \mathbf{U}_R^{\nu\dagger} \nu'_R, \\
u_L &= \mathbf{U}_L^{u\dagger} u'_L, u_R = \mathbf{U}_R^{u\dagger} u'_R, d_L = \mathbf{U}_L^{d\dagger} d'_L, d_R = \mathbf{U}_R^{d\dagger} d'_R.
\end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

When the Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} is written in terms of the true fermions, the \mathbf{U} s disappear, except in the terms $\bar{u}'_L \mathbf{U}_L^u \tilde{\sigma}^\mu W_\mu^\pm \mathbf{U}_L^{d\dagger} d'_L$ and in $\bar{\nu}'_L \mathbf{U}_L^\nu \tilde{\sigma}^\mu W_\mu^\pm \mathbf{U}_L^{e\dagger} e'_L$. Because of this and because of some constants absorbed into the fermion fields, all the parameters in the \mathbf{U} s are contained in just four components of the Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa mixing matrix $\mathbf{V}^q = \mathbf{U}_L^u \mathbf{U}_L^{d\dagger}$ and in four components of the Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata mixing matrix $\mathbf{V}^l = \mathbf{U}_L^\nu \mathbf{U}_L^{e\dagger}$. In the strand tangle model, fermion mixing is due to tether braiding and thus due to the weak interaction. The braiding also implies that leptons mix only among themselves and so do quarks. As the boson tangles show, braiding does not mix bosons beyond the well-known electroweak effects.

The resulting unitary mixing matrices \mathbf{V}^q and \mathbf{V}^l are often parametrized as

$$\mathbf{V} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{23} & s_{23} \\ 0 & -s_{23} & c_{23} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\frac{\delta}{2}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{i\frac{\delta}{2}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{13} & 0 & s_{13} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_{13} & 0 & c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\frac{\delta}{2}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{i\frac{\delta}{2}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{12} & s_{12} & 0 \\ -s_{12} & c_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

with $c_{jk} = \sqrt{1 - s_{jk}^2}$. (49)

The fundamental constants describing quark mixing and lepton – by convention, neutrino – mixing are measured to be

$$\begin{aligned} \delta^q &= 69(4)^\circ, & s_{12}^q &= 0.2253(7), & s_{23}^q &= 0.041(1), & s_{13}^q &= 0.0035(2), \\ \delta^l &= \text{yet unknown}, & s_{12}^l &= 0.560(16), & s_{23}^l &= 0.7(1), & s_{13}^l &= 0.153(28) \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

and their values need to be explained with strands.

The Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} of the standard model with massive neutrinos is invariant under an electroweak $U(1) \otimes SU(2)$ gauge transformation with $U^{-1} = U^\dagger$, $\det U = 1$ and θ a real function. The gauge transformation behaviour is the following:

$$\begin{aligned} B_\mu &\rightarrow B_\mu + (2/g_1) \partial_\mu \theta, & B_{\mu\nu} &\rightarrow B_{\mu\nu} \\ \mathbf{W}_\mu &\rightarrow U \mathbf{W}_\mu U^\dagger - (2i/g_2) U \partial_\mu U^\dagger, & \mathbf{W}_{\mu\nu} &\rightarrow U \mathbf{W}_{\mu\nu} U^\dagger, \\ \phi &\rightarrow e^{-i\theta} U \phi, \\ \begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix} &\rightarrow e^{i\theta} U \begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix}, & \begin{pmatrix} u_L \\ d_L \end{pmatrix} &\rightarrow e^{-i\theta/3} U \begin{pmatrix} u_L \\ d_L \end{pmatrix}, & \nu_R &\rightarrow \nu_R, & u_R &\rightarrow e^{-4i\theta/3} u_R, \\ & & & & e_R &\rightarrow e^{2i\theta} e_R, & d_R &\rightarrow e^{2i\theta/3} d_R. \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

As argued in references [125, 127, 128], strands reproduce electroweak gauge invariance and explain that electroweak effects act on all fermions.

The Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} is also invariant under $SU(3)$ gauge transformations of the strong interaction. These transformations are described by special unitary matrices V , thus obeying $V^{-1} = V^\dagger$ and $\det V = 1$. The fields transform in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G}_\mu &\rightarrow V \mathbf{G}_\mu V^\dagger - (i/g) V \partial_\mu V^\dagger, & \mathbf{G}_{\mu\nu} &\rightarrow V \mathbf{G}_{\mu\nu} V^\dagger, \\ u_L &\rightarrow V u_L, & d_L &\rightarrow V d_L, & u_R &\rightarrow V u_R, & d_R &\rightarrow V d_R. \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

All other fields remain unchanged. As explained above and shown in references [125, 127, 128], strands reproduce the $SU(3)$ invariance and imply that the strong interaction, which is due to the third Reidemeister move, only acts on quarks.

In short, every term in the Lagrangian density (37) of the standard model with massive neutrinos is reproduced by the strand tangle model. Every term is due to the fundamental principle. Also the algebraic behaviour of each term is reproduced by strands. As mentioned already, any observation disagreeing with the Lagrangian density (37) would immediately falsify the strand tangle model. Only one set of questions remains.

34 The fundamental constants and their properties

Particle physics is characterized by three sets of dimensionless *fundamental constants*: the ratios between the elementary particle masses and (half) the Planck mass, the gauge coupling constants,

Outer chiral crossing switches *couple* to photons

Figure 40: The coupling of crossing switches to photons determines the fine-structure constant. The angles in the graph were used in reference [129] to deduce an estimate of its value.

and the mixing angles and CP phases. Among their numerous effects, these fundamental constants determine all colours and all shapes in nature. Any *unified* description of motion must allow the calculation of the fundamental constants, including their running, i.e., their dependence on four-momentum.

In the strand tangle model, the fundamental constants are determined by the average *tangle core shapes*. Given that the core shapes are determined by the tangle structure, strands fix the fundamental constants are *uniquely*. The fundamental constants cannot be varied or tuned in any way.

Given that the tangle shapes change due to special relativity, the *running* of the fundamental constants with four-momentum is also determined and fixed uniquely. The running due to *shape* change contrasts with those particle properties that are due to the *topology* of the tangles, such as quantum numbers, which do not run. This contrast agrees with observations.

In short, strands imply the *uniqueness* of the fundamental constants, i.e., the uniqueness of the coupling constants, of the mixing matrices, and of the elementary particle masses.

Test 36: Strands thus reject ‘fine tuning’, ‘multiple vacua’, and the ‘multiverse’.

Any contradicting observation would immediately falsify the strand tangle model. Strands also predict that only the fundamental constants run with four momentum and that they do so in a unique way – as expected and as observed. The predicted uniqueness of the fundamental constants and of their running allows numerical estimates and allows testing the strand model.

35 Calculating the coupling constants

As Feynman wrote [175], the electromagnetic coupling constant, the well-known fine-structure constant α , is the squared probability that a unit charge emits or absorbs a photon. This probability can be estimated with the strand tangle model.

The strand description of the electromagnetic interaction is given in Figure 30; its principle was illustrated in Figure 26 and is repeated, with more detail, in Figure 40. A particle with unit electric charge, such as an electron, has a topologically chiral tangle core with three chiral outer crossings. The probability of photon absorption by the electron depends on the average shape of the outer crossings. Each chiral outer crossing yields a probability of absorbing a photon. Not all incoming photons are absorbed; those that arrive at the core *between* the outer chiral crossings are not absorbed. The fine-structure constant is thus automatically smaller than 1, as observed.

Figure 40 yields a simple but rough approximation for the electromagnetic coupling. In an electron, the tethers of each outer crossing, on average, at a right angle $\delta = \pi/2$. A chiral outer tether pair will only absorb photons arriving in the cone spanned by the two tethers. A cone with full opening angle $\pi/2$ has a solid angle given by $\Omega = 4\pi \sin^2 \pi/8$. This is a fraction $(2 - \sqrt{2})/4$ of the full solid angle 4π . An electron tangle has 3 such cones. Each of the three cones is expected to absorb only 1/2 of the arriving photons, namely those of the correct helicity. If a photon arrives inside the cone, but at its very border, it is expected to be absorbed only rarely. The average over all incoming photon angles β and γ is expected to lead to a further approximate factor 1/2. A charged lepton will thus absorb a fraction

$$(3/4)(2 - \sqrt{2})/4 \approx 0.11 \quad (53)$$

of all incoming photons. In comparison, the square root of the fine-structure constant is

$$1/\sqrt{\alpha_{\text{exp}}} \approx 0.0854(1) \quad (54)$$

The simple cone approximation thus yields a value for $1/\sqrt{\alpha}$ that is too large by a factor of 1.3, leading to an estimate $\alpha \approx 1/81$, overestimating the fine-structure constant by a factor of about 1.7.

Using a more precise averaging over the possible shapes of the electron tangle of Figure 40, reference [129] deduced an estimate for the fine-structure constant given by

$$\alpha_{\text{strands}} = 1/126 \pm 30\% \quad (55)$$

The error might have been overestimated. The value is compatible with the experimental value

$$\alpha_{\text{exp}} = 1/137.035999(1) \quad (56)$$

Improved calculations of α are in progress.

Strands also reproduce the running of the fine-structure constant with four-momentum. At Planck energy, the value for the standard model is about 1/100, yielding a value 0.1 for its square root, when deduced from reference [266]. At Planck energy, the tangle of a charged lepton is flat. A flat structure implies that the three chiral tether pairs cover 1/2 of the full angle 2π . Dividing by 4, because of the two helicities and because of the angular averaging, yields the estimate 0.125 for $1/\sqrt{\alpha_{\text{Pl}}}$ at Planck energy. Again, the estimate is acceptable. Strands thus reproduce the observed, rather moderate increase of the fine-structure constant with energy. Improved calculations are in progress.

The strand description of the strong interaction in Figure 30 also provides a rough estimate of the strong coupling constant. Using the shape of gluons and the topology of quark tangles, reference [130] deduced an estimate for the strong coupling constant at Planck energy correct to within 15%. Like for electrodynamics, a geometrical average over all possible gluon-quark interactions was used. Also the running of the strong coupling constant, including the phenomenon of asymptotic freedom, is reproduced by strands. At very high energy, the flattened shapes of quark tangles no longer interact. At low energy, quark tangles remain topologically interlocked and lead to an interaction potential that increases linearly with distance, as observed [130].

This relation between tangle shapes and the coupling constants yields a prediction.

Test 37: Because of the lack of grand unification, supersymmetry, and new energy scales, the three running couplings *do not need to converge to a common value at any energy*.

Such a lack of convergence is indeed observed [266].

In short, the strand tangle model allows estimating the coupling constants from the fundamental principle, using the core shape of the particle tangles. These estimates might well be the first ab initio estimates. The running of the coupling constants is reproduced [qualitatively](#).

Test 38: Strands *predict* that the calculated coupling constants and their running agree with measurements.

Any disagreement would immediately falsify the strand tangle model. [This prediction should be tested in detail in the future.](#)

36 Properties of particle mixing and CP violation

In the strand tangle model, braiding or unbraiding tethers involves *pairs* of strands. Therefore, both processes are effects of the weak interaction. At the same time, the braiding and unbraiding of tethers change the type of particle, i.e., the particle flavour. In contrast, in the strand tangle model, the electromagnetic and the strong interaction cannot do so.

Test 39: Strands imply that only the weak interaction can change particle flavour.

Strands thus explain the appearance of particle mixing, which was discovered by Cabibbo [267] and reproduce the observation that only the weak interaction can change quark flavours or neutrino flavours [127]. All this is as observed [75].

In the strand tangle model, because of the chirality of the fermion tangle cores, the SU(2) group of spin and the SU(2) of the weak interaction disturb each other. As a result, strands predict a non-vanishing CP phase for the weak interaction, as is observed [75]. So far, no estimate has been deduced from the chirality of tangle core shapes. Estimating the Jarlskog invariant with strands remains an open challenge; ideas such as those of Luo and Xing [268] might be useful.

No disturbance of the SU(2) spin group and the gauge group is possible for the electromagnetic and strong interactions. In particular, because no such disturbance is possible for SU(3), the strand model for quantum chromodynamics implies

Test 40: Strands exclude CP violation in the strong interaction.

Indeed, no such CP violation is observed [75]. Strands thus solve the strong CP problem [130].

In nature, particle mixing is described by the Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) mixing matrix for quarks and by the Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata (PMNS) mixing matrix for neutrinos. Each mixing matrix is due to three *mixing angles* and one *CP phase*. Strands imply that all eight values derive from tangle core shapes. A look at the topology and geometry of fermion tangles in Figure 27 shows that the required braiding to get from one generation to the next differs for leptons and for quarks. The braiding is easiest among neutrinos; therefore, large mixing angles are expected. The braiding for quarks gets more difficult with increasing mass; therefore, the mixing angles for quarks should be smaller than for neutrinos and should decrease with mass. All this is observed.

Strands imply that fermion mixing is due to tether braiding. This leads to

Test 41: Strands imply the unitarity of the mixing matrices.

Strands thus also imply weak universality. For quarks, strands also imply that the diagonal elements of the mixing matrix, thus among quarks of the same generation, have the largest magnitude. Because of the braiding, strands further imply that the elements of the mixing matrix between the first and third generation of quarks have the smallest magnitude. All these conclusions agree with observations [75]. Numerical estimates of the mixing angles are a topic of research. Also the symmetry of the normed mixing matrix elements requires explanation.

The strand model implies that the mixing angles depend on the average shape of tangles. The shapes change with four-momentum. This yields

Test 42: Strands imply that the mixing angles *run* with four-momentum and *predict* that the calculations will agree with observations.

The running is observed [75]. Numerical estimates of the running from the strand tangle model are the subject of research.

No other ab initio explanation of mixing or its running that agrees with observations is found in the literature. Attempts based on additional symmetries or additional dimensions [269] have not been successful.

In short, strands *predict* that tangle core shapes describe quark mixing and neutrino mixing with complete precision, including their running with energy. Precision estimates require numerical simulations of strand tangle fluctuations. It might also be possible to deduce estimates of the elements of the mixing matrices without any simulations. Any disagreement with observations would immediately falsify the strand tangle model.

37 Properties of particle mass values

According to experiment and to quantum theory, when a particle advances, its quantum phase rotates. According to the strand tangle model, a chiral particle core moves through the vacuum like a maple seed moves through the air.

▷ The inertial mass m describes the coupling between translation and phase rotation.

A *larger* mass value implies a *faster* rotation, and a *shorter* wavelength.

In the strand model, when a fermion tangle moves through the vacuum, the frequency of the core rotation and of Dirac's trick determine the mass value of the particle. The mass value is thus due to the topology and to the average chirality of the tangle core. The *chirality* is a quantity describing the "maple seed effectiveness" of the shape of the tangle core.

Test 43: Because mass is due to the core shape, strands deduce that the mass values of all elementary particles (at low energy) are *positive, fixed, unique* and *constant* in time and space, across the universe.

Test 44: Strands predict that mass values for particles and antiparticles, i.e., for tangles and mirror tangles, are *equal*.

These qualitative consequences agree with observations [75].

Whenever a chiral body moves through air or through a fluid, it starts to rotate. For example, this occurs when a chiral pebble falls through water or a maple seed falls through the air. The rotation is due to the chiral shape of the body [270–273]. Also a tethered chiral body – such as a tethered maple seed, a tethered propeller, or a tethered spinning top – moving with a low Reynolds number through a fluid will rotate, as long as the tethers are elastic and their motion is not disturbed. The motion of a tethered particle through the vacuum is similar, though it takes place without friction.

In the strand tangle model, translation and phase rotation for particles with spin are modelled by the translation and rotation of the tangle core. Indeed, strands imply that chiral tangle cores rotate when they move through the vacuum. Except for the Higgs, all tangle cores of the elementary particles are chiral. As a note, in the strand tangle model, chirality also applies to the d quark, once the coupling to the Higgs is taken into account. As a second note, a different process applies to the motion of the Higgs boson itself, as explored below, because the Higgs boson is not chiral. The combination of chirality and tethers yields the coupling between translation and rotation. Figure 2 gives an impression of how core translation and rotation are coupled. Thus, the strand tangle model implies

- Test 45:** Tethered, non-trivial, topologically chiral, rational 3d tangle cores – thus localized cores composed of two, three, or more strands – are predicted to be *massive particles*. A tangle is *localized* or *localizable* – or simply *non-trivial* – if the core collapses to a tight tangle when the tethers are imagined to be inelastic ropes that are ‘pulled outwards’.
- Test 46:** The mass value for tangles made of a few strands is *not arbitrary* but is *uniquely determined* by the tangle structure and by the resulting average core *shape*. Elementary particle masses are thus *calculable* from the tangle topology
- Test 47:** The *more complex* the tangle core – for the same number of tethers – the slower the translation per rotation and thus the *larger* the predicted mass value. By comparing the topological complexity of tangles with the same number of tethers, the strand tangle model yields the correct mass sequences for elementary particles and for all mesons and baryons, as explored elsewhere [130]
- Test 48:** A small mass for at least two neutrinos arises. The strand tangle model predicts normal mass ordering for neutrinos [127, 128].
- Test 49:** *Unlocalized*, or *trivial* tangles – which disappear if their ends are pulled outwards – are predicted to be massless, even if they are geometrically chiral. This is the case for photons, gluons and gravitons.
- Test 50:** Only localizable, non-trivial tangles have *inertial* mass. Strands predict that only *localizable* tangles interact with the Higgs field and thus have Yukawa couplings. In particular, in the strand tangle model, only fermions, W, Z, and the Higgs boson have positive mass.
- Test 51:** Because fermion masses are due to the frequency of Dirac’s trick, massive fermions are surrounded by a cloud of virtual gravitons. The gravitons are the two-stranded twists arising in their tethers, as illustrated in Figure 2. Virtual gravitons have spin 2 and vanishing mass. Therefore, they induce a $1/r^2$ dependency of gravity in flat space. Only localizable, non-trivial tangles have *gravitational* mass.

The predictions about particle masses deduced from the fermion tangles of Figure 27 and from the boson tangles of Figure 36 agree with observations [75].

The strand tangle model also allows the comparison of the *inertial* and the *gravitational* mass values. On the one hand, the chiral core shape and Dirac’s trick generate a displacement and thus relate rotation and displacement. This relation, illustrated in Figure 2, defines the *inertial* mass. On the other hand, the tether twists generated by Dirac’s trick correspond to virtual gravitons. Thus, Dirac’s trick also defines and generates *gravitational* mass.

- Test 52:** Strands predict that the inertial and the gravitational masses of every particle are due to the same processes and thus are intrinsically *equal*, at all times, places, and energies.

The prediction agrees with all observations. The prediction is of interest because it contradicts certain versions of modified Newtonian dynamics (MOND) suggesting a difference between the two mass values, for the masses of stars or galaxies [274, 275].

In the strand tangle model, the highest possible energy value for an elementary particle, the corrected Planck energy, is one crossing switch per corrected Planck time. Dirac’s trick for a moving tangle core is much less probable.

- Test 53:** The complex tether motion required for Dirac’s trick implies a low probability for the involved strand deformations. Strands therefore predict that the mass m_{el} of *elementary* particles is *much smaller* than the corrected Planck mass:

$$m_{el} \ll \sqrt{\hbar c/4G} = 6.1 \cdot 10^{27} \text{ eV}/c^2 . \quad (57)$$

Thus, the strand tangle model solves the *mass hierarchy problem* [276]. In addition, this yields

Test 54: The product of the Lorentz factor γ and the elementary particle mass m_{el} obeys

$$\gamma m_{\text{el}} \ll \sqrt{\hbar c / 4G} = 6.1 \cdot 10^{27} \text{ eV}/c^2 . \quad (58)$$

Both inequalities agree with observations, such as those of high-energy cosmic rays [82].

In short, the strand tangle model explains the origin of particle mass values as a consequence of the chiral shape of their tangle cores and solves the mass hierarchy problem. Above all, the chiral motion and the precession of the tethered core, with the Dirac trick occurring during the motion of particles through the vacuum, promise to allow estimating mass values.

38 Calculating particle masses

As Feynman explains, a fermion advances through the vacuum like a chiral maple seed falls through the air. Both rotate when they advance. Even though quantum field theory does not explain particle mass values, strands do.

When a fermion tangle moves through the vacuum, the frequency of the core rotation and of Dirac's trick determines the mass value of the particle. As just shown, the low probability per time of Dirac's trick when a tangle advances through the vacuum is the reason that elementary particle masses indeed are much smaller than (half) the Planck mass. Figure 7 illustrates that, during Dirac's trick, the six lepton tethers must go through a specific sequence of intermediate steps. For each of the two core rotations, at least three intermediate steps are needed. Dirac's trick is thus defined by at least $2 \cdot 3$ intermediate steps. To reproduce Dirac's trick, the intermediate steps have to occur in the correct sequence. In each of the intermediate steps, every tether must have the correct configuration in space and none of the $6! - 1$ possible alternatives. The probability per time of Dirac's trick for a lepton is thus about

$$m_{\text{lepton-strands}} < \left(\frac{1}{6!} \right)^{2 \cdot 3} \approx 7.2 \times 10^{-18} \approx 44 \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (59)$$

The last expression used, for the mass unit, the maximum possible elementary particle mass $\sqrt{\hbar c / 4G} = 0.61 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ GeV}/c^2$, or half the Planck mass. Because the time needed for the core rotation was neglected, this lepton mass estimate is an *upper limit*. Nevertheless, expression (59) is one of the first ab initio estimates of a particle mass. The *measured* mass value of the most massive lepton, the tau, is

$$m_{\tau} = 1.78(1) \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (60)$$

The upper lepton limit suggested by strands is thus about 25 times larger than the tau mass. The tau mass does not saturate the mass limit because the tau core itself also needs to be set into rotational motion, to trigger Dirac's trick. This requirement further reduces the probability per time for rotation and leads to a mass value for the tau that is smaller than the lepton mass limit.

The muon and the electron tangles are not as complex as the tau tangle. Therefore, they are less chiral; when they propagate through the vacuum, they rotate less frequently and thus their mass values are lower. The muon and electron masses are thus limited both by the Dirac trick *and* by the lower chirality of their cores. Estimating the mass values of the leptons is not straightforward and is a subject of research. Any disagreement between future lepton mass calculations and the observed lepton mass values will immediately falsify the strand tangle model.

The lepton tangles imply a straightforward prediction about their masses.

Test 55: The neutrino tangle assignments explain their extremely small mass values. For the electron neutrino, the simplest tangle is similar to a vacuum configuration and has a low chirality. Strands predict that the electron neutrino mass arises almost only through the Higgs mechanism – without any see-saw mechanism – and thus is the smallest of all elementary particles.

Test 56: In other words, strands imply and predict

$$m_{\nu_e} < m_{\nu_\mu} < m_{\nu_\tau} \ll m_e < m_\mu < m_\tau . \quad (61)$$

Test 57: Strands predict that neutrino masses can be calculated before they are measured.

The normal order of neutrino masses might soon be testable in experiments [75].

Strands also allow statements about quark and hadron masses. The prediction that more complex tangles have larger mass values (for the same number of tethers) is valid for all hadrons with the same number of tethers, as shown in references [127, 128, 130]. Strands also imply that quarks do not arise as free particles, because their four tethers do not blend into the vacuum strands, due to their tetrahedral arrangement. Therefore, quark masses are more complex to define and to determine from strands. This will be explored in a separate article. Strands also explain the unexpected value of the d quark mass. Because of its tangle symmetry, the d quark has more ways to rotate than the u quark, and thus is more massive than the u quark, despite being less complex. The argument does not work for the other generations.

Strands also yield an estimate for the mass of the Higgs boson. The tangle of the Higgs boson is a linear three-stranded braid with six crossings. The Higgs braid, shown in Figure 36, explains the vanishing spin, the vanishing electric charge, and the positive C and P parities. The Higgs braid also yields the Higgs mechanism that gives mass to the weak bosons: the W and Z boson masses arise by braiding a vacuum strand into the unbroken weak boson tangles. As mentioned above, a particle with spin advances through the vacuum by rotating. In contrast, a spin 0 particle such as the Higgs particle does not rotate. In the strand tangle model, when the Higgs tangle of Figure 36 moves to the right, the last crossing on the left end of its core is undone, and a new crossing between the same two strands is added to the right of the core. This process also occurs for the two other strand pairs. Then the three steps are repeated. In this way, a Higgs braid moves through the vacuum.

The probability per time of the steps of the Higgs motion determines the value of the Higgs mass. For a tether to move around another in a set of three, three small displacements are needed. In each displacement, the moving tether can move forward to the next position, move backwards, or move away in three directions. Only one displacement is correct. Each tether pair exchange thus has an estimated probability of $1/5^3 = 1/125$. To get the full cycle of six exchanges of the correct tether pairs, the probability per time is

$$m_{\text{Higgs-strands}} \approx \frac{1}{(6 \times 125)^6} \approx 5.6 \times 10^{-18} . \quad (62)$$

The probability $1/125$ is an estimate with at least 30% uncertainty. Using again the maximum elementary particle mass as the mass unit, the Higgs mass estimate becomes

$$7 \text{ GeV}/c^2 < m_{\text{Higgs-strands}} < 287 \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (63)$$

The mass range includes the measured value

$$m_{\text{Higgs}} = 125(1) \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (64)$$

The estimate of the Higgs mass is not precise, but it is *ab initio*. As such, the estimate contrasts with many Higgs mass predictions from the past [277], which were more precise but were all based on data. An *ab initio* estimate with higher precision will probably require a computer simulation.

Strands also allow estimating the W boson mass and comparing it to the measured mass value

$$m_W = 80.4(1) \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (65)$$

The W boson tangle, shown in Figure 36, has spin 1 because it can return to itself after the core rotates by 2π . The W core rotation resembles that of photon core made of three strands. When the W boson tangle in Figure 36 advances towards the reader, the encountered vacuum strands rotate the core around the line of sight. In such a W core rotation, each of the three crossings must move to the position and orientation of the next crossing. Each crossing can move, for each of the three coordinates, towards the correct next position or towards the wrong one, and rotate towards the correct orientation or towards the wrong one. A rough estimate is 1 out of $4^3 = 64$ options. To realize the full W core rotation, all three crossings must move three times into the correct position and orientation. The rotation probability per time is

$$m_{W\text{-strands}} \approx \frac{1}{(64^3)^3} \approx 5.6 \times 10^{-17} . \quad (66)$$

Given that the estimate $1/64$ has an error of at least 30%, and using the maximum elementary particle mass as the mass unit, strands estimate the W boson mass as

$$31 \text{ GeV}/c^2 < m_{W\text{-strands}} < 8.3 \text{ TeV}/c^2 . \quad (67)$$

The estimate is wide but contains the measured value. It is useful to note that the W mass estimate differs from the one for the electron, which has a similar core, because no Dirac trick is necessary to rotate the spin 1 W boson core. The W core rotates more easily than an electron core and thus has a larger mass.

Figure 36 also suggests an estimate for the Z boson mass. The Z boson has spin 1; it has four crossings that must move in two steps. The exponent in the estimate for the rotation probability per time will be 8 instead of 9 for the W boson. The probability that a crossing reaches the position and orientation of the next one will be about $2/3$ of the case of the W boson. This yields

$$m_{Z\text{-strands}} \approx \frac{1}{(96^4)^2} \approx 1.4 \times 10^{-16} , \quad (68)$$

suggesting that the Z boson is 2.5 times heavier than the W boson. This is not the case; the measured mass ratio is 1.13 [75]. Despite the roughness of the estimate, strands solve the *gauge hierarchy* problem. A better estimate for the W and Z boson masses is the subject of research. Such an estimate will allow determining the weak mixing angle *ab initio*.

All particle tangle cores get *flatter* at higher four-momentum. This flattening influences the frequency of Dirac's trick. As a result,

Test 58: Strands imply the *running* of elementary particle masses with four-momentum and *predict* that the calculated runnings with four-momentum *agree with experiment*.

Qualitatively, the deductions from the tangle model agree with the observations and with standard model calculations, such as those by Xing et al. [278] and by Huang and Zhou [279]. Performing a quantitative test of the running of masses is a subject of research.

In total, strands thus appear to explain the origin of particle physics. Strands solve the questions on particle physics raised by Gell-Mann et al. in 1983 [280]. In particular, strands eliminate

supersymmetry, grand unification, and additional particles of any kind, from axions to ‘haplons’. Instead, strands promise to solve the open questions of particle physics, *if* the calculated fundamental constants agree with the observed values.

In short, the fundamental principle of the strand tangle model promises to determine the fundamental constants – the coupling constants, the mixing matrices and the particle masses – from the average shape of particle tangles. The first ab initio estimates are rough but compatible with observations. Doing so, strands explain the lepton mass hierarchy and the gauge hierarchy.

Test 59: The strand tangle model *predicts* that the values for the fundamental constants calculated from the average tangle shapes *will agree with experiments*.

Strands promise precise calculations of the constants with the help of computer simulations. Any mismatch between strand calculations and observations or any different explanation of the fundamental constants would immediately falsify the strand tangle model. In addition, the strand tangle model implies the same perturbation expansions as conventional quantum field theory [129, 130]. The higher orders in the perturbation expansions are due to the more complex tangles arising from shape fluctuations at small scales. This implies

Test 60: The tangle model *predicts* that the standard model with massive mixing Dirac neutrinos is valid at all measurable energies, without any measurable modification, and thus predicts the *lack* of measurable effects *beyond* the standard model.

This conclusion agrees with all observations [75]. [Any decisive test must include the calculation of the fundamental constants.](#)

39 Further experimental tests of the tangle model

The strand tangle model implies a natural *cut-off* at the Planck scale and a well-defined *continuum limit* that arises when the strand radius is assumed to vanish.

Test 61: Strands predict that physical space has *three dimensions* at all measurable scales.

Test 62: Strands predict that there is *only one vacuum state* in nature. In particular, no domain walls between “different” vacuum states exist.

Test 63: Strands imply the uniqueness of the vacuum.

Test 64: Strands predict the lack of vacuum energy in the flat vacuum.

So far, these predictions agree with observations [75]. The predicted lack of trans-Planckian effects includes a lower limit on the effective size of elementary particles:

Test 65: No elementary particle has an intrinsic diameter smaller than the minimum length.

The minimum size of elementary particles could imply non-vanishing electric dipole moments. The most sensitive measurements are for the electron [80, 81]: the experimental upper limit is the elementary charge multiplied by around a thousand Planck lengths. However, the strand tangle model predicts no dipole moment for the electron. Tangles limit electric dipole moments of all elementary particles to a few times the minimum length times the elementary charge. Alas, measuring the electric dipole moment of the W, Z, and the Higgs seems impossible. Also measuring the dipole moment of quarks to such a precision appears out of reach, even by measuring the dipole moment of the neutron.

Deviations from point-like behaviour can also be searched in interactions. However, collider experiments will never reach the required short distances. For the nuclear interactions, the tangle structure *could* lead to cosmological effects in the non-perturbative domain. However, the possibility for detection appears remote [130].

In simple words, direct observation cannot confirm the existence of strand tangles.

Test 66: Tangles predict the lack of measurable deviations from locality in nature.

Test 67: Strands predict that tangles are unobservable.

In the research literature, alternatives to the strand tangle model are rare. Only one further approach attempts to deduce the fundamental constants, the octonion model due to Singh [281, 282]. So far, the octonion model appears to predict additional particles and possibly additional interactions [283]. These have not yet been observed. Other approaches, such as the holomorphic unified field theory by Moffat and Thompson [284] or Finster’s causal fermion systems [285] still contain unexplained parameters. It seems that no further model in the literature incorporating general relativity or even relativistic quantum gravity deduces estimates for all fundamental constants of nature *ab initio*. Conversely, no other attempt to calculate the fundamental constants appears to include general relativity and the standard model with massive neutrinos. The derivation of particles and interactions provided by strands is *hard to vary*; thus it realizes Deutsch’ requirement for a good scientific explanation [286].

In short, strands predict the lack of new physics and *lack of future breakthroughs* in elementary particle physics. Tangles of strands predict that all elementary particle properties are known completely and that no additional observable particle properties will be found. Equivalently, strands predict that the standard model of particle physics *limits* what we humans can achieve and how we can influence our environment. Nevertheless, because strands are not observable, any direct experimental confirmation of particle tangles is excluded. [Tangles can only be tested by calculating the fundamental constants – particle masses, coupling constants, and mixing angles – and their running with four-momentum.](#)

40 Open issues of particle tangles

The above presentation of the strand tangle model may contain inconsistencies or errors. First, it could be that the tangle assignments for the quarks, leptons, or bosons require corrections. [For example, a smooth transition between d quark and anti-d quark is difficult to visualize.](#)

Test 68: Even if specific tangle corrections will be necessary, the strand tangle model is predicted to agree with observations and thus remain valid.

A second open point is the completeness of the classification of the rational 3d tangles given above. For example, when a braid is formed from three sets of two strands each, it is unclear which set of elementary particles corresponds to the resulting configuration.

In short, it is possible that future investigations lead to corrections to the tangle model.

41 Conclusion: strands show that the standard model is simple and elegant

Ciò che per l’universo si squaderna:

...

La forma universal di questo nodo

...

Dante, *Paradiso*, Canto XXXIII, 87, 91.

Starting from the Planck limits, Dirac’s trick, and the ideas of Battey-Pratt and Racey, particles and space are modelled with unobservable fluctuating strands with Planck radius. *Every crossing switch yields a quantum of action \hbar .* This fundamental principle was first proposed by Kauffman.

Because of the fundamental principle, propagating particles are modelled as advancing, rotating, and fluctuating rational 3d *tangles* of unobservable fluctuating strands with Planck radius. Therefore, every particle is connected to the cosmological horizon and is either a fermion or a

boson. The oriented crossing density of a fluctuating fermion tangle reproduces spin $1/2$ and defines its emergent wave function, including its spinor behavior. Oriented crossing densities reproduce the probabilistic behaviour of quantum theory in all details, including superpositions, Hilbert spaces, decoherence, entanglement and the measurement process.

Rational fermion tangles of strands yield the Dirac equation. The strands of the vacuum yield virtual particle-antiparticle pairs. The classification of the possible rational 3d tangles with Reidemeister's theorem yields the three generations of elementary fermions and the elementary bosons, all with their observed quantum numbers. Rational tangles of strands yield massive mixing Dirac neutrinos. The classification of tangle core deformations with the Reidemeister moves yields the gauge interactions and the observed Lie gauge groups. The topology of the rational tangles yields the Higgs mechanism, the breaking of $SU(2)$, lepton mixing, and maximal parity violation of the weak interaction. The Planck radius and the average shapes of particle tangles yield unique elementary particle mass values, coupling constants, and mixing angles.

The text also summarized the results of previous publications. The topology of the elementary rational 3d tangles yields the observed Feynman vertices, particle reactions, and decay modes. Rational tangles of strands yield the quark model, glueballs, and the lack of CP violation in the strong interaction. Rational tangles of strands yield quantum electrodynamics, quantum chromodynamics, and the theory of the weak interaction. Rational tangles of strands yield the complete Lagrangian of the standard model with massive neutrinos, without any modification, in full agreement with observations.

From their tangling, strands yield the three dimensions of space. From their crossing switches, strands yield maximum force, space curvature, Bekenstein's entropy bound, the thermodynamics of black holes and Einstein's field equations.

In short, taken together, these results imply: *Only* strands yield both the Hilbert Lagrangian of general relativity and the standard model Lagrangian with massive mixing neutrinos, **without any modifications**. All consequences deduced from the fundamental principle of the strand tangle model are in full agreement with observations. Strands allow *everybody* to understand quantum mechanics **and should be useful for teaching quantum theory**. Strands predict the lack of new physics and the possibility of calculating the observed fundamental constants to high precision, including their running with four-momentum. As usual in physics, all these statements can be falsified with a single counterexample; it would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model. **Strands show the simplicity of nature – and of the standard model.**

42 Outlook: calculations can be faster than experiments

Strands offer many research challenges in mathematical physics. Exploring the Heisenberg picture of quantum theory will deepen understanding. Deducing Schwinger's quantum action principle from strands is of interest. Deducing the Dyson–Schwinger equations and the Ward–Takahashi identity from strands of zero radius is attractive. Deducing axiomatic quantum field theory from tangles of zero radius is worthwhile. The relation between crossings, qubits, entanglement, and quantum gravity should be explored further. The consequences of strands for entanglement entropy and for quantum measurements should be examined. The relation of rotating tangles to Hestenes' geometric algebra should be studied. Animations of particle propagators and Feynman vertices will be useful. Exploring perturbation theory and renormalization in quantum field theory and quantum gravity is promising; an example is the Kinoshita–Lee–Nauenberg theorem [287]. Ultraviolet issues and questions about anomalies will become more accessible using strands. Non-perturbative effects in quantum field theory are more accessible with strands.

In cosmology, a definitive estimate of the cosmological constant from strands should be derived, including its time dependency or lack thereof. The latest explorations in this domain tend to confirm the approach by Wiltshire et al. [288], who explain the cosmological constant, dark energy, and the acceleration of the expansion of the universe as effects resulting from the specific position of our galaxy in the universe. Strands appear to confirm that the effects attributed to the cosmological constant are apparent and not fundamental, and that the cosmological constant vanishes.

In the domain of numerical simulations, precise calculation methods for the fundamental constants and their running with four-momentum should be developed. The study of the quantification of the geometric shape and chirality of tangle cores should be intensified. Exploring the rotation of asymmetric and tethered bodies in viscous flows will lead to better approximations for the mass values of elementary and composite particles. Numerical quantum chromodynamics is expected to be enhanced. Geometric *ab initio* approximations for quark and neutrino mixing, for the Higgs mechanism, and for the W and Z masses should be developed. All such calculations are predicted to agree with the measurements. Any lack of agreement would immediately refute the strand tangle model.

In short, with a manageable effort, strands will allow the calculation of neutrino masses and mixing angles before they are measured.

Acknowledgments and declarations

The author thanks Thomas Racey, Lou Kauffman, and Michel Talagrand for valuable exchanges. The author also thanks Bernd Thaller, Isabella Borgogelli Avveduti, Saverio Pascazio, Eric Rawdon, Luca Bombelli, Volodimir Simulik, Sergei Fadeev, Peter Schiller, Rodolfo Gambini, and Jorge Pullin for fruitful discussions. Part of this work was supported by a grant from Klaus Tschira via his Klaus Tschira Foundation. The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest or competing interests. No additional data are associated with this work.

Appendix

A On deducing general relativity and all of nature from strands

In the strand tangle model, everything observed in the universe – particles, space and horizons – is composed of strands of Planck radius. The corresponding strand structures are illustrated in Figure 41. Thus

- ▷ The universe is expected to be one long closed strand – i.e., a strand with the topology of a ring – that crisscrosses all of nature and forms space, particles and horizons.

However, the statement is not unique; the universe could also consist of a finite number of closed strands. Figure 42 illustrates the strand tangle model of cosmology.

- ▷ With time, the universal strand(s) tangle(s) up.

The simplest possible case of a single strand thus realizes Heraclitus' idea that everything in nature is connected to everything else. In addition, nature is a unity without exact parts.

In the strand tangle model, *flat empty space*, the flat vacuum, is a homogenous aggregate composed of fluctuating *untangled strands*, packed as densely as possible. The lack of tangles implies the lack of particles. At large scales, the strand aggregate forming the vacuum is homogeneous.

Figure 41: Homogeneous untangled aggregates of strands from *flat* space, inhomogeneous aggregates from *curved* space, weaves of strands from horizons, and rational tangles from particles. The present text concentrates on particles; for the exploration of space, curvature, and black hole horizons, and for the deduction of black hole entropy and Einstein’s field equations, see references [58] and [59].

The strand fluctuations yield isotropy and Lorentz invariance, and avoid the difficulty that static discrete or finite models cannot achieve these properties [289]. *Curved space* is an *inhomogeneous aggregate* of untangled strands, in which some strand pairs are twisted, i.e., meet again, and represent real gravitons or virtual gravitons, i.e., spatial curvature. *Black hole horizons* are one-sided *weaves* of strands. Because the Planck limits are part of the fundamental principle of the strand tangle model, strands of Planck radius imply the maximum force $c^4/4G$. As shown elsewhere [58, 59, 127], strands imply the usual expressions for black hole mass, the moment of inertia of black holes, black hole entropy and black hole temperature. The usual logarithmic correction to black hole entropy also arises – but it is unmeasurably small. Despite their numerous tethers, black holes can still rotate with the help of Dirac’s trick. In the strand model of black holes, for an observer at spatial infinity, mass is distributed over the horizon. This mass distribution explains the non-vanishing moment of inertia of black holes deduced by Ha [290]. All these results are as expected.

Using the existing literature, it is straightforward to prove that strands and their properties

Figure 42: The whole universe is expected to consist of a single closed strand. (Several closed strands are also a possibility.) The early universe (top) and the present universe (bottom) are illustrated.

imply general relativity, i.e., Einstein's field equations and the Hilbert Lagrangian, without any measurable deviation. In nature, maximum force $c^4/4G$ alone implies general relativity, as shown in [12, 14, 21, 48, 58, 59]. The derivation is a further example of how a fundamental inequality, in this case the Planck limit $F \leq c^4/4G$, leads to precise equations of motion. The derivation of general relativity from maximum force is independent of the strand model. However, strands contain maximum force in the fundamental principle: maximum force is the maximum local force that can arise on a particle. Maximum force is the ratio of the Planck energy and the minimum length. Strands thus confirm the maximum force and thus imply general relativity. Because strands imply general relativity without any deviation, all properties of gravitation deduced from strands agree with all experiments, as reviewed by Will [51]. Also all LIGO observations about gravitational waves confirm general relativity. In particular, no black hole merger exceeds the power limit $P \leq c^5/4G$ [49, 50, 291], and thus none of the other black hole limits, such as maximum force $c^4/4G$, mass flow rate $c^3/4G$, and mass per length $c^2/4G$.

Strands thus predict that *no* new effect of relativistic quantum gravity can be observed [58, 59].

Test 69: Deviations from continuous space-time or from classical relativistic gravity will not be observed, single gravitons will not be detected, the Planck scales will never be reached, and the equivalence principle will be confirmed in all measurable situations.

In nature, all observed fields are particle densities composed of elementary particle fields. In the strand model, all elementary particle fields are *rational 3d tangles* of strands. Every elementary particle is effectively a *defect* in space. This old idea has been explored by many researchers, including Hehl and Kröner [292] or Kleinert [293]. Searching for all the possible defect structures in the strand vacuum only yields horizons and particles, and no other possibilities [58, 59]:

Test 70: Strands predict that nature has no domain walls, line defects, cosmic strings, singularities, white holes, space-time foam, wormholes or non-trivial topology.

For gravitons, the usual Feynman diagrams arise [294]. Strands solve the problems of gravitational collapse listed by Misner, Thorne and Wheeler about general relativity [295]: strands eliminate wormholes, describe space-time fluctuations, prevent singularities, describe spin 1/2 and explain dimensionality – all this with a specific type of pregeometry, different from but similar to the one they explored and dismissed in their Figure 44.3. In particular, strands and their tangling also imply that physical space cannot have fewer or more than three dimensions.

The strand tangle model of cosmology is illustrated in Figure 42. Strands predict the existence of a cosmological horizon. The tangle model defines a preferred reference frame, namely the frame in which the cosmological horizon and the cosmic background radiation are isotropic. This is also the natural reference frame to observe the maximum possible elementary particle energy, $\sqrt{\hbar c^5/4G}$, if the value were achievable. This description with Planck limits resembles the approach by Amelino-Camelia [296]. In highly boosted reference frames, the background formed by horizon strands would not be isotropic and the derivation of the Dirac equation in Part III would not apply. However, at all realistic boost values, deviations from the Dirac equation are unmeasurable. In addition, strands confirm that the idea of ‘wave function of the universe’ makes no sense because at cosmological scales there is no distinction between fields and space nor is there any outside observer. Strands also imply the lack of inflation. As mentioned above, strands suggest the lack of elementary dark matter particles. Strands also suggest the lack of dark energy. Both options appear to agree with observations, as argued by Wiltshire and his group [288, 297].

In short, in the strand tangle model, *all* systems found in nature – particles of radiation and matter, flat and curved space, cosmological and black hole horizons – consist of strands. Strands imply that black hole horizons have the usual entropy. **Strands imply that space curvature and gravitation are described by Einstein’s field equations, without any measurable deviation, in agreement with all experiments.** Finally, strands yield an unusual model of cosmology, without dark energy, without dark matter, and without inflation, that appears to agree with observations. **Any deviation from these predictions immediately falsified the strand model and its fundamental principle.**

B On qubits and Urs

Qubits, a contraction of ‘quantum bits’, play an important role in quantum computing and in relativistic quantum gravity. In modern quantum computing research, physical qubits are commonly realized as trapped ions, quantum dots, nitrogen-vacancy defects in diamonds, or superconducting loops. The state of a qubit can be visualized with the Bloch sphere, which illustrates the SU(2) structure of the qubit state space [298–300]. In quantum computing, quantum gates are represented by unitary operators. The different types of quantum gates can be represented as different operations on the Bloch sphere.

The strand tangle model for fermions – as illustrated in Figure 20, Figure 22 and Figure 23 – is useful for visualizing qubits. *In the strand tangle model, the Bloch sphere describes the orientation of the tangle core and the twisting of its tethers.* In the strand tangle model, unitary operators are represented by strand deformations that keep the average shape of the tangle core untouched, but change the core orientation in space. In this way, a non-trivial tangle visualizes a single-qubit state, and many non-trivial tangles visualize multi-qubit states.

The quest to construct nature from qubits is not new. A ‘qubit’ is the modern expression for the ‘Ur’, the fundamental and continuous alternative, described by $SU(2)$, that Weizsäcker introduced in the 1970s [301, 302]. Weizsäcker dreamt of deducing all laws of nature by building them from Urs [303]. (The correct German plural is ‘Ure’.) The research approach was also explored by Kober [304] and by Lyre [305, 306]. The fundamental principle of Figure 5, which generates $SU(2)$, can be seen as the simplest possible realization of an Ur. Thus, the strand tangle model can be said to realize Weizsäcker’s wish: *nature is built of Urs.*

In 2001, Zizzi formulated the aim of this quest with the expression ‘it from qubit’ [307]. It has become common to ask questions about qubits in the context of relativistic quantum gravity. How can one imagine a region of space-time that includes vacuum, matter and particles in terms of qubits? In particular, do qubits form lattices, random structures, or other types of structures? Is the number of qubits finite, countably infinite or uncountably infinite? Such questions concern the microscopic, Planck-scale constituents of nature as a whole [308].

Given the possibility of describing quantum theory, gravity and quantum field theory with strand tangles [58, 127–129], relations between tangles and qubits arise almost immediately. Given that space, curvature and particles are due to strands and their tangling, one can interpret the fundamental principle of Figure 5 as a maximally simplified qubit. Indeed, as long as the strand segments are kept close to each other in a crossed configuration, the two strand segments can be seen as a simplified belt buckle realizing $SU(2)$. In other words, a strand crossing is a qubit.

The fluctuations of the strands continuously change the structure and the interdependencies of the crossings – the qubits – in nature. Strands clarify that the number of their crossings – the number of qubits – is countable in principle, but that it is not fixed. [With this interpretation of the tangle model, strands can be said to confirm that *nature is built of qubits.* \(Stretching the analogy even more, one could claim that quaternions are at the basis of nature.\)](#)

An approach to qubits similar to that of strands arose recently. In 2016, Freedman and Headrick introduced *bit threads* to describe entanglement, holography and the Ryu-Takayanagi entropy [309]. Central to the idea of bit threads is the hope that space can be seen as a consequence of the entanglement of filiform entities with Planck-sized diameter [310]. Various authors explored the topic [311–318]. It is expected that with time, research on bit threads will retrace that on strands.

In short, strand tangles are useful tools for teaching and visualizing qubits in quantum computing. In the field of relativistic quantum gravity, the fundamental principle can be seen as a specific version of building ‘it from qubit’ and ‘nature and her laws from Urs’.

C On quantum fields

Traditionally, quantum fields are introduced as part of the axioms of quantum field theory [319]. In particular, quantum field theory defines fields assuming *point-like* particles and using *local* commutator relations and operator-valued *local* densities. In the description of nature provided by quantum field theory, the fundamental constants – particle masses, couplings and mixing angles – must be added by hand and cannot be explained. Instead, strands propose a different view, because the minimum length prevents using local operators or distributions as fundamental concepts.

- ▷ In the strand tangle model, *quantum fields* emerge from fluctuating *rational 3d tangles* made of strands with Planck radius.

The traditional, axiomatic quantum field concept with local behavior is an *approximation* to the tangle definition of fields. All concepts of axiomatic field theory, from C^* -algebras to fibre bundles, are approximations. Traditional axiomatic local quantum field theory only arises when strands are approximated to have *zero radius* and, in the path integral formulation, tangle cores are approximated to be point-like.

The strand tangle model reproduces *particle creation* by tangling, particle *annihilation* by untangling, particle *absorption* by tangle transfer or combination, particle *mixing* by braiding and unbraiding, particle *emission* by tangle separation, and particle *reactions* by strand rearrangements. (Knots, knotted tangles, ribbons, or other topological structures do not reproduce virtual particles or the observed particle reactions.) The strand description of quantum operators as deformations of tangle cores given in Section 14 yields the description of particle creation and annihilation as operators. The two operators *tangle* or *untangle* strands; equivalently, they *braid* or *unbraid* strands. Both operators are *almost* local, realizing the observational constraints and theoretical demands. Both operators ensure that the number of particles is always an *integer*. Strands thus eliminate the need for ‘second quantization’ – and for any other type of quantization. The tangle model eliminates the need for superselection rules. Nevertheless, the general strand description of operators as deformations of tangle cores yields the usual result that quantum fields are operator-valued distributions [289] – in the limit of vanishing strand radius.

The strand tangle model reproduces all effects traditionally attributed to quantum field theory. As a consequence, in the strand tangle model, an expression such as ‘an electron is an excitation of the electron field’ is misleading or even wrong. More drastically, concepts such as ‘electron field’ or ‘neutrino field’ make no sense. In the strand tangle model, particles are excitations of the common vacuum. Each field, each ‘excitation’, is a specific way of tangling vacuum strands.

Strands simplify quantum field theory in other ways. Whenever space is assumed to be described by a lattice, the Nielsen–Ninomiya theorem implies the necessity of doubling the number of chiral fermions [320–322]. This theorem has generated numerous studies on its extensions and limitations. The theorem is also the reason for various difficulties in numerical simulations of elementary particles. In the strand tangle model, because of the minimum length, space is *not* a lattice and thus has no Brillouin zone. Therefore, the strand tangle model does not realize the conditions for the doubling of fermions and the no-go theorem published by Nielsen and Ninomiya.

In 1955, Haag proved that an interacting quantum field theory is mathematically inconsistent. The proof is based on continuous space, on the properties of vacuum polarization and on its behaviour under renormalization [323, 324]. However, given that nature is *not* characterized by continuous space, *nor* by continuous observables, *nor* by local operators, the conditions for the theorem are not satisfied. Once more, strands simplify quantum field theory.

In the tangle model, because of the minimum length, the issue of ultraviolet completeness loses its importance and effectively dissolves. The same happens with renormalization, even in the case of quantum gravity. Also anomalies, which were so important in the early days of superstring theory, lose their importance.

In short, fluctuating tangles and their crossing densities reproduce, visualize, and define both wave functions and quantum fields. **Both wave functions and quantum fields emerge from the fundamental principle of the strand tangle model and thus from a common and unique vacuum state, as observed.** Additional simplifying aspects of strands are presented in the following appendices.

D On preons

In 1979, both Harari [325] and Shupe [326] proposed models of composite quarks and leptons. In both models, there are only two fundamental particles, which Harari called *rishons* and Shupe *quips*. Nowadays, such hypothetical particles are generally called *preons*. Both approaches assumed that the preons had a charge $e/3$, anti-preons $-e/3$ and that leptons were composed of three preons, as already proposed earlier on [327]. Shupe explored states with fewer and more preons as models for gauge bosons and gravitons, deduced the vanishing mass of preons and tried to model Feynman diagrams.

Many explorations of preon models followed and continue to this day, too numerous to mention all [328–335]. However, approaches that attempted to add interactions or dynamics to preons had no success. Likewise, preons do not explain the fundamental constants or general relativity. In retrospect, this lack of success resulted from the insistence on finding a new Lagrangian with new symmetries and on retaining the idea of point particles, despite the evidence, summarized in Section 2, against this approach.

A partial solution is offered by the fascinating preon approach by Bilson-Thompson, based on braided ribbons [117–121], which has generated various subsequent studies. The approach developed a topological model for a generation of elementary particles. Despite their similarity to strands, ribbons do not seem to explain wave functions, the gauge groups, the fundamental constants, or general relativity. However, replacing each ribbon edge with a strand yields an approach similar to the strand tangle model and could yield new insights.

If instead, one starts from strands and calls a strand crossing a ‘preon’ and its mirror inverse an ‘anti-preon’, one finds several similarities to preon models: ‘preons’ have fractional electric charge $\pm e/3$, they are massless, and their composites form both fermions and bosons. However, such preons do not explain the gauge groups, whereas strands do.

In short, point-like preons seem to be more similar to fundamental quantum numbers and to strand crossings than to fundamental particles. Ribbon-like preons do not seem to provide a unified description. It appears that tangles of strands solve the problems that preons leave open: strands explain wave functions, describe the quantum of action \hbar , and deduce the gauge groups, the fundamental constants, and general relativity.

E On superstrings and supermembranes

At first sight, strands differ from superstrings and supermembranes in several respects. Superstrings are characterized by Planck tension, have a Lagrangian, live in 10 dimensions, realize dualities, carry supersymmetric superfields and possibly imply grand unification [336, 337]. Superstrings have been generalized to various types of supermembranes, including D-branes. In contrast, strands have no tension or Lagrangian, generate and populate the usual $3 + 1$ dimensions, carry no fields or other observables and exclude supersymmetry and grand unification. There is only one type of strand: unobservable, fluctuating, filiform entities with Planck radius.

At second sight, the differences between strands and superstrings might be much smaller. If one adds two ‘strand surface coordinates’ for each strand, a higher number of dimensions can be imagined to arise. Elementary particles with three strands, with two surface dimensions each, would then yield a ten-dimensional space-time. Calabi-Yau manifolds might arise as the shape of the vacuum between strands.

For D-branes, and possibly for other types of supermembranes, the Planck tension might disappear. These types of supermembranes respect the Planck limits like strands do. Like strands, such

types of supermembranes arise in finite numbers in finite volumes of three-dimensional space. If one imagines that the superstring tension is responsible for forming strands, the resulting strands might nevertheless be wobbly, as is assumed in the strand tangle model. Strands might thus be seen as *tubular supermembranes*. Indeed, some recent versions of superstring theory [338] describe the three-dimensional vacuum in a way that resembles a strand aggregate.

Strands include non-commutativity. An aggregate of strands resembles a fermionic space. Supersymmetry may be seen as a result of assuming ubiquitous strand crossing switches. There might be a way to reconcile the two approaches.

In the strand tangle model, crossing switches yield observable Lagrangians. In the case of superstrings, the original Lagrangian(s), including the Polyakov action, might only be a bookkeeping tool, not a real observable Lagrangian. The fundamental supersymmetry assumed in superstring theory might not be observable, nor might its super-Lie group. Indeed, supersymmetry is not observed. Experiments also imply that the idea of grand unification, often assumed to exist in superstring theory [336, 337], must be abandoned. The assumption could simply be dropped.

Finally, superstring theory uses dualities of various kinds. Among them, *holography* is a duality defined with the statement that “the entire information content of a quantum gravity theory in a given volume can be encoded in an effective theory at the boundary surface of this volume” [339]. A specific example of gauge-gravity duality in superstring theory is the one between anti-de Sitter space and conformal field theory, often AdS/CFT duality [337]. So far, there is no experimental evidence for anti-de Sitter space, for conformal field theory, for AdS-CFT duality, for any other duality, and for any of their consequences. The last appendix even shows that ‘information’ in relativistic quantum gravity contradicts experiments.

Superstring dualities can be compared with the statements and results of the strand tangle model. At first sight, there is no correspondence, because superstring dualities assume the existence of arbitrarily small distances and of local operators. Also, as shown above, strands fix the possible gauge interactions, fix the values of coupling constants, and fix the number of dimensions of space. None of these properties can be varied, as is often done in duality research. Strands imply that gauge interactions are due to tangle core deformations and that gravity is due to tether deformations. At Planck scales, the two descriptions meet and must merge. But because the Planck scale is unattainable, strands also predict that the merging of the two descriptions cannot be observed. Strands further imply that neither description has implications for the other one. However, there is a non-vanishing chance that in the approximation of vanishing strand radius, even in three space dimensions, some superstring dualities might arise also in the strand tangle model.

In short, there should exist a mapping between certain supermembranes and strands. Superstring theory has not yet managed to transform the statement ‘particles are vibrating superstrings or supermembranes’ into a concrete model for particles and interactions. Mapping rolled-up supermembranes to tangles of strands should enable doing so.

F On the Yang-Mills millennium problem

In the year 2000, the Clay Mathematics Institute asked, in its list of millennium problems, to prove the existence of a non-trivial quantum field theory for every non-Abelian compact simple gauge group in continuous flat space-time. The problem, formulated by Witten and Jaffe [340], also asks to prove that each such quantum field theory leads to a finite mass gap. In the millennium problem, a quantum field theory is defined as a structure realizing the axioms of Streater and Wightman, as well as those of Osterwalder and Schrader. All these axioms are based on perfect locality and continuous quantum fields. This millennium problem has two aspects: a *physical* aspect about

nature and a *mathematical* aspect about axiomatic quantum field theory.

The *physical* aspect of the Yang-Mills millennium problem is answered both by nature and by the strand tangle model. Because of the minimum length, in nature, continuous space-time does not exist. In nature, additional gauge groups do not exist: only the two nuclear interactions are observed to be non-Abelian gauge theories. Experiments thus answer the millennium problem *negatively*. Strands confirm these observations by excluding *every* imaginable alternative to the standard model with massive Dirac neutrinos: because of the existence of just three Reidemeister moves and of the minimum length, additional gauge groups and additional gauge particles are impossible, as told in the main section of this article. Strands clarify the relation between the three dimensions of space, the three possible gauge groups and the three fermion generations. In particular, strands imply that the emergence of three-dimensional space and the lack of higher gauge groups are two sides of the same coin. Strands, like experiments, thus answer the physics challenge that motivated the millennium problem *negatively*.

In addition, *any* unified description of nature will answer the physical aspect of the millennium problem negatively. Whatever the unified description may be, it does not comply with the assumptions of spatial continuity and of locality in the Yang-Mills millennium problem. Whatever the unified description may be, it will, by definition, explain why the observed three-dimensionality arises at low energies. Whatever the unified description may be, it will, by definition, explain why only the observed gauge interactions exist. Whatever the unified description may be, it will, by definition, explain why only the observed particle masses and couplings occur.

In summary, if the Yang-Mills millennium problem is restricted to the *physical* aspect – the existence and mass gap of gauge theories *in nature* – observations and any unified theory conclude that additional Yang-Mills theories do not exist. The best one can do is to restrict the Yang-Mills millennium problem to proving the existence of a finite mass gap in the case of the gauge group $SU(3)$ of the strong nuclear interaction. The $SU(3)$ case has a positive answer, due to the existence of glueballs – both in observations [75] and in the strand tangle model [130].

The *mathematical* aspect of the millennium problem also has issues. *Continuous* space is in contrast with the minimum length and time in nature. Continuous flat space provides no length or time units. All length or time units are tied to the quantum of action \hbar . Therefore, continuous space without length or time units is *in contrast* with quantum field theory. But there is more.

In mathematics, one can choose to ignore nature and physics and assume both continuity and quantum field theory at the same time. This leads to a further issue. The statement of the millennium problem defines a quantum field theory as a structure realizing specific axioms. The axioms assume that the quantum of action \hbar and the speed of light c are finite. Now, exact space continuity implies that the Planck length is zero. This implies that the gravitational constant G must vanish. A vanishing G is in contrast to observations. A vanishing G also implies that mass units cannot be defined, that mass values *cannot* be measured and thus that mass cannot be defined. However, the Yang-Mills millennium problem explicitly asks for a mass value.

In mathematics, one can choose to ignore nature and physics and assume continuity, quantum field theory, and non-vanishing G . However, if one insists that G is finite after all, then one has a non-vanishing minimum length. The minimum length implies that there are no points, no sets, and no axioms, as deduced in detail in Appendix G. Quantum field theory and finite G , taken together, thus imply that there is *no* axiomatic quantum field theory. However, the Yang-Mills millennium problem asks for such a theory.

In mathematics, one can choose to ignore nature, mathematics and physics further and assume both that continuity and axiomatic quantum field theory are valid at the same time. The two assumptions, taken together, imply the description of particles as exact point particles. This purely

mathematical result contradicts general relativity: no object can be smaller than the Schwarzschild radius determined by its mass. Thus, the concepts of ‘particle’ and ‘quantum field’ assumed in the millennium problem contradict general relativity and have no relation to actual particles in nature or actual quantum fields. The two mathematical assumptions have a further consequence. Different elementary particles differ at least at the Planck scale. Only Planck scale differences explain the existence of different types of quarks and leptons. Eliminating the Planck scale by assuming point particles implies that the existence of different elementary particles cannot be derived but must be *assumed*. In particular, assuming point particles also prevents deducing whether additional elementary gauge bosons exist. Therefore, it is impossible to derive whether additional gauge interactions with additional gauge groups exist. It is equally impossible to derive whether additional particles exist, such as generalizations of glueballs for additional gauge interactions. Thus, it is impossible to deduce the existence of any additional mass gap. However, the Yang-Mills millennium problem asks for additional gauge theories and for additional mass gaps.

In short, the speed limit c , the quantum of action \hbar and the maximum force $c^4/4G$ imply a minimum length, the lack of continuity of space, and the lack of perfect locality. The Planck limits lead to the emergence of wave functions, quantum field theory, gauge theories, elementary particles, measurement units, mass, physical observables and the three dimensions. In contrast, the Yang-Mills millennium problem starts with different assumptions: continuity of space, perfect three-dimensionality, perfect locality, point-like particles, axiomatic quantum field theory, predetermined gauge bosons, and predetermined mass generation mechanisms. **Because of the logical contradictions among the assumptions, a mathematical proof of the existence of additional Yang-Mills theories and of their mass gaps is impossible.** The only known explanation for the gauge theories and their gauge groups, the strand tangle model, implies the lack of any Yang-Mills theory beyond SU(3) and deduces the existence of a finite mass gap for SU(3) [130].

G On physics’ axioms and Hilbert’s sixth problem

The following arguments do not rely on strands. However, strands allow visualizing them.

Combining maximum speed c , the quantum of action \hbar and maximum force $c^4/4G$ yields a minimum length in nature, given by twice the Planck length. The minimum length is also the minimum possible length measurement error. The same applies to time. Therefore, measurement results without errors are impossible – for every physical observable.

The lack of exact measurement results for all physical observables implies the *lack of sharp boundaries* in nature. Thus, there is no *exact* way to distinguish two observable values or even two objects. In nature, therefore, there is no exact way to separate space into separate regions. At the Planck scale, nature is inherently fuzzy. Nature has no parts that can be distinguished *exactly*. In simple words, nature has no parts.

The lack of sharp boundaries and of parts implies the *lack of sets* in nature. The lack of exact distinctions and of exact parts implies the impossibility of defining *elements* in nature. These conclusions apply to nature near the Planck scale, thus to the foundations of nature.

The lack of parts, elements, and sets due to the Planck limits has two consequences. Information consists of bits, i.e., of distinguishable states. Such distinctions are impossible at the Planck scale. The first consequence is: *nature neither consists of information nor does information describe nature.*

In mathematics, all axioms are based on distinctions, elements, sets, and boundaries. However, all these concepts do not exist in nature because of the minimum length and time measurement errors. Therefore, the minimum length implies a second consequence: physics as a whole *cannot*

be based on axioms. Hilbert's dream [341], most clearly stated in his sixth problem [342, 343], in which he asked for an axiomatic system for all of physics, *cannot* be realized whenever gravity and quantum theory are combined. Likewise, because the minimum length excludes elements and sets, it circumvents Gödel's consistency problems [344].

In contrast, *branches* of physics *can* be based on axioms. Axioms are possible in quantum field theory without gravity, or in relativistic gravity without quantum theory – because in these domains the minimum length does *not* arise. In branches of physics, length and time measurements without errors and with infinite precision *can* be assumed. As became clear above, assuming strands of vanishing radius as constituents of nature instead of points reproduces (axiomatic) quantum field theory. Likewise, assuming strands of vanishing radius reproduces (axiomatic) general relativity. Only the combination of quantum theory and general relativity introduces minimum measurement errors, requires strands of Planck radius, and thus eliminates the possibility of defining axioms.

Despite the impossibility of unified axioms, a complete and unified description of nature remains possible, as long as it is *logically circular*. Such a logically circular description is automatically introduced when using space and time to describe nature. Even though space and time are approximations, they *must* be used to talk about nature. There is no way to describe nature without space and time. The Planck limit c , \hbar , $4G$ and $k \ln 2$ – and thus all measured quantities, directly or indirectly – contain the metre and the second in their units and use space and time in their fundamental implementations. Space, time, and boundaries are necessary for thinking, defining information, and communicating. Even the act of counting requires space and time. A description of nature without a space-time background is impossible. A logically circular description is automatically introduced when using particles and space to describe physical systems. In nature, space is defined with the help of rulers, thus with the help of particles. In nature, particles are defined as localized structures in space. As became clear above, strands reduce, but maintain this logical circularity: in the strand tangle model, (background) space and time are part of the fundamental principle, while, at the same time, (physical) space and time arise from averaging strands. Likewise, tangles define particles, and at the same time, untangled tangles define space.

The first mathematical proposal that eliminated exact parts was by Kauffman [345, 346]. In his proposal, all sets and elements are approximate concepts that result from the folding of a unique fundamental entity. Kauffman's proposal is realized by the fundamental principle of Figure 5. In the strand tangle model, nature consists of a single closed strand (or a small number of them) and all *parts* are approximate. The strand tangle model confirms the unity of nature and its lack of exact parts. All so-called 'parts' of nature – points, instants, particles – are low-energy approximations.

In short, every unified description of motion incorporating relativistic quantum gravity implies minimum measurement errors for length and time, each given by twice the Planck unit. Therefore, precise distinctions, sets, and elements are impossible at the Planck scale – and so is an *axiomatic* theory of relativistic quantum gravity. The lack of axioms requires that any unified description of nature must be *logically circular* and contain *no parts*. In other words, the Planck limits eliminate reductionism, though in a gentle way: reductionism disappears only at the unattainable Planck scale. Although relativistic quantum gravity implies that points and instants do not exist, *emergent* space and time made of points and instants *must* be used as *communication tools* to describe nature. Fluctuating strands with a Planck radius whose crossing switches define the quantum of

action realize these aspects and requirements. No other option appears possible.

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